

ANTECEDENT-ANAPHOR RELATIONS IN
THE ÒLU DIALECT OF ÌGBÒ

BY

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A THESIS IN THE DEPARTMENT OF LINGUISTICS AND AFRICAN
LANGUAGES SUBMITTED TO THE FACULTY OF ARTS IN PARTIAL
FULFILMENT OF THE REQUIREMENTS FOR THE DEGREE OF

DOCTOR OF PHILOSOPHY
OF THE
UNIVERSITY OF IBADAN

MAY, 1998

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DEDICATION

To God

and

To the entire members of my

Family

CERTIFICATION

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ACKNOWLEDGEMENT

I wish to use this opportunity to express my deep appreciation to all those who have contributed in various ways towards the successful completion of this work.

I am highly indebted to Rev. Mother M.A.N. Uwalaka who supervised this thesis. I thank her for her patience and understanding all through the stages of this work. More importantly, there is no way I can sufficiently show my appreciation to mother and her D.D.L. Sisters of No 5 Sankore Avenue, University of Ibadan. However, I thank them for their hospitality.

I also thank Professor K. Owolabi of the Department of Linguistics and African Languages for his interest and advice in the course of this work. My gratitude also goes to Arc. A.U. Awuzie who was responsible for the production of one of the drafts of this thesis.

Let me thank Chief G.A. Ibe, Mr C.C. Okorienta, Mr D.U. Aliakor, and my childhood friend, Ethel A. Nzeogu for their financial support. To all my friends and colleagues, I owe

you a lot of thanks for your goodwill and encouragement.

To the entire members of my family - my sibling brothers and sisters and their families - I say thanks for your care and concern. I am grateful to my Mama who has sacrificed a lot on my behalf. I sincerely thank my wife, Uju for her love and interest in my work. Equally also, I thank our dear children - Chinonye, Chukwudaalu, Chiamaka, Chikezie, and Chinedum - for what they have endured for my sake.

Finally, I give thanks and glory to God for his abiding mercies.

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LIST OF ABBREVIATIONS

ST	-	Standard Theory
EST	-	Extended Standard Theory
SD	-	Structural Description
SC	-	Structural Change
NSR	-	Nuclear Stress Rule
HT	-	High Tone
LT	-	Low Tone
pst	-	Past Tense
Appl	-	Applicative
Perf	-	Perfective
Ben	-	Benefactive
Aux	-	Auxiliary
pl	-	Plural
sg	-	Singular
2pl	-	Second Person Plural
Cst	-	Causative
Procl	-	Proclitic
COMIT	-	Comitative
Stat	-	Stative
Fut	-	Future
Coref	-	Coreferential
Poss	-	Possessor
Hd	-	Head

Recip	-	Reciprocal
Refl	-	Reflexive
Pron	-	Pronoun (Pronominal)
Ana	-	Anaphor
Symm	-	Symmetrical
Diff	-	Differentiated
Imp	-	Imperative
Subj	-	Subject
Obj	-	Object
Poss	-	Possessive
G-B	-	Government-Binding
LF	-	Logical Form
PF	-	Phonetic Form
Tns	-	Tense
AGR	-	Agreement
AGR _i	-	Agreement with subject NP
INFL	-	Inflection
E.C.M.	-	Exceptional Case Marking
ECP	-	Empty Category Principle
A-/A-	-	Argument/NonArgument
CFC	-	Complete Functional Complex
IP	-	Inflection Phrase
CP	-	Complementizer Phrase
Lit.	-	Literal

C	-	Complementizer
S	-	Sentence
TOP	-	Topic
Spec	-	Specifier
NP	-	Noun Phrase
VP	-	Verb Phrase
AP	-	Adjective Phrase
PP	-	Prepositional Phrase
N	-	Noun
V	-	Verb
A	-	Adjective
P	-	Preposition
PRO	-	Abstract Pronominal Subject of an infinitive phrase
LHR	-	Lefthand Head Rule
RHR	-	Righthand Head Rule
CONJ	-	Conjunction
IC	-	Inherent Complement
PREF	-	Prefix

ABSTRACT

This study investigates instances of antecedent-anaphor relations in the Oly dialect of Igbo. The relations in question involve the Reflexive/Reciprocal anaphor, and the ergatively derived NP-trace. For our theoretical framework, we adopt Chomsky's Government-Binding Theory (1981(a), 1981(b), 1986(a) and (1986(b)). This model has been adopted extensively in the analysis of linguistic data from European languages. But it has not been widely applied to data from African languages. We therefore adopt the said theoretical framework for our analysis, in order to evaluate the extent to which it can be applied to a set of Igbo data.

Though the Government-Binding theory accounts for much of the data in this study, there is a set of data which seem to counter-exemplify some of the claims of the theory. For instance, we observe that in Igbo an infinitival clause can co-occur with a lexicalized subject which functions as the antecedent of a reflexive anaphor. In such a case, we postulate the 'copula verb complementizer' by to license the lexicalized subject of the infinitival clause. There is also the case of lack of an α -command relationship between an

antecedent and its anaphor in $[-\text{Spec}, \text{CP}]$ position.

Here, we claim that the m -command relationship is mediated by the trace of the displaced anaphor in $[-\text{Spec}, \text{CP}]$ through the chain transmission mechanism.

Furthermore, we find that an anaphor in a subjectless imperative sentence can take its antecedent from an abstract pronominal element pro. We claim that this pronominal element is supplemented by the $[+\text{AGR}]$ features inherited by the pronominal clitic o- $\emptyset$ or -nu for the singular and plural subjectless imperative sentences respectively. Finally, we observe that the Binding Theory is silent over the precedence relation between an antecedent and its anaphor. Though there is an assumption that an antecedent should precede its anaphor at S-structure we find a set of Igbo data involving the co-arguments of experiential/psych verbs in which the precedence relation does not hold.

CHAPTER ONE

INTRODUCTION

1.0 Characteristics of Anaphors

The class of nominal expressions in language is grouped into three sub-classes: anaphors, pronominals, and referential expressions (R-expressions). Reflexives, reciprocals, and NP-traces constitute the class of anaphors (Chomsky 1981(a): 101, May 1981(a): 220, Aoun 1985:1). Whereas reflexives and reciprocals are lexical or overt anaphors, an NP-trace, as the name implies, is non-overt or non-lexical. The class of pronominals are such noun phrases (NPs) as personal pronouns, PRO, and pro. PRO and pro are non-overt, while personal pronouns are overtly realized. R-expressions include proper names, and wh-traces. Like NP-traces, PRO, and pro, wh-traces are non-overt (May 1981(a): 220.)

A characteristic feature of anaphors is that they lack independent reference. For this reason, they derive their reference from some other nominal expression. The source from which an anaphor derives its reference is referred to as the antecedent. Therefore, antecedent-anaphor relations deal with the grammatical cum semantic relationship between anaphors and their antecedents.

At this juncture, let us consider some examples of anatecedents and anaphors in Igbo. The anatecedent of a reflexive anaphor is the direct target of the action or state described by the verb. The example below is a construction with the reflexive anaphor ònwè yā (himself/herself/itself).

1. Àchọ _i	gbùrù ònwè	yā _i
Achọ	kill-pst-poss	him
"Achọ	killed	"himself"

In (1) the verb gbu (kill) describes an action performed by the subject Àchọ. This action affects the object ònwè yā (himself), which is the same individual as the subject. In other words, the action performed by the subject reverts to the same subject. English for example has a set of reflexive anaphors (myself, yourself, himself/herself, etc) which are distinguished for person, number, and gender. In some languages, for example Russian, the reflexive anaphor is marked by the use of a particular affix on the verb (Lyons 1986:362).

Unlike a reflexive anaphor however, a reciprocal anaphor expresses a mutual action or state between it and the antecedent. Consider the Igbo sentence below.

2. $\left[\overline{\text{Dikē}} \text{ nà } \overline{\text{Ogù}} \right]_i$ gbakètàrà ònwe hā_i àzù
 Dike and Ogu back-pst poss them back
 "Dike and Ogu backed each other"

The reciprocal anaphor ònwe hā (each other) is interpreted in such a way that the statement expresses a mutual relationship between Dikē and Ogù. "In other words, the use of reciprocal pronouns postulates a symmetry between the actions or relation of the members of the relevant antecedent" (Kjellmer 1982:241).

In grammatical exposes, reciprocal anaphors are generally treated alongside reflexive anaphors. This is because both the reflexive and reciprocal anaphors are assumed to share a great deal in common. According to Kjellmer (1982:236).

The reciprocal pronouns are certainly reflexive in character, but unlike the real reflexive pronouns, they express ... a 'two way reflexive relationship'. Intuitively, an important difference between reflexive and reciprocal expressions is the obligatory plural character of the noun phrase to which the latter refer.....

Having examined the reflexive and reciprocal anaphors, we now turn to the NP-trace. The concept of trace follows from the structure-preserving constraint. As proposed by Emonds (1976:3),

a transformational operation is structure-preserving if it moves, copies, or inserts a node C into some position where C can be otherwise generated by the grammar.

A trace is a lexically empty syntactic category or the anaphoric copy of an item which has undergone a movement rule. When a category undergoes movement, it leaves behind a 'ghost copy' or trace coindexed with the moved category. As a coindexed empty category, a trace makes it possible to keep track of the moved category which the trace represents. It is assumed that at S-structure, traces mark D-structure grammatical relations from structures enriched with traces. Consequently, thematic relations are recoverable from S-structure" (de Haan 1981:14).

A typical ergatively derived NP-trace is exemplified in Igbo below

3. (a) Egwu_i nà-àkụ t_i
 Music Aux-playing t
 "Music is playing".
- (b) NPe nà-àkụ egwū
 NPe Aux-playing music
 "Npe is playing music"

The trace t in (3a) is an NP-trace which results from the movement of the NP egwu from object position to the empty subject position as (3b) shows. It is claimed that the relation between an NP-trace and its antecedent is interpreted as that of bound anaphora. As Freidin (1978:524) points out,

This interpretation allows us to capture the striking generalization that NP-traces and bound anaphors (e.g reflexives and reciprocals) are subject to exactly the same conditions.

In (3a) therefore, the derived subject egwu functions as the antecedent of the object NP-trace t. Hence both are anaphorically related in the same way that reflexive and reciprocal anaphors are related to their antecedents. In the section that follows, there will be a review of some of the major theoretical models which have been adopted in discussing antecedent-anaphor relations. This review of literature will help to place our discussion on this subject in perspective.

1.1 Literature Review

There is an extensive literature on antecedent-anaphor relations in languages such as English, Spanish, and Russian (cf Lees and Klima (1963), Jackendoff (1972), Green (1975),

Timberlake (1979), 1980), Wasow (1979), Chomsky (1980, 1981 (a), 1986 (a), 1986 (a), and Aoun (1985). On the contrary, very little work has been done on antecedent-anaphor relations in Ìgbò. In this literature review, we will consider first of all, the major contributions on the analysis of anaphoric relations carried out within the Transformational Generative Theory (as represented essentially by Lees and Klima (1963), Chomsky (1965), and Langacker (1969). In addition we will examine the Lexicalist-Interpretative approach (essentially those of Dougherty (1968) and Jackendoff (1972) and Wasow (1979). By this review, we will examine critically how these models have been able to account for anaphoric relations, and also how they differ from one another. Thereafter, we will consider the available literature on anaphoric relations in Ìgbò.

1.2 The Transformational Generative Theory

Lees and Klima's (1963) work on pronominalization was the first generative account of anaphora. In the Transformational-Generative framework, antecedent-anaphor relations involve a rule of reflexivization.

This framework rests on two assumptions. The first is that a formative which is specified as $\langle \bar{+} \text{ Refl}, +\text{Coref with NP } x \rangle$ is transformationally derived from an NP specified in the base as $\langle \bar{+} \text{ Coref with NP } x \rangle$. The second assumption is that the transformation which accounts for the distribution of this formative is formulated as an erasure operation which uses one NP to delete another under the condition of strict identity¹ (Greenberg 1972:20).

According to Lees and Klima (1963:18), "when the subject and the object of a sentence are identical the object must be the corresponding-self forms". Perhaps, this is a carry over of the repetition constraint. This is a prohibition against the repetition of the object of a sentence when in that sentence the subject and object are identical (Lees and Klima 1963:18; Langacker 1972:110). In other words, when two NPs satisfy the identity requirement the reflexive transformation obligatorily applies. The following sentences in Igbo exemplify this.

¹'Strict identity' involves lexical identity (two NPs with the same lexical items) as well as referential identity (two NPs referring to the same person or thing) (Lyons 1979:132)

4. (a) Òkoro₁ tàrà Òkoro₁ arū ⇒

Okoro bite-pst Okoro bite

"Okoro bit Okoro"

(b) Òkoro₁ tàrà ònwè yā₁ arū

Okoro bite-pst poss him bite

"Okoro bit himself"

It is assumed that in (4a) the coindexed subject and object NPs refer to the same individual within the same simplex. Hence, the two NPs have satisfied the strict identity requirement. Having met this requirement, the repeated NP is deleted and is subsequently substituted with the appropriate reflexive form as (4b) shows.

In the Transformational-Generative model, the reflexive transformation is stated formally as follows (taken from Culicover 1976:146):

5.	S.D.:	X	-	NP	-Y	NP	-	Z	
		1		2	3	4		5	⇒
	S.C.:	1		2	3	4		5	
						$\left[\begin{array}{l} +Pro \\ +Ref1 \end{array} \right]$			

Conditions: (a) 2 and 4 are coreferential

(b) 2 and 4 are in the same simple S.

The assumption is that a morphological rule will substitute the deleted NP with the appropriate reflexive form which has the features [+Refl, +Coref].

Within the framework which is under review, there is equally a reciprocal rule. Both the reflexive and reciprocal rules operate in a similar manner. The difference is that unlike the reflexive object, there is a restriction on the appearance of a reciprocal object. The restriction is that the antecedent of the reciprocal object has to be a plural NP, since the reciprocal is said to be intrinsically plural (Butler 1976:335). The following sentences are examples.

6. (a) $\left[\bar{N}di\ enyi\ \grave{a}bu\grave{o}\ ah\grave{u}\ \bar{J}_i \right]$ $t\grave{a}r\grave{a}$ $\left[\bar{N}di\ enyi\ \grave{a}bu\grave{o}\ ah\grave{u}\ \bar{J}_i \right]$ that

These friend two that blame-pst these friend two

$\grave{u}t\grave{a}$

blame

"The two friends blamed the two friends"

(b) $\left[\bar{N}di\ enyi\ \grave{a}bu\grave{o}\ ah\grave{u}\ \bar{J}_i \right]$ $t\grave{a}r\grave{a}$ $\left[\bar{o}nwe\ h\bar{a}\ \bar{J}_i \right]$ $\grave{u}t\grave{a}$

These friend two that blame-pst poss them blame

"The two friends blamed each other".

7. (a) * $\angle$ Nnwa m $\int_1$ hùrù $\angle$ umù m $\int_1$ n'anya $\implies$
 Child my see - stat children my in eye
- (b) * $\angle$ Nnwa m $\int_1$ hùrù $\angle$ onwe hā $\int_1$ n'anya
 Child my see - stat poss them in eye

In (6a) the subject ndi enyi àbuō ahù, which serves as the potential antecedent for the reciprocal anaphor, and the object ndi enyi àbuō ahù are taken to be coreferential since they have fulfilled the requirement for identical reference. Again, the subject and object NPs are plural. The reciprocal transformation then applies by deleting and substituting for the repeated NP the appropriate reciprocal form shown in (6b). Sentences (7a-b) are ungrammatical. This is because the object in (7a), which pronominalizes as the reciprocal anaphor in (7b), has a singular subject as its antecedent. Besides that, this singular subject nwa m is a member of the set of the plural object umù m in (7a). Therefore the subject in (7a) should not be a singular entity. The reciprocal rule, which is similar to the reflexive rule, is formulated as follows (taken from Lees and Kilma 1963:26):

8.	S.D.:	X	- NP _{pl}	- Y	- NP _{pl}	- Z	
		1	2	3	4	5	$\implies$
	S.C.:	1	2	3	4	5	
					$\angle$ +Recip +Coref $\int$		

Conditions: (a) 2 and 4 are coreferential

(b) 2 and 4 are in the same simple S.

So far, we have tried to show to what extent the Transformational-Generative framework has succeeded in handling the range of data in the examples we have used. However, this approach has its shortcomings and has attracted a number of criticisms.

One of the criticisms against the Transformational-Generative analysis of antecedent anaphor relations is the issue of deletion and substitution under strict identity of reference. Chomsky (1972:109-110) claims that the transformational analysis of antecedent-anaphor relations is inadequate on account of such data as in (9).

9. John hit Bill and then George hit him (taken from Chomsky 1972:109).

He argues that when unstressed, him can refer to Bill. Conversely, it can refer to someone other than John or Bill when it is stressed. The conclusion then is that the assignment of reference to him, in relation to John or Bill involves a surface structure interpretation. Going by the deletion and substitution analysis, him is three ways ambiguous as to whether the reference is to John, Bill or

someone other than John or Bill.

Like the first criticism, the second relates to stress assignment. On this issue, we consider the effect of the pronominalisation rule and the Nuclear Stress Rule (NSR) on the following string in the course of derivation.

10.	Tim _i	believes	[	Ann	Loves	Tim _i	]		
	1	1		1	1	1		Word Stress	} 1st cycle
				2	2	1		Nuclear Stress Rule	
	Tim _i	believes	[	Ann	loves	him _i	]	Pronominalization	} 2nd cycle
								[-stress]	
	2	1		3	3			Nuclear Stress Rule	

The matrix clause subject Tim and the Subordinate clause object Tim are coreferential. Each of the lexical items in (10) bears a primary stress 1.

As a cyclic rule, the NSR applies at the end of each transformational cycle, beginning with the embedded clauses. In (10) what happens on the first cycle is that the NSR assigns main stress (1) to the subordinate clause object Tim. Consequently, the other words in that clause are reduced to secondary stress (2). On the second cycle, the pronominalization rule applies. This rule results in the destressing of the object pronoun him in the subordinate clause. Thus,

the verb believe in the matrix clause is left as the rightmost primary stress bearing element in (10).

At the end of the second cycle, the verb believe is assigned primary stress (1), giving rise to the incorrect (11a) instead of (11b).

11. (a) *Tim believes Ann loves him
 (b) Tim believes Mary loves him.

The incorrect string (11a) results from the pronominalization rule. According to Wasow (1979:19),

The derivation of anaphoric pronouns from full NPs forces the NSR to reduce. The well-motivated cyclic ordering of the NSR makes it possible to pronominalize before this incorrect stress reduction would take place.

The third criticism against the Transformational-Generative analysis of antecedent-anaphor relations concerns the deletion and substitution processes. The deletion and substitution analysis of anaphoric pronominal reference is criticized on the grounds that such an analysis violates the principle which stipulates that items with semantic content cannot be changed by transformation (Brown 1984:166).

Consider the following examples:

12. (a) Àda₁ kpòtárà nne Āda₁ ⇒
 Ada bring-pst mother Ada
 "Ada brought Ada's mother"

- (b) Àda_i kpòtàrà nne yā_i
 Ada bring-pst mother her
 "Ada brought her mother".

The pronoun ya in (12b) is two-way ambiguous. It may refer to Àda or to some unspecified individual. If the possessive pronoun ya were a transform of the possessive nne Àda it would be difficult to assign the appropriate reference to the pronoun ya. Thus in the transformational analysis, it would be difficult to determine which of the two readings is intended.

The fourth criticism is that the transformational analysis of reflexivization cannot account for antecedent-anaphor relations in such simple sentences as the following:

13. (a) John_i saw a picture of himself_i
 (b) Mary_i read a book about herself_i

Each of the sentences in (13) has two object NPs, one of which is the object of the verb, and the other the object of a preposition. In (13a) for example, the verb see has a picture as its object and the preposition of has the reflexive anaphor himself as its object. The first of the two object NPs (a picture) intervenes between the subject John and the reflexive anaphor himself. It will be recalled that in (5), it is the object of the verb that is specified as being coreferential with the subject. According to the constraints imposed by the reflexive rule in (5), there is no way in which

the subject and the reflexive anaphor in any of the sentences in (13) can be construed as being coreferential under any formulation of identical reference.

Finally, Lees and Klima's (1963) formalization of the reflexive and reciprocal rules has failed to take into consideration the interpretation of two or more coreferring NPs in a non-simplex sentence. On the contrary, the analysis of such coreferring NPs can be adequately taken care of within the G-B framework (cf section 4.5).

It should however be borne in mind that at the time Lees and Klima (1963) did their work, transformational rules were the only available mechanism to formulate their insight. For this reason they proposed that antecedent-anaphor relations be derived transformationally from full NPs under identity with some other NP in the sentence. Nevertheless, in spite of the weaknesses attributed to Lees and Klima's transformational analysis of anaphoric relations, their theoretical framework did make some significant contributions to the study of anaphoric relations in language. For instance, Lees and Klima's (1963) pronominalization transformation was for several years adopted as the standard practice in generative grammar. Lees and Klima (1963) also introduced the idea that reflexives belong to a special class of anaphoric pronouns which occur in the same clause as their antecedent (Wasow 1979: 13).

The criticisms levelled against the transformational analysis have led to the search for an alternative approach that would capture significant generalizations about antecedent-anaphor relations in language. In the next section, we will consider this alternative analysis of antecedent-anaphor relations.

1.3 The Lexicalist-Interpretive Theory

The Lexicalist-Interpretive approach to the analysis of anaphoric relations marks a departure from the transformational analysis of reflexive and reciprocal anaphors. It will be recalled that within the transformational framework, these anaphors are treated as "transforms of fully specified NPs, coreferential with and bearing a certain structural relation to other such NPs" (Greenberg 1972:20).

In the Lexicalist-interpretive theory, reflexive and reciprocal anaphors are inserted into the deep structure at some point in the derivation of the sentence where they are interpreted by an interpretive rule (Dougherty 1969:492). Hence, these anaphors are base-generated and are never introduced into the surface by transformations.

In Jackendoff's (1972) account, coreference relations between NPs are assigned by rules of semantic interpretation.

He incorporates the lexicalist hypothesis into his interpretive theory. The lexicalist hypothesis is an offshoot of the transformational theory. Unlike the transformational analysis, the lexicalist hypothesis claims that derived nominals are independent lexical items rather than items derived transformationally from their corresponding verbs. Riemsdijk and Williams (1986) assert that:

Many verbs do not have a derived nominal associated with them and correspondingly, that many nominals do not have a verb from which they might have been derived (Riemsdijk and Williams 1986:38).

In English for instance, verbs like to roam and to quash do not have a derived nominal. Similarly, nominals like thesis and custom lack a verb source. In the lexicalist hypothesis therefore, these verbs and nouns are listed in the lexicon. The nominalization transformation is blocked for such verbs as to roam and to quash in the transformational analysis by a rule feature which gives an exception to such a transformation.

For nouns like thesis and custom the transformational analysis would posit abstract, nonexistent verbs as their source of derivation (Riemsdijk and Williams 1986:39). Within the lexicalist-framework (Chomsky 1972) reflexive and reciprocal anaphors, as well as personal pronouns, are regarded

as basic lexical items. As lexical items, they are inserted into the base by lexical insertion rules. Thus, the canon of Jackendoff's Lexicalist interpretive position is that in the lexicon, the reflexive anaphor is specified as $[+Ref1]$, and $[-Coref \text{ with } NP_1]$ (Greenberg 1972: 17).

Jackendoff (1972: 112) proposes the following rules (adapted from Greenberg (1972: 34) and Hust and Brame (1976: 256):

14. (a) $[-NP_2]$ is coreferential with NP_1 iff;
 $[+Ref1]$
- (b) NP_2 does not both precede and command NP_1
- (c) NP_2 has not been marked for coreferentiality with any other NP.

Rule (14) will correctly account for the following Igbo sentences:

15. (a) Ibè_i nà-àgara onwe yā_i
 Ibe Aux-go-Ben Poss him
 "Ibe keeps to himself"
- (b) Unù_i tàrà ònwe unù_i ahụhụ
 You-pl punish-pst poss you-pl suffering
 "You punished yourselves"

What (14) implies is that in (15a-b) the reflexive anaphors do not precede and command their coindexed antecedents.

That is to say, the reflexive anaphor is not in subject position and the S node dominates both the subject and object positions. In addition, the reflexive anaphors in (15) have not served as NP in a coreference rule (cf (14c)).

But let us consider the following Ìgbò sentence to see whether rule (14) can handle the relation between the antecedent and anaphor.

16. Òbì₁ kwètàrà nà ya tàrà ònwe yā₁ aru
 Obi agree-pst that he bite-pst poss him bite
 "Obi accepted that he bit himself"

Sentence (16) can be illustrated with the tree diagram (17).

Sentence (16) has the reading in which the pronoun ya refers to the matrix clause subject Òbì, as well as to the reflexive anaphor ònwe yā. The reflexive anaphor ònwe yā is the object of the subordinate clause, and has ya, the subject of the embedded clause, as its antecedent.

By rule (14b) the reflexive ònwè yā neither precedes nor commands its antecedent, yā is "dominated by S in the subordinate clause which does not dominate NP₁" (Greenberg 1972:23). Supposing that yā and ònwè yā in the subordinate clause are marked as coreferential, it then follows that ònwè yā will be coreferential with Òbi. It is this kind of relationship that is referred to in Wasow (1979:49) as the Transitivity Condition, defined as follows:

18. If A, B, and C, are elements in a sentence such that A and B are anaphorically related, then the sentence is ungrammatical unless A and C are anaphorically related.

The relationship which is defined in (18) cannot be handled by (14c). Going by rule (14c). Òbi, yā, and ònwè yā cannot corefer, since yā (NP₂) (cf NP₂) in (14c) and (17) has been marked for coreferentiality with ònwè yā in the subordinate clause, prior to its being specified as coreferential with Òbi (NP₁) in the matrix clause.

Thus, for such sentences as (16) "Jackendoff's coreference rule provided no interpretation of the pairwise coreference relations of" Òbi, yā, ònwè yā (Greenberg 1972:49). In other words, the reflexive anaphor ònwè yā has a nearby antecedent yā within the same clause, as well as a remote antecedent Òbi in the matrix clause.

It is necessary to show that sentence (19) is a counter-evidence to rule (14b).

19. ònwe gī_i dì gī_i mmā

Poss you be you goodness

"You feel satisfied with yourself"

The reflexive anaphor ònwe gī is in subject position in (19), hence it both precedes and commands its antecedent gī. Further discussion on examples such as (19) will be taken up in section 4.4. In the light of sentences (16) and (19), we find that Jackendoff's (1972:112) coreference rule (14) is unable to account for such antecedent-anaphor relations as exemplified in these sentences. This then shows that Jackendoff's approach has failed to account for all cases of antecedent-anaphor relations.

We now examine Wasow's (1979) interpretive account of anaphoric relations. Wasow argues for what he refers to as a heterogeneous theory of anaphora. By this, he claims that:

the rules governing anaphora share a number of properties which differentiate them from other categories of rules needed for the description of languages (Wasow 1979:48).

According to Wasow, the shared properties of anaphora rules include the precede-command condition, and the Transitivity Condition (18). Wasow further claims that his analysis of pronominal anaphora generalizes to other anaphoric relations

such as the null anaphors like VP anaphora (Wasow 1979: Ibid). Wasow incorporates an anaphora rule and a semantic rule into his theory of anaphoric relations. The anaphora rule stipulates that in pronoun-antecedent pairs "an NP may serve as the antecedent for a given pronoun if they agree in certain features" (Wasow 1979: 153). These are number, person and gender (for languages that mark gender) features. In addition to this requirement, certain structural relations like the precede-command conditions have to hold between the antecedent and its anaphor. The anaphora rule is supplemented by the semantic rule which assigns the reference or reading of the antecedent to the anaphor (Wasow 1979: 153).

With regard to null-anaphors, Wasow claims that they are base-generated, like the pronominal anaphors. The null-anaphors are assumed to "have all the structure of their antecedents, lacking only "phonetic material". (Wasow 1979: 109). Like the pronominal anaphors, the null anaphors are equally subjected to the anaphora and semantic rules. Whereas pronominal anaphors and their antecedents are required to share person, number and gender features, its analogue for the null anaphors is the non-distinctness condition. This is to say that the null-anaphors are associated with the appropriate antecedents,

all of which "have to be non-distinct (in some sense which must include near identity of structures....)" (Wasow 1979: 109).

It is important to note that Wasow's heterogeneous theory of anaphora claims to provide a unified account of anaphoric relations in language. However, as Wasow admits, this theory does not have the notational conventions and the necessary formalism for stating the rules, constraints, and generalizations which govern anaphoric relations (Wasow 1979: 146).

Let us consider the following set of Igbo data, vis-a-vis Wasow's theory which, as he claims, lacks the necessary rule formalism and constraints.

20 (a) Àda_i hùrù [ònwé [yā_i]] n'anya

Ada see-pst poss her in eye

"Ada loves herself"

21 (a) Àda_i hürù [dòkìtá [yā_i/j]] n'anya
 Ada see-pst doctor her in eye
 "Ada loves her doctor"

One interesting observation about our data is that both Ònwe (poss) in (20) and dòkìtá (doctor) in (21) seem to share some distributional features. They function as head of their

respective NPs onwe yā (lit. poss her) and dokita ya (lit, doctor her). Both onwe and dokita are modified by the third person singular pronoun ya (her) which corefers and shares agreement features of person and number with the subject NP Ada. These seemingly shared features tend to suggest that in (20) and (21) the object NPs onwe yā and dokita ya would be interpreted in the same sense. Despite the similarities, only (20) has a reflexive reading, while (21) has a genitival reading interpreted as "Ada loves her own doctor" in the first reading and "Ada loves someone else's doctor" in the second reading.

In view of the observation we have made about the data in (20) and (21), we conclude that Wasow's theory seems to be inadequate in handling our data. This is because the theory fails to incorporate the necessary rule formalism and constraints that will account for the intended readings of (20) and (21). This will however be taken care of in section 3.2.

In the preceding discussion, we examined the basic tenets of the Lexicalist-Interpretive theory as regards the formalization of rules for interpreting anaphoric relations. In spite of its weakness, the Lexicalist-Interpretive theory has its merits.

It is this theory which is credited with the current practice of positing anaphors "in deep structure, with their antecedents determined by rules operating on derived structure" (Wasow 1979:48). We however need to mention that another theoretical framework which purports to handle antecedent-anaphor relations better will be adopted for this work. But before then, the literature on anaphora in Ìgbò will be examined.

1.4 Literature on Anaphora in Ìgbò

Of the popularly cited works in Ìgbò grammar, namely Green and Igwe (1963), Carrell (1970), Emenanjo (1978), Ezikeojiaku (1989) Oluikpe (1979) and Uwalaka (1988), only Oluikpe and Uwalaka discussed anaphoric relations in Ìgbò. Ume et al (1989:70) merely listed five sentences containing reflexive anaphors.

Oluikpe's (1979:73-96) analysis of reflexivization is based on the Transformational-Generative model, already discussed in section 1.2. In his account, the reflexive transformation rule

adds the feature set $\left[\begin{array}{l} +\text{pron} \\ +\text{Ref1} \end{array} \right]$ to the reflexivized

NP which is realized as ònwé (self) plus a personal pronoun which agrees in number and person with its antecedent.

The examples below are adapted from Oluikpe (1979:73-74)

22. (a) M_i $tòrò\ m_i$ $\Rightarrow$
 I praise-pst me
 "I praised me"

(b) M_i $tòrò\ ònwe\ \bar{m}_i$
 I praise-pst poss me
 "I praised myself"

23. (a) $\grave{A}da_i$ $hùrù\ \grave{A}da_i$ $\Rightarrow$
 Ada see-pst Ada
 "Ada saw Ada".

(b) $\grave{A}da_i$ $hùrù\ ònwe\ y\bar{a}_i$
 Ada see-pst poss her
 "Ada saw herself".

It is assumed that in examples (22) and (23), the (b) sentences are transformationally derived from the (a) example. In (23a) for instance, the second occurrence of Ada in object position is coindexed with the subject Ada. The coindexation is on the assumption that both occurrences of Ada are referentially identical. Thus in (23b), the subject Ada is deleted and is subsequently substituted with the appropriate reflexive form ònwe yā.

Uwalaka's (1988:70-92) analysis of anaphoric relations in Ìgbò is conducted within the framework of Case Grammar. She has a lengthy discussion on the nature of reflexive and reciprocal verbs in Ìgbò. Our analysis of reflexive and reciprocal verbs in section 3.8.2 and 3.8.3 is based largely on Uwalaka's insight. However, we will go beyond her analysis by incorporating the Lexical Thematic Representation of the reflexive and reciprocal verbs in our own discussion.

From this review of literature on antecedent-anaphor relations in Ìgbò, we observe that the language is deficient in the literature on the subject. Apart from the works of Oluikpe (1979) and Uwalaka (1988), there seems to be no other discussion on the subject known to us. For Oluikpe, the reflexive pronoun is a transformationally derived structure. In this respect, his analysis shares the same criticism as that of Lees and Klima (1963).

1.5 Objective of Study

We have seen the paucity of literature on antecedent-anaphor relations in Igbo. Therefore, there is need to conduct a comprehensive study on the subject. It is envisaged that the results of our findings will be a significant contribution to the study of antecedent-anaphor relations in language. Furthermore, this study will help bring about a modification of some assumptions of our theoretical framework.

1.6 Methodology

For the methodology, we adopt a systematic presentation and analysis of data which represent instances of antecedent-anaphor relations in Ìgbò. The data are based on the Òlù dialect of Ìgbò. It is the variety of Ìgbò which is spoken in the Ìsu clan of Orlu Local Government area. Occasionally however, data from other native speakers of Ìgbò were elicited, especially when we are in doubt of our intuitive knowledge of the language.

In this study we adopt the grammatical constraint regulated by the Binding Theory to account for antecedent-anaphor relations in Ìgbò. The Binding Theory is defined configurationally in terms of m-command and government. The terms will be made explicit in the appropriate sections.

However, where a sample of data provide counter evidence against the basic claims of the Binding Theory, the theory will then be modified to accommodate the data within the overall framework. In the chapter that follows, we present an overall view of the Government-Binding Theory.

CHAPTER TWO

THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK

2.0 Preliminaries

Our study is conducted within the framework of the Government-Binding Theory as proposed in Chomsky (1981(a), 1981(b), 1986(a), 1986(b) and such related works as Reinhart (1983), Aoun (1985), Williams (1986), Belletti and Rizzi (1988), Radford (1988), Haegeman (1991), among others. For this reason, this chapter examines the grammatical framework in the light of Igbo data.

The Government-Binding Theory is a product of the earlier Transformational-Generative models of linguistic theory - the Standard Theory (ST) and the Extended Standard Theory (EST) of Chomsky (1965) and (1972) respectively. In this study, we presume our readers' familiarity with the Standard and Extended Standard Theories.

The Government-Binding Theory differs from its predecessors in a number of ways. For instance, only one base rule and one transformational rule are stipulated. The theory has incorporated the principles of the X-bar (X') Syntax developed in Chomsky (1972) and Jackendoff (1977) to supplant the PS rules of the ST and EST.

It is claimed in G.B. that X'-theory can account for more generalizations than PS rules. X'-theory captures cross-categorical similarities, unlike PS rules that make use of a set of rules to account for the same facts.

The levels of deep and surface structures in the ST and EST have been replaced with D-structure and S-structure levels in GB. In Horrocks (1987:288) the D-structure is defined as:

a representation of predicate-argument structure in which each argument is identified with a syntactic category whose grammatical function is determined by the configuration of elements in which it occurs (Horrocks 1987:288).

This leads us to the definition of what predicate and arguments are. Fillmore (1968:373) defines the predicate as:

a term which identifies some property of an object or some relation between two or more objects. The objects concerning which a predicate asserts something are the arguments of that predicate.

According to Jacobsen (1986:31), an argument could be "an R-expression, a pronoun (including PRO), an overt anaphor, or a clause."

The S-structure, on the other hand, is the product of the application of the only transformational rule Move- α on the D-structure. Thus, the S-structure representation accounts for the surface ordering of the constituents.

In the G-B framework, unlike in the ST and EST, the number of transformations has been reduced drastically. All the transformations in the earlier models have now been subsumed under one single transformational rule, Move - α . By this rule, an element is moved from its original position (the extraction site) to somewhere else in the string (the landing site).

The moved element is said to leave a trace at the extraction site. This trace consists of the category label and index of the moved element. The trace encodes information from D-structure configurations into S-structure. Thus, semantically relevant grammatical relations are represented simultaneously at both levels of D-structure and S-structure. These grammatical relations between the trace and the moved element (the antecedent of the trace) are transmitted through a chain mechanism. Chomsky (1981(a):331) defines a chain as "a sequence of categories at S-structure coindexed by Move - α ". Radford (1988:562) asserts that the chain mechanism ensures:

that the inherent properties of antecedents are transmitted to traces, and conversely that the assigned properties of traces are transmitted to their antecedent.

Thus in (3a), repeated here as (24);

24. Egwu_i na-àkụ t_i
 Music Aux-Playing t
 "Music is playing"

The moved NP egwu in subject position, and its trace in object position, constitute a movement chain. The head of the chain is the highest element in the chain (the subject egwu), while the lowest element (the object trace) is called the foot or tail of the chain.

2.1 General Organization of the Grammatical Model

The central guiding principle within the GB framework is that the internal structure of the grammar is modular. Each module is autonomous and is associated with a finite set of principles. Chomsky (1981) states that the modular nature of G-B theory is understood;

in the sense that the full complexity of observed phenomena is traced to the interaction of partially independent subtheories, each with its own abstract structures (Chomsky 1981(a):135).

In other words, at each level of representation: D-structure, S-structure, and Logical Form (LF), these modules or rules interact with one another, as if in a relationship of mutual conspiracy; to ensure the well-formedness of structures (Green, 1970:270). Frasier (1988) adds that;

In this modular view, what appear on the surface to be major structural differences among languages result from each language setting slightly different values (parameters) for each of the various grammatical subsystems (Frasier 1988):9-10).

The diagram below is a representation of the grammatical model as presented by Sells (1985:24).

In the G-B framework, the base, the transformational, and interpretive components constitute the three major components of grammar. The base component consists of the lexicon, syntax and categorial rules. The transformational component is made up of the only transformational rule Move - α . The interpretive components consist of the Phonetic Form (PF), and the Logical Form (LF). The PF component is associated with the phonological rules, in addition to low-level transformational processes which may involve deletion, and contraction (Lasnik and Uriagereka 1988:1). The LF is a level of syntactic representations. All these levels are equally "subject to the principles that govern syntactic representation, such as the projection principle or the ECP" (Haegeman 1991: 444).

The lexicon specifies the abstract morphophonological structure of each lexical item in language, including its categorial, syntactic, and contextual features. The categorial rules are constrained by X'-Theory. The base rules, made up of the rules of the lexical and categorial subcomponents, generate the D-structure. The projection principles, θ -Theory, and Case Theory determine the well-formedness condition of the D-structure constituents.

The D-structure constituents are mapped into S-structure by the rule Move- α . However, this movement is not arbitrary. Move- α is constrained by independent principles which dictate what can move and where it can move to.

We will attempt to specify the functioning of some of the components and principles of grammar as presented in G-B Theory. As the study progresses, a number of these principles will be examined in some detail as they affect antecedent-anaphor relations.

2.2 The X-Bar (X'-) Theory

The discussion in this section is based on the Theory of categories. This theory of categories is referred to in G-B as the X'-Syntax or X'-Theory. It specifies how phrases and clauses are built up out of lower-level constituents.

Two specific goals have been set in this section. The first is a discussion on why the X'-Theory is preferred to the erstwhile PS rules of the ST and the EST. The second goal examines how the X'-Theory has been constrained so as to be able to justify our preference for it.

X'-Theory has supplanted PS rules of the 50s and early 70s, on the basis of a number of objections against PS rules.

The first objection is that PS rules can only account for lexical and phrasal categories without taking into account the reality of an intermediate category level which is larger than the lexical category but smaller than the phrasal category (Radford 1981:91; 1988:167). The second is that X'-Theory, unlike PS rules, makes use of category neutral rules which can be generalized over categories. This contrasts with PS rules which make use of category specific rules. It is striking to note the structural parallelism or symmetry between the different types of phrases which has made it possible to replace particular statements about the internal structure of specific types of phrase (NP, VP, AP, PP, etc) by a single more general statement Xⁿ (or XP). X'-Theory therefore has come to fulfill the need for a category variable, which is a symbol that can stand for any category of a given type. In other words, the X'-Theory is a device that will "enable us not to talk about individual categories (Noun, Verb, Adjective, Preposition, Adverb) but rather about all categories in general" (Radford 1988:228-229). The third objection points to the overlap between PS rules and subcategorization frames. It is assumed, as proposed by Radford (1988) that;

much of the information contained in traditional PS rules is redundant because it duplicates information already contained in the sub-categorization frames of lexical entries (Radford 1988:367).

The introduction of the X'-convention therefore has eliminated syntactic information which mirrors the lexical properties of particular items. These properties specify the range of complements an item belonging to a given category may require.

X'-Theory is construed as a set of restrictions on possible phrase structure configurations of D-structure. To achieve the goal of restricting possible phrase structure configurations, certain constraints have been built into the theory. These constraints include the Endocentricity Constraint, Modifier Maximality Constraint, and the Succession Principle.

First, let us consider the Endocentricity Constraint. It is a condition on the base rules used to generate D-structures such that phrases or clauses are uniquely headed, thereby eliminating the possibility of multiple heading (Radford 1988:262). Following Cowper (192:20), we define the head of any category as the element after which the category is named. Chomsky 1986(a):160) argues that the major lexical categories (N,V,P.A) are construed as X^0 -(Zero-bar) categories which create a full set of non-terminals projected from them.

In other words, phrasal categories are regarded as projections of their corresponding lexical categories which head them.

Thus, the categorial features of a maximal phrase or phrasal node are determined by the categorial features of its head.

As Cowper claims, the term head;

refers only to the lexical head of a category, that is to the node which has no bars and is of the same category (N, V, etc) as the phrase category itself (Cowper 1992:33).

To exemplify the Endocentricity Constraint in Ìgbò, consider the underlined subject and object NPs² in sentences (25) and (26) respectively.

25. (a) Umùakwukwo bī n'ulō anyi àlótala

Students live in house our return-perf

"The students who live in our house have returned"

(b) Umùakwukwo alótala

Students

return-perf

"The Students have returned".

26. (a) Egbe ēburula oke okukò ojii ahù

Kite carry-perf male fowl dark that

"A kite has carried away the black male fowl"

²We will continue to make use of the phrasal category labels NP, VP, etc, since they are not crucial to our discussion.

- (b) Egbe ēburula okukò
Kite carry-perf fowl

"A kite has carried away the fowl".

The underlined subject and object NPs in (25a) and (26a) respectively are non-simplex NPs. The underlined subject in (25a) is made up of the lexical head Umyakwukwo, and a relative clause bī n'ulō anyi. In (26a) the underlined object consists of the lexical head okukò, which is preceded by the noun modifier oke, and followed by the adjective ojii and the specifier (Spec) ahù. The underlined non-simplex NPs in (25a) and (26a) satisfy the Endocentricity requirement. As examples (25b) and (26b) show the respective heads of the underlined NPs in (25a) and (26a) share the same distribution.

Secondly, we examine the Modifier Maximality constraint. Chomsky (1986(a):3) claims that all Modifiers - Specifiers, Adjuncts, Attributes, and Complements must be maximal projections of their respective categories. What this constraint specifies is that these modifiers (Specifiers, Adjuncts, attributes, and Complements) must be full phrases such as DP, NP, VP, AP, PP, etc. Thus in examples (25a) and (26a) the non-head terms ahù, anyi (DP), bi VP, oke (NP); ojii (AP) and n'ulō (PP) are maximal projections of their respective head categories.

Thirdly, there is the Succession Principle (Kornai and Pullum 1988). This principle is a requirement on the lexical head to project to an intermediate level, X' , a level larger than the lexical head but smaller than the maximal projection. Then, the X' level will project maximally to an X'' . In other words, "The head term is one-bar-level lower than the immediately dominating phrasal node" (Kornai and Pullum 1990:36). It thus follows that in X' -Theory, the Succession Principle is observed. This can be captured by the rule schema (27) below:

$$27. \quad X^0 \longrightarrow X' \longrightarrow X''$$

The rule schema (27) can be used to expand any phrasal category as shown in (28) below.

(Adapted from Haegeman 1991:95).

29. (a) $X^n \longrightarrow X'$ Spec
 (b) $X' \longrightarrow X'$ X^n
 (c) $X' \longrightarrow X^0$ X^n

The configuration in (28) is specified by the rules in (29a-c), on the assumption that the head term X^0 occurs with a full complement of Spec, Attribute, Adjunct, and Complement, all of which are maximal projections. Let us start from rule (29c) to show how an X^0 -category can project maximally. Rule (29c) shows that an X^0 -category combines with its X^n complement to form an X' projection. The next rule (29b) applies to the output of (29c), which is an X' projection. The output of (29c) combines with an adjunct phrase X^n to form an X' projection. Rule (29b) applies recursively, with the X' projection taking on an attribute phrase X^n . The output of this iterative rule (29b) now feeds (29a), with the X' projection and Spec forming a maximal projection X^n .

At this juncture we illustrate how the X' -Theory can be used to characterize the underlined object NP in (26a) above, which is represented below as (30).

In the configuration (30) the lexical head okukò does not subcategorize for any complement and so by rule (29c) the head projects to a non-branching N'. Rule (29b) applies to the output of (29c), combining the non-branching N' with the attribute phrase (AP) to form an N' okukò ojii. The iterative application of (29b) combines the N' okukò ojii with the NP modifier oke to form the N' projection Oke okukò ojii. Finally, the output of (29b) feeds rule (29a), the N' projection combines with the Spec ahù to form the maximal projection (NP) oke okukò ojii ahù.

It is pertinent to point out that in the X'-Theory, there is no fixed order for any phrasal constituent in relation to its head term. The assumption is that constituent order is subject to parametric variation between languages. The

following Igbo and English NPs in (31) and (32) respectively will illustrate the point.

31. (a) Agadī nwaanyī oma ahụ
 Elderly woman beautiful that
 "The beautiful old woman"

32. (a) The tall woman on the bus

In (31b) and (32b) for instance, we observe that within the respective NPs agadī nwaanyī oma ahụ and the tall woman on the bus the head terms nwaanyī and woman are the first constituents

of the minimal N^0 . Thus in terms of head-complement order, Igbo and English represent the head first parameter. But there are different values in the specifier-head order for both languages. Whereas Igbo belongs to the Spec-last languages (with the specifier coming after the head term), English belongs to the Spec-first language (with the specifier preceding the head term). It then means that each language determines how the constituents are ordered in relation to the head term (Radford 1988:273).

In the course of our discussion, we tried to highlight the advantages of the X'-Theory over the traditional PS rules. It is claimed that there are three distinct levels - X^0 , X' , and maximal phrasal category X'' . In terms of cross-categorial generalization, Cowper argues that;

The most restrictive theory would allow exactly the same number of levels for all categories in all languages. We will therefore adopt such a theory, in the expectation that if it is wrong, data will soon emerge to falsify it (Cowper 1992:46).

2.3 The Lexicon

Fillmore (1968:389) has aptly described the Lexicon as "a list of minimally redundant descriptions of the syntactic, and phonological properties of lexical items "Fillmore's

definition of the lexicon is still valid in standard G-B practice. The syntactic properties of a lexical item include its categorial and contextual features. The categorial properties specify an item as either a noun, verb, or adjective. The contextual features of a lexical item will specify its subcategorization properties. That is, the subcategorization features determine what category-type a given lexical item may select as its complement. For instance, the subcategorization properties will show whether the item subcategorizes for an NP, VP, PP, clause, or nothing at all. As an illustration, the lexical items in (33) below are Igbo items, with their associated categorial feature complements.

33. (a) si (cook) $\langle \bar{+}V, -N \bar{\rangle}$; $+ \langle \bar{\quad} \bar{\quad} \bar{\quad} \bar{\quad} NP \bar{\rangle}$
- (b) nye (give) $\langle \bar{+}V, -N \bar{\rangle}$; $+ \langle \bar{\quad} \bar{\quad} \bar{\quad} NP Np \bar{\rangle}$
- (c) tinye (Put) $\langle \bar{+}V, -N \bar{\rangle}$; $+ \langle \bar{\quad} \bar{\quad} \bar{\quad} \bar{\quad} NP PP \bar{\rangle}$
- (d) chọ (want) $\langle \bar{+}V, -N \bar{\rangle}$; $+ \langle \bar{\quad} \bar{\quad} \bar{\quad} \bar{\quad} \left\{ \begin{array}{l} NP \\ S \end{array} \right\} \bar{\rangle}$
- (e) nwu (die) $\langle \bar{+}V, -N \bar{\rangle}$; $- \langle \bar{\quad} \bar{\quad} \bar{\quad} \bar{\quad} NP \bar{\rangle}$
- (f) okpoō (dry) $\langle \bar{+}V, +N \bar{\rangle}$; $+ \langle \bar{NP} \bar{\quad} \bar{\quad} \bar{\quad} \bar{\quad} \bar{\rangle}$
- (g) oma (good) $\langle \bar{+}V, +N \bar{\rangle}$; $+ \langle \bar{NP} \bar{\quad} \bar{\quad} \bar{\quad} \bar{\quad} \bar{\rangle}$
- (h) na (in, on, etc) $\langle \bar{-}V, -N \bar{\rangle}$; $+ \langle \bar{\quad} \bar{\quad} \bar{\quad} \bar{\quad} NP \bar{\rangle}$
- (i) banyere (about) $\langle \bar{-}V, -N \bar{\rangle}$; $+ \langle \bar{\quad} \bar{\quad} \bar{\quad} \bar{\quad} NP \bar{\rangle}$

The first entry for each of the items in (33a-e) specifies that the given item belongs to the category verb $[+V, -N]$. The items in (33f-g) belong to the category adjective $([-V, +N])$, while those in (33h-i) are prepositions $([-V, -N])$. The second entry is a specification of the complement type which is subcategorized for by each of the items. As an illustration, the verb si in (33a) subcategorizes for an NP complement, while the verb nye in (33b) subcategorizes for two NP complements. The verb tinye in (33c) takes an NP and PP complement. The verb nwu in (33e) has a null complement. The items in (33f-g) are adjectives, and they subcategorize for an NP complement. The same applies to the items in (33h-i) which are prepositions.

You will have noticed that the items in (33a-d) and (33f-i) are positively specified for the complement types they take, whereas item (33e) is negatively specified. The use of positive and negative subcategorization features seems to be a handy tool in accounting for the difference between items that can subcategorize for complements and those that cannot. However, the specification of subcategorization features in (33) can be simplified in respect of the positive and negative specifications. This simplification involves only the inclusion of positive subcategorization features in lexical entries as shown, for example, in (34a-g).

34. (a)	si	$\langle +V, -N \rangle$;	$\langle -NP \rangle$
(b)	nye	$\langle +V, -N \rangle$;	$\langle -NP NP \rangle$
(c)	tinye	$\langle +V, -N \rangle$;	$\langle -NP PP \rangle$
(d)	chọ	$\langle +V, -N \rangle$;	$\langle - \left\{ \begin{matrix} NP \\ S \end{matrix} \right\} \rangle$
(e)	nwu	$\langle +V, -N \rangle$;	$\langle - \emptyset \rangle$
(f)	na	$\langle -V, -N \rangle$;	$\langle -NP \rangle$
(g)	banyere	$\langle -V, -N \rangle$;	$\langle -NP \rangle$

In this way, Radford (1988:342) asserts;

it becomes redundant to mark each such subcategorization property as being positively specified: therefore, we... simply specify the range of structures which a given item can occur in, without attaching any positive 'feature' to this specification.

The sentences below are used for illustration. The complements which the sample items in (35a-e) subcategorize for are underlined and labelled according to category type.

35. (a) Àda sìrì nri (NP)
 Ada cook-pst food
 "Ada cooked some food".
- (b) Uchè nyèrè ànyì (NP) azù (NP)
 Uche give-pst us fish
 "Uche gave us some fish".

- (c) Òbi tìnyèrè egō (NP) n'akpà (PP)
 Òbi put-pst money in pocket
 "Òbi put some money in the pocket".
- (di) Òlā chòrò egō (NP)
 Òlā want-pres money
 "Òlā needs some money".
- (dii) Òkoro chòrò kà ya kwuo ugwo mà ahù (S)
 Òkoro want-pres that he pay cost knife that
 "Òkoro wants to pay for the knife".
- (e) Ughò nwùrù (Ø)
 Ughò die-pst
 "Ughò died".

The verbs in (35a-d) subcategorize for complements whereas in (35e) the verb does not. It thus follows that verbs which subcategorize for complements are referred to as transitive while those that do not, like the verb nwu are intransitive.

The semantic properties of a lexical item indicate the representation of the conceptual content of the lexical item. For example, the semantic content of the verb imposes selectional restrictions on its complement. These restrictions, according to Radford (1988:370), are semantic/pragmatic in nature.

The verb si in (35a) has the semantic property of selecting an edible entity nri as its complement. In addition to this, part of the semantic property of a verb is that it imposes a selectional restriction on its subject, even though verbs do not subcategorize for their subjects. It is claimed that "the semantic influence of the verb is dominant, extending itself over the subservient accompanying nouns, and over other elements in the sentence" (Uwalaka 1983:7). The verb si in (35a) selects a subject Ada with the feature $[\bar{+}Human]$. Hence, selectional restrictions hold between the predicate: si, and its arguments, Ada and nri. Therefore in terms of their semantic properties, verbs are assigned semantic functions or θ -roles (Theta-roles) whose "function is to mark certain structural positions as argument positions" (Ravin 1990:46).

Consider the verb nye in (35b) in terms of θ -role assignment. This verb takes three arguments - the subject Uchè, the indirect object anyi, and the direct object azù, in that order. It is the property of this verb to assign θ -roles to its argument positions. Thus, the subject position bears the θ -role Agent. This role defines the entity who intentionally initiates the action expressed by the verb. The **indirect object**

position is assigned the θ -role Goal, which signifies the entity towards which something moves. The direct object position is assigned the Theme θ -role. This role signifies the entity affected by the action expressed by the verb.

In the lexicon, verbs are specified in terms of their categorial and contextual features, plus their semantic properties which are realised as θ -roles. The verb nye will then be specified as follows:

36. nye (give) [$\bar{+}V, -N$]; [$\bar{-}NP NP$]
 Agent <Goal, Theme>³

The entries associated with the verb nye in (36) refer to its categorial and subcategorization properties, as well as its argument structure, and conceptual content.

We now take a quick look at the morpho-phonological properties of lexical items, since a detailed discussion of these properties is beyond the scope of this work. The morpho-phonological properties of a lexical item specify the "phonological or orthographic shapes which the item assumes under given grammatical conditions" (Fillmore 1970:370).

³The angled brackets are used to enclose the verb's internal arguments/ θ -roles. For example, the Agent θ -role which is placed outside the angled brackets is an external argument/ θ -role.

Note that the verb si in (33a) has a high tone (HT) in its citation. However, it assumes a low tone (LT) when it co-occurs with the past tense marker(pst) - ri in a declarative sentence such as (35a).

To summarize, the lexicon provides the set of lexical items that occur in language. These items are associated with syntactic, semantic, as well as morpho-phonological properties which they assume, relative to the grammatical contexts in which they occur.

2.4 The Projection Principle

The projection principle derives from the existence of the lexicon. As discussed in the preceding section, all the lexical items in language are specified in terms of their syntactic, semantic, and morpho-phonological properties. It is thus the duty of the projection principle "to link lexical entries to base-structure configurations" (Ravin 1990:51). The lexical items, with their associated representations, are specified at each level of syntactic representative (D-structure, S-structure, and LF). Thus, Chomsky (1981(a):29) claims that:

The Projection Principle ensures that representations at each syntactic level are projected from the lexicon in that they observe the strict subcategorization properties of the lexical items.

This means that if a syntactic position is required at D-structure, it will also be required at S-structure. Consider the Igbo verb tu (place an order for). The complement subcategorized for by this verb has to be syntactically represented at the various levels of syntactic representation. Assuming that at some point, the complement lacks an overt content at S-structure, the Projection Principle then ensures that this complement be represented as "an empty category of the required type" in that position as in (37b) (Chomsky 1986(a):84).

37. (a) Ùju tùrù hà motò
 Uju place order-pst them car
 "Uju placed an order for a car through them".
- (b) Gĩnī_i kà Ùju tùrù hà t_i?
 What that Uju place order-pst them t?
 "What did Uju place an order for through them?"

The verb tu in (37a) takes the NP complement motò. This complement position however is phonologically null in (37b).

The presence of this null element in a position subcategorized for a lexical NP is explicable. The explanation is that the complement which otherwise would have been in that position has been preposed by Move - α . This movement leaves the subcategorized position phonologically empty. The empty category t , which is the trace of the moved element, marks the S-structure position of the preposed element.

It is necessary to point out that the projection principle is not restricted to the issue of subcategorized positions. In the preceding section, we did mention the feature of subject selection by the verb, since a verb does not subcategorize for a subject. Let us examine the following verbs in (38a-b) vis-a-vis subject selection (39a-b).

38. (a) si (cook) $[\bar{+}V, -N]$; $[\bar{---} NP]$

(b) nwụ (die) $[\bar{+}V, -N]$; $[\bar{---}\emptyset]$.

39. (a) *Siri nri

Cook-pst food

(b) *Nwùrù

Die-pst

As shown in examples (39a-b), it is not possible for the verbs to occur in well-formed strings without a subject.

Now contrast the examples in (39) with the analogous sentences in (40), each of which has a subject.

40. (a) Àda siri nri
 Ada cook-pst food
 "Ada cooked some food"
- (b) Ughò nwùrù
 Ugho die-pst
 "Ugho died".

In addition to subcategorization therefore, verbs are required to select their subject. This subject requirement however is not restricted to verbs. Clauses are equally required to have subjects. Sentences (41a-c) illustrate subject requirement with regard to clauses.

41. (a) Àda_i Chòrò [_{IP} [_{NP} PRO_i VP [_{VP} isì ji]]]]
 Ada want-Ben PRO to cook yam
 "Ada wants to boil some yams"
- (b) Àda mà [_{CP} nà [_{IP} [_{NP} Ola_i VP [_{VP} siri ji]]]]]
 Ada know that Ola cook-pst yam
 "Ada knows that Ola boiled some yams".
- (c) *Àda mà [_{CP} nà [_{IP} [_{NP}^e VP [_{VP} siri ji]]]]]
 Ada know that cook-pst yam.

The bracketed infinitival clause in (41a) lacks an overt subject. However, its reading shows that the subject of that clause is somehow present. It is assumed that the subject selected by the infinitive verb form igI in the subordinate clause of (41a) is interpreted as being identical with the subject of the finite verb chòrò in the matrix clause.

We now compare the infinitive verb igI in the subordinate clause of (41a) with the finite verb siri in the embedded clause of (41b) in relation to how the subject of these verbs can be realized. In the subordinate clause of (41b), the subject Olà is phonological. What accounts for its deviance is that in the subordinate clause, the finite verb siri fails to satisfy the subject requirement for that clause. This issue of subject requirement by a clause is constrained by the Extended Projection Principle. This principle as stated in Radford (1988) stipulates that:

Lexical requirements (Viz categorial, subcategorization, and thematic properties) and structural requirements (Viz the requirement that a clause should have a subject) must be uniformly satisfied at all syntactic levels (Radford 1988: 552).

2.5 Government Theory

The term government had long been in use in traditional grammatical analysis. In this usage, government refers "to the control by a verb or adjective over the case or mood

of a following noun or verb..." (Green 1974:58). The term government has been incorporated into G-B Theory as one of the modules of grammar. In G-B syntax, Government Theory involves "the limitation of the sphere of influence of a particular category with respect to adjacent categories" (Horrocks 1987:103). Government Theory is assumed to be central to G-B Theory as a whole. This is because a number of other modules namely, θ -Theory, Case Theory, the Empty Category Principle (ECP), and the Binding Theory are dependent upon it, since these modules (to discussed in the relevant sections) are formulated in terms of Government Theory (Aoun 1985:22).

Lexical heads (N,V,P,A) and INFL (ection) are assumed to govern their complements. Thus in Chomsky (1981(a):162), Government is stated as the relationship between a lexical head and its complement in the phrase headed by the lexical head. This relationship also exists between INFL and the subject when INFL contains $[+\text{Tense}, +\text{AGR}]$. The relationship between INFL and subject is on the assumption that INFL is the head of IP. The configurational relationship between a lexical head and its complement is the specification of the domain of Government. This domain is the configuration which is defined in terms of C-command.

Thus a governing domain is the maximal category X^m that dominates the lexical head, as well as the element that is under government.

In what follows, we intend to examine how Government Theory can be applied in the light of Ìgbò. The following sentences (42a) and (43a), with their corresponding partial tree diagrams (42b) and (43b), will be considered. The partial tree diagrams will focus on the relevant X^m configurations, with V(erb) and P(reposition) as governors.

42. (a) Ùju zùtára motò
 Uju buy-pst car
 "Uju bought a car".

43. (a) Àda tìnyèrè ngàjì nà òkàtà
 Ada put-pst spoon in basket
 "Ada put the spoon in the basket".

(b)

The VPs in diagrams (42b) and (43b) above are maximal projections of their respective heads zùtàrà and tìnyèrè. The NP motò in (42b) is the complement of the verb zu (buy). Similarly, the NP ñgàjì and the PP nà ñkàtà are the complements of the verb tìnye (put) in (43b). Again the PP in (43b) is the maximal projection of the preposition (P) na, whose complement is the NP ñkàtà. From the configurations in (42b) and (43b), we observe that the various heads C-command their respective complements, and vice versa.

As conceived here, government is a relationship of mutual or strict C-command. In this sense therefore, C-command is defined as follows:

44. α C-commands β iff the first branching node dominating α dominates β and α does not contain β
(Chomsky 1981(a):166).

Government, on the other hand is defined as shown in (45) below.

45. α governs β iff
(i) α is a governor; and
(ii) α C-commands β and β C-commands α
(Chomsky 1981(a):163).

The verb zùtàrà and its NP complement motò in (42b) mutually C-command each other. This relationship of mutual C-command exists because the first branching node V' dominates the verb and its complement, and the verb V does not dominate (or contain) its complement. In addition to this, the verb zùtàrà governs its NP complement motò, since the verb belongs to the class of governors. Similarly, in (43b) the first branching node V' dominates the verb tìnyèrè and its NP (ngàji) and PP (nà òkàtà) complements. Hence, the relationship between the verb and its complements is that of mutual C-command.

It is relevant to point out that the definition of C-command in (44) is inadequate. By this definition, the verb tìnyèrè

in (43b) C-commands the NPs - ngàjì and nkàtà. Yet, the verb tìnyèrè will not be the governor for the NP nkàtà. What is really the case is that the verb tìnyèrè in (43b) can only govern the NP ngàjì, while in the PP complement na nkàtà, it is the P (na) which governs its complement nkàtà. In view of this, therefore, there is need for a finer definition of C-command.

In Barriers, Chomsky (1986 (b):8) defines C-command and Government as follows in (46) and (47) respectively.

46. α C-commands β iff
- (i) α does not dominate β , and
 - (ii) Every γ that dominates α dominates β .
47. α governs β iff
- (i) α M-commands β , and
 - (ii) No barrier intervenes between α and β
 - (iii) Maximal projections are barriers to Government.

The definition in (46) takes care of strict C-command as well as M-(Maximal) command. Thus where γ is interpreted as the first branching node, strict C-command is involved, and where it is interpreted as a maximal projection, then M-command is involved.

In like manner, the definition of Government in (47) guards against any possibility whereby a potential governor governs in a multiple way. This restriction is achieved by the proviso that maximal projections act as barriers to government. A barrier is defined as "a node that blocks some relation, such as government, or movement, from holding between two positions in a structure" (Cowper 1992:183). For this reason, the verb tìnyèrè in (43b) only governs the NP complement ngàjì. But this verb cannot govern into its PP complement nà ñkàtà because it is barred from governing into the NP complement of P. The restriction against the verb in (43b) from governing into the NP complement of P is as a consequence of the PP complement of V. This PP complement of V in (43b) constitutes a barrier. Hence, the PP complement blocks the verb tìnyèrè from governing the NP (ñkàtà) complement of P. The closest governor is therefore allowed to govern its complement. This is what is referred to in recent G-B literature as the Minimality Condition (Chomsky 1986(b):10). Henceforth, we adopt the definitions of C-command and Government in (46) and (47) respectively.

2.6 Case Theory

Case Theory is the module of grammar that regulates the assignment of case to the NPs of a given Case assigner. Case Theory and Government Theory interact in that Case is assigned under the configuration of Government. The term Case is used to express the morphological relationship between a governor and the NP it governs. The Case assigned to a given NP is determined by the function of that NP. With regard to Case features, Jones (1988:100) argues that:

The principal function of Case features is to encode (indirectly) grammatical relations (subject, object, etc) which in turn are mapped on to θ -roles via the lexical properties of the predicates to which they bear these relations. Since NPs typically require θ -roles, it is in some sense natural that they should bear the morphological features which indirectly encode these roles.

In languages with rich inflectional morphology, as typified by Italian, Spanish, and Russian, Case forms are usually realized morphologically. This is referred to as morphological case. However, such languages as English and Igbo are deficient in inflectional morphology. In these languages therefore, Case forms do not manifest overtly, except in highly restricted cases. Thus in such languages,

abstract Case is assigned. Case inflection is residual in English, it features in pronominal NPs to indicate number, gender, and person agreement. In Igbo, only the second person (i/i:gi) and third person (o/o:ya) singular pronominal forms seem to exhibit features of morphological Case. The rest of the pronominal forms are invariant, as the table below shows.

Personal Pronoun Forms in Igbo

TABLE 1

Person	Singular			Plural		
	Subj.	Obj.	Poss.	Subj.	Obj.	Poss.
1st	M/Mu	m/mu	m/mu	anyi	anyi	anyi
2nd	i/i	gi	gi	unu	unu	unu
3rd	o/o	ya	ya	ha	ha	ha

The morphological Case inflection in the Igbo personal pronoun forms will be illustrated with the following sentences. Attention will be paid to the underlined pronominals in (48a-d).

48. (a) I kwètàrà nà m hùrù gị ònyàahù
 You accept-pst that I see-pst you yesterday
 "You accepted that I saw you yesterday".
- (b) O Chòrò kà ì zàara yā ụlò
 He want that you sweep-Appl him house
 "He wants you to sweep the house for him".
- (c) Nne Yā gàrà ahịa
 Mother his/her go-pst market
 "His/her mother went to the market".
- (d) Amà ì nà ì gwàrà ì eziokwū
 Know I that you tell-pst me truth
 "I know that you told me the truth."

The underlined personal pronouns in subject position in examples (48a-c) are morphologically distinct from those in object position. This difference is attributed to Case inflection which morphologically (overtly) encodes the grammatical relations that hold between these pronominal forms and their predicates. The Case features exhibited by the pronominals in (48a-c) differ from those in the underlined pronouns in (48d). Those in (48d) are invariant, irrespective of their grammatical relations to the predicate, in that, they

do not exhibit any overt morphological Case inflection. Sentence (48c) contains a genitival phrase nne ya. This phrase is headed by the noun nne, while the possessive pronoun ya is the modifier. In isolation, both nominals have inherent high tone. However, when they enter into a genitival relationship, they assume a different morphotological realization. The possessive pronoun ya assumes a high-down-step (HD-S) tone. Hence, this morphotonological change is assumed to be the reflex of the genitival inflection in English.

In G-B, it is claimed that every NP, provided it is lexically realized, must be assigned Case. The Case may either be abstract or morphological. This requirement is expressed in terms of the Case Filter (49).

49. *NP if NP has phonetic content and has no Case (Chomsky 1981(a):49).

The implication of (49) is that every lexical NP at S-structure must be assigned Case, otherwise the string is rendered

ungrammatical. Consider the following English sentences in

(50). (a) N₀nye is likely [$\bar{t}_i$ to be a successful lawyer].

(b) NP^e is likely [$\bar{N}_0$ nye to be a successful lawyer].

(c) It is likely [$\bar{t}$ that Nonye will be a successful lawyer].

(d) *It is likely [Nonye to be a successful lawyer].

In (50a), Nonye is the understood subject of the bracketed clause. This is shown by its D-structure representation in (50b). The verb to be in the bracketed clause of (50b) is an infinitival predicate, hence it lacks the [$\bar{t}$ Tns, +AGR] INFL element to enable it assign Nominative Case to the subject (Nonye) of its clause. Consequently, the NP Nonye is forced to vacate its subject position in the bracketed clause. The subject (Nonye) of the bracketed clause in (50b) is now "raised" to the empty subject position in the matrix clause, as shown in (50a). The derived subject Nonye in the matrix clause of (50a) is assigned Nominative Case by the [$\bar{t}$ Tns, +AGR] INFL element of that clause. This accounts for the grammaticality of (50a). As indicated in (48a) the derived subject in the matrix clause, and its subject trace t in the subordinate clause are coindexed.

The subject Nonye in (50c) remains in situ in the bracketed clause because the verb in that clause is finite. As a result of this the [$\bar{t}$ Tns, +AGR] INFL element assigns Nominative Case to Nonye.

This contrasts with the subject position occupied by Nonye in the infinitival clause of (50d). Here, the subject Nonye is not assigned the relevant Case because there is no $\langle \bar{+}Tns, +AGR \rangle$ INFL element within that clause to assign Nominative Case to the subject Nonye. In addition to this fact, Nonye cannot be 'raised' to the subject position in the matrix clause because that position has already been filled by the expletive it. The subject of the bracketed clause in (50d) therefore violates the Case Filter (49), hence the ungrammaticality of (50d).

We have already noted that Case is assigned under government. The choice of the appropriate Case is determined by the governor (Horrocks 1987:103). Thus, while the $\langle \bar{+}Tns, +AGR \rangle$ INFL element is assumed to assign Nominative Case to the NP it governs, the verb assigns Accusative/Objective Case to its complement. The status assumed by INFL then means, according to Mohanan (1982)

that the verb cannot govern, and hence assign Case to its subject, and that if the INFL is $\langle \bar{-}AGR \rangle$, as in a non-finite clause in English, the subject is not governed in its own S (Mohanan 1982:323).

Dative/Obllique Case to its complement her. The pronoun subject him in the bracketed infinitival clause of (51c) is governed, as well as assigned, Accusative Case by the prepositional complementizer for. This is reflected in the morphological form of this pronominal subject. Similarly, in (51d) the pronominal subject him of the bracketed infinitival clause receives Accusative Case from the matrix clause verb believe. The verb believe assigns this Case across the maximal projection IP.

Verbs like believe and expect are referred to as ECM verbs. Such verbs
 / are assumed to subcategorize for infinitival clauses as complement. These infinitival clauses do not constitute barriers for outside government. For this reason, ECM verbs are assumed to govern and Case-mark across the relevant IPs (Haegeman 1991: 159).

52. (a) Àda hùrù ya

Ada see-pst him/her

"Ada saw him/her".

(b) Ọ gbàrà mbò $\left[\begin{array}{c} \bar{} \\ \text{pp} \end{array} \right]$ màkà gị]

He/She make-pst effort for you

"He/She made efforts on your behalf".

(c) `Ada kwèrè [gì ilū ya]

Ada agree-pst you to marry her

"Ada agreed to marry you".

(d) `Ada kwèrè [kà [i luọ yā]]

Ada agree-pst that you marry her.

"Ada agreed that you marry her".

The third person pronoun object ya in (51a) is assigned Accusative Case by the verb hu. In (52b) the third person pronoun subject o receives Nominative Case from the [+ Tns, + AGR] INFL element, while the preposition màkà assigns Oblique Case to its object complement, the second person pronoun gi. Example (52c) is analogous to the English sentence in (51d).

The bracketed infinitival clause subject gi in (52c) is governed and Case marked as Accusative by the matrix clause verb kwe, across the maximal **projection IP**. This shows the existence of Exceptional Case-marking in Igbò. Example, (52d) contrasts with (52c), even though the same verbs kwe and lu occur, respectively, in the matrix and bracketed complement clauses of both sentences.

The verb ilū in the infinitival complement clause of (52c) bears the $\langle \bar{-} \text{Tns}, -\text{AGR} \rangle$ feature, unlike its counterpart luo in the finite complement clause in (52d) which has the $\langle \bar{+} \text{Tns}, +\text{AGR} \rangle$ feature. Thus, while the subject qi of the infinitival complement clause in (52c) bears the Accusative form, its counterpart, the subject i in the complement clause of (52d) receives Nominative Case. This Nominative Case is assigned by the $\langle \bar{+} \text{Tns}, +\text{AGR} \rangle$ INFL element in the complement clause of (52d). The Case-marking mechanisms we have examined agree with Brody's Case-linking Requirement. This is a locality condition which stipulates that "the Case on an NP must be related to the Case on its governor" (Brody 1985:519).

2.7 Theta-(θ)-Theory

The θ -Theory of the G- θ framework is an adaptation from the pioneering works of Fillmore (1968), Jackendoff (1972) and Gruber (1976) who had tried to develop theories that would account for the semantic content of the arguments of a predicate. It is assumed that in addition to the assignment of the categorial, subcategorization, selectional, and morpho-phonological features to lexical items, they should

also be assigned θ -roles. These θ -roles specify what a given predicate in the sentence semantically encodes about each of its arguments. θ -Theory is therefore concerned with regulating the assignment of θ -roles to the structurally realized argument positions of a particular predicate. This theory is "definable in terms of the rules linking general conceptual structure to syntactic structure" (Speas 1990:10).

The assignment of θ -roles to the argument positions of a predicate is not done randomly. θ -Theory is highly constrained by the θ -Criterion which is stated in Chomsky (1981(a):136) as follows:

53. Each argument bears one and only one θ -role, and each θ -role is assigned to one and only one argument.

According to Dowty (1991) the implication of the θ -Criterion is that :

What the meaning entails about every argument must always be distinct enough that two arguments clearly do not fall under the same role definition (Dowty 1991:549.

In other words, the θ -Criterion ensures that θ -roles are assigned uniquely to the argument positions of a given predicate. It will be recalled that the verb nye in (36), repeated here as (54), was specified as

The assumption here is that the external θ -role is assigned 'Compositionally', since the nature of this role is determined by the entire verb phrase, not just by the verb alone.

Thus, the external θ -role is assigned by the verb and its internal argument positions (Radford 1988:386).

Levin and Rappaport (1986) state that some of the θ -roles selected by a:

verb may need to be assigned by other θ -role assigners, typically prepositions. Therefore, an NP may be the argument of a verb yet receive its θ -role from a θ -role assigner other than the verb, (Levin and Rappaport 1986: 638).

Take the case of the verb kwanye as in (56a-b).

56. (a) Kwanye (pack into) $\langle +V, -N \rangle$; $\langle \text{---NP PP} \rangle$
Agent $\langle$ Theme, Loc. $\rangle$

(b) Chikē kwanyèrè afere (Theme) nà òkàtà (Loc.)

Chike pack into-pst plate in basket

"Chike packed the plates into the basket".

The verb kwanye takes three arguments. The subject position occupied by the NP Chikē is the external argument. This position is assigned the Agent θ -role. The two internal argument positions receive their θ -roles by different θ -role assigners. The NP position adjacent to the verb kwanye is assigned the θ -role Theme directly by the verb,

while the NP position adjacent to the preposition na receives the Locative (Loc) θ -role from the preposition. This preposition na is incidentally a governor as well as a Case assigner. Now, contrast the Lexical-Thematic Representation in (54) with that of (56a). In (54) the Goal θ -role is the first constituent in the internal argument structure, with the Theme as the second member. This order is reversed in (56a) where the Theme role is the first member, while the Locative θ -role comes second. Perhaps the Goal role in (54) precedes the Theme because there is no other governor and θ -role assigner other than verb. This contrasts with the Locative θ -role in (56a) where the indirect object is governed and assigned θ -role by the preposition na.

The facts which emerge from our discussion of sentences (55) and (56b) give an insight into the nature of Igbo verbs which occur with double objects. We notice that when the preposition is incorporated⁴ in the verb, the Benefactive/Goal role precedes the Theme. However, when the verb takes a lexical preposition, the argument positions are reversed. In this case, the Theme role precedes the Benefactive/Locative role. This claim is exemplified as follows:

⁴Baker (1988(a):229 defines incorporation as "the syntactic movement of an X^0 category to adjoin to its X^0 governor". This X^0 movement is an instance of a generalized syntactic movement (Move- α) which involves a lexical category (N, V, P or A etc) rather than a phrasal category (NP, VP, PP, OR AP etc). See also Uwalaka on X^0 -Movement.

57. (a) **Ibè kòròrò hà akukọ**
 Ibe tell-pst-Appl them story
 "Ibe told them a story".
- (b) **Ibè kòròrò akukọ banyere hā**
 Ibe tell-pst story about them
 "Ibe told a story about them".
58. (a) **Àda tèèrè Òkoro ofe egwūsi**
 Ada cook-pst-Appl Okoro egwūsi soup
 "Ada cooked some soup for Okoro".
- (b) **Àda tèrè ofe egwūsi màkà Òkoro**
 Ada cook-pst soup egwusi for Okoro
 "Ada cooked some egwusi soup for Okoro".
59. (a) **Ọjì sùrùrù m akwà ahù**
 Oji wash-pst-Appl me cloth that
 "Oji washed the cloth for me"
- (b) **Ọjì sùrùrù akwà ahù màkà m**
 Oji wash-pst cloth that because of me
 "Oji washed the cloth for my sake".
60. (a) **Ike gbààrà m ògìgè**
 Ike make-pst Appl me fence
 "Ike made a fence for me".

(b) Ike gbàrà ògìgè n' ubi

Ike make-pst fence in farm

"Ike built a fence on the farm".

The (a) sentences in (57-60) illustrate cases in which the preposition is incorporated into the verb, while the (b) sentences show the occurrence of a lexical preposition.

In English for example the verb give exhibits two options in terms of its Lexical-Thematic Representation in (61a).

(b) John gave the books to Mary.

(c) John gave Mary the books

For option (61(a)i) the Theme role is the first member in the verb's internal argument structure, while for option (61(a)ii) the Goal role assumes the first position. The constituent order of the internal arguments in (61b) and (61c) are represented by the Lexical-Thematic Representation of (61(a)i) and (61(a)ii) respectively. The verb give in (61b) governs the

NP books and so directly assigns it the θ -role Theme, whereas the preposition to governs and assigns the θ -role Goal to the NP Mary. In (61c) the Goal NP Mary is not governed by any preposition. The pattern exhibited here is similar to what we have in the Igbo examples, (54) and (57-60).

Having examined three-place predicates such as nye and kwanve in Igbo, we will now consider two-place and one place predicates like ky and nwy, respectively.

The verb ky has the capability of exhibiting two options in terms of its Lexical Thematic Representation (62a).

- 62 (a) Ky (ring); $\langle \bar{+}V, -N \rangle$
- i $\langle \bar{\quad} \text{NP} \bar{\quad} \rangle$
Agent $\langle \text{Theme} \rangle$
- ii $\langle \bar{\quad} \text{NP} \bar{\quad} \rangle$
Theme

(b) Òbi kùrù mgbìrìngba
Obi rang-pst bell
"Obi rang the bell".

(c) Mgbìrìngba kùrù
Bell rang-pst
"The bell rang".

In (62a), both the Agent (external) and Theme (internal) θ -roles are expressed, as in (62b). A different picture is however

presented in (62(a)ii) as typified by (62c). Here, it does appear that the verb has suppressed its external θ -role. Thus, in the Lexical-Thematic Representation of the verb ky, the θ -role assignment options it permits follow from the verb's membership of the ergative class of verbs. For this class of verbs, "the NP which functions as the surface subject occurs within the VP in D-structure" (Jones 1988:90). At S-structure therefore the Theme θ -role becomes the subject of the sentence, as illustrated in (62c). There are verbs which exhibit three options in their Lexical-Thematic Representation. The English verb destroy is an example of such verbs.

- (b) The enemy destroyed the city.
 (c) The city was destroyed by the enemy
 (d) The city was destroyed.

Sentences (63b-d) are paraphrases of each other. (63c-d) are the passive forms of (63b).

Example (63b) reflects option (63(a)i) in the verb's Lexical-Thematic Representation. Here, both the external and internal θ -roles are expressed. For option (63(a)ii), The external θ -role is suppressed, but it occurs as a by phrase at the end of the sentence. Sentence (63c) illustrates this. In (63d) the external θ -role (the Agent) is suppressed and is not realized phonetically. The Theme θ -role in (63(a)i) and (63(a)ii) becomes the S-structure subject. The suppression of the external θ -role in passive structures is based on the assumption that the passive morphology of the verb absorbs its Agent θ -role. Thus, in support of this claim Levin and Rappaport (1986) assert that

The affixation of the passive morpheme to a verb prevents the verb from assigning its external θ -role to the $\langle \bar{NP}, \bar{S} \rangle$ position (Levin and Rappaport 1986:645, (cf also Baker (1988:385) and Stroik (1992:129)).

Consider now the Igbo verb nwu, a one-place predicate verb which has only one argument position to which it assigns a θ -role.

64. (a) nwu (die): $\langle +V, -N \rangle$ $\langle \text{---} \emptyset \rangle$
 Theme $\langle \emptyset \rangle$

(b) Ughò ànwuola
 Ugho die-perf
 "Ugo has died".

The verb nwu does not subcategorize for any internal argument, as its Lexical-Thematic Representation (64a) shows. The only argument position is the external argument which has the θ -role Theme.

At this juncture, we examine the manner in which the external θ -role is selected. Consider such Igbo and English verbs ku in (62(a)ii) and destroy in (63(a)ii) and (iii) respectively. In these examples, the θ -role Theme is selected as the S-structure subject. In recent G-B literature, as in Belletti and Rizzi (1988:344), Speas (1990:10) and Dowty (1991:575) it is argued that there is need to recognize that there is a principle by which arguments are ordered in the Lexical-Thematic Representation of a given predicate. This principle is referred to as the Thematic Hierarchy (Speas 1990:15). In order to account for the choice of the external θ -role, we adopt Speas (1990:16) and Dowty's (1991:578) Hierarchy stated as follows:

(where > = greater than).

As Belletti and Rizzi (1988:344) claim

A plausible generalization of this statement would consist in a general thematic hierarchy: (1) Agent,

(2) Experiencer,...

(3) Theme and the instruction that syntactic configurations projected from a given θ -grid should reflect the hierarchy, so that for every pair of θ -roles in the grid, the higher role in the hierarchy is projected to a higher structural position.

Let us consider the implication of the above claim in the light of the external argument selection by the predicates ku and destory in (62c) and (63c-d) above. As (62c) shows, the Agent role is unrealized. In the absence of the Agent role, the Theme role becomes the highest in the Thematic hierarchy and so assumes the role of the external argument. The Theme role in (63c) surfaces as the S-structure subject, with the Agent relegated to the adjunct position as a by phrase. While giving credence to this view Cowper (1992) says that:

the Agent, although not itself an argument of the verb, can be thought of as being identified with the implicit argument of the verb (Cowper 1992:82).

The analysis of (63d) is analogous to that of (62c).

We have examined the θ -Theory in relation to the assignment of θ -roles to the arguments of a given predicate. We also examined the Lexical-Thematic Representation of a set of Igbo and English verbs.

The conclusion to be drawn from our observation is that the Thematic Hierarchy of θ -roles is crucial in determining which role is realized as the external argument of a given predicate.

2.8 Bounding Theory

Bounding Theory is the module of grammar that constrains the process, Move- α . This theory is proposed to ensure that the movement or displacement of a given constituent does not cross more than one bounding node. Bounding Theory is defined in terms of subjacency. Subjacency is "a measure of the structural distance between two nodes in a tree" (Cowper 1992:120). As Radford (1988:569) puts it, subjacency determines "how far a given constituent can be moved in any single rule application".

Subject to parametric variation, the nodes that count for subjacency include NP, S, and S'. In English, it is assumed that NP and S are bounding nodes, whereas in Ìgbò, NP and S' count as bounding nodes for subjacency (Uwalaka 1991:195). Sells (1985) describes the Bounding Theory as the theory which ensures:

that domains of rule application must be relatively close to each other - not as close as adjacent, but rather one step removed, hence subjacent (Sells 1985:48).

This statement is represented formally in Cole (1982:139) as follows:

66.X....[̄ α ...[̄B... Y...]

where α and B are bounding nodes. In effect (66) states that Move- α cannot involve X and Y if α and B are bounding nodes and thus constitute a barrier.

This means that Move- α should not take a constituent across two bounding nodes or barriers in one fell swoop. Here, we adopt the definition of the Subjacency Condition which is stated in Cowper (1992:121) as follows:

67. A trace must be 1-subjacent to its closest antecedent in a chain. Consider sentence (68), taken from Chomsky (1986(a):153):

68. * $\bar{\text{Who}}$ $\bar{\text{CP}}$ $\bar{t}_i$ $\bar{\text{C}}$ $\bar{\text{does}}$ $\bar{\text{John}}$ $\bar{\text{believe}}$ $\bar{\text{NP}}$ $\bar{\text{the claim}}$ $\bar{\text{CP}}$ $\bar{t}_i$ $\bar{\text{that}}$ $\bar{\text{C}}$

$\bar{\text{Bill}}$ saw t_i $\bar{\text{J}} \bar{\text{J}} \bar{\text{J}} \bar{\text{J}} \bar{\text{J}} \bar{\text{J}} \bar{\text{J}} \bar{\text{J}} ?$

The deviance of (68) results from the Subjacency violation involving wh-movement out of the complex NP the claim that Bill saw t_i . In the first cycle, the wh-element moves into the lower (Spec, CP) position. It then moves finally into the matrix $\bar{\text{Spec, CP}}$. In this last movement, the moved wh-element crosses more than one bounding node: the NP the claim and the IP John believe in one fell swoop, since there is no 'escape hatch' between the two bounding nodes (NP and IP).

Subjacency is not violated by moving the wh-element from the lowest $\bar{\text{Spec, CP}}$ position in a successive-cyclic manner until it reaches the highest $\bar{\text{Spec, CP}}$. This cyclic movement is usually preferred to as the 'Comp-to-Comp wh-movement'. The empty COMP position provides an 'escape hatch' for the wh-element. Consider example (69) below:

69. $\bar{\text{whom}}$ $\bar{\text{CP}}$ $\bar{\text{I}}$ $\bar{\text{C}}$ $\bar{\text{did}}$ $\bar{\text{IP}}$ $\bar{\text{Bill}}$ say $\bar{\text{CP}}$ $\bar{t}'_i$ $\bar{\text{that}}$ $\bar{\text{C}}$

$\bar{\text{John}}$ would meet t_i $\bar{\text{J}} \bar{\text{J}} \bar{\text{J}} \bar{\text{J}} \bar{\text{J}} \bar{\text{J}} \bar{\text{J}} \bar{\text{J}} ?$
IP

In sentence (69) the wh-element moves into the lower $\bar{\text{Spec, CP}}$ position, crossing only one bounding node (the lower IP).

Hence, the resultant string is grammatical.

We now examine the following Ìgbò sentences and their associated representations in terms of the subadjacency Condition.

70. (a) Èbeē_i kà Àda gàrà, t_i?
 Where that Ada go-pst t
 "Where did Ada go to?"

71. (a) * $\bar{\angle}$ Onye_i $\bar{\angle}$ kà $\bar{\angle}$ Ike tu $\bar{\angle}$ fùrù ego, $\bar{\angle}$ hà sì
 who that Ike lose-pst money they say
 $\bar{\angle}$ nà $\bar{\angle}$ Ogù zìtèèrè ti_i $\bar{\angle}$ $\bar{\angle}$ $\bar{\angle}$ $\bar{\angle}$ $\bar{\angle}$ $\bar{\angle}$?
 that Ogu send-pst t
- (b) * $\bar{\angle}$ Onye_i $\bar{\angle}$ kà $\bar{\angle}$ Ike tu $\bar{\angle}$ fùrù ego $\bar{\angle}$ hà sì
 CP C IP IP
 $\bar{\angle}$ t $\bar{\angle}$ nà $\bar{\angle}$ Ogù zìtèèrè ti_i $\bar{\angle}$ $\bar{\angle}$ $\bar{\angle}$ $\bar{\angle}$ $\bar{\angle}$ $\bar{\angle}$
 CP C IP

In (70b) the moved wh-element in $\bar{\angle}$ Spec, CP $\bar{\angle}$ position has crossed only one bounding node, the subject NP node. There is no Subjacency violation, hence the grammaticality of sentence (70). For (71b) the first movement of the wh-element within the most deeply embedded clause is in order. Only one bounding node, the subject NP node of that clause has been crossed before the wh-element lands in the $\bar{\angle}$ Spec, CP $\bar{\angle}$ of its clause. The subsequent movement leads to a violation of the Subjacency Condition as two bounding nodes, the subject NP nodes of the intermediate and matrix clauses, are crossed in one single movement. This Subjacency violation leads to the ungrammaticality of example (71b).

2.9 Control Theory

Control Theory is the sub-theory of grammar that encodes the relations involved in assigning reference to the empty subject of a non-finite clause. The mechanism involved in encoding these relations is stated lucidly by Bresnan (1982:372) as

a relation of referential dependency between an unexpressed constituent (the controlled element) and an expressed or an unexpressed constituent (the controller).
The referential properties of the controlled element... are determined by those of the controller.

Thus, Control Theory specifies obligatory coreference between an antecedent and an empty node in certain constructions. Control Theory makes the claim that an empty NP in sentence initial position is subject to obligatory control by an antecedent NP. This control configuration is represented in Woolford (1986:313) as follows:

72. $NP_i \dots \bar{S} \langle \bar{NP}^e \bar{I}_i \bar{I} \rangle$

The examples in (71) are illustrative.

73. (a) $Dokit\grave{a}_i \text{ ch\grave{o}r\grave{o}} \langle \bar{k}\grave{a} \text{ ya lee } g\grave{i} \text{ \grave{a}h\grave{u}} \bar{I} \rangle$
 Doctor want that he examine you body)
 "The doctor wants to examine you".

- (b) Dọkítà_i chọrọ [$\bar{P}RO_i$ ilē gị àhụ]]
 Doctor want PRO to examine you body
 "The doctor wants to examine you".
- (c) Ùkọ egō m̀̀r̀̀r̀̀ Àda_i (PRO_i ir̀̀̀kpọ ahịa yā]]
 Scarcity of money cause Ada [$\bar{P}RO$ to sell off goods her]]
 "Lack of money made Ada to sell off her goods".
- (d) Òbi_i mà [$\bar{n}$ à PRO_i/arb isī nri adīghị òferè]]
 Obi know that PRO to cook food be-not easy
 "Obi knows that to cook is not easy".
- (e) [$\bar{P}RO_{arb}$ ihāpù okwu ahụ]] abàghị urù
 PRO to leave talk that be-not profit
 "To abandon the case is not profitable".

Example (73a) does not present a control structure because its bracketed complement clause has the pronoun ya as subject, and a finite verb from lee.

Sentences (73b-e) illustrate the application of the Control Theory. In each of these sentences, the bracketed infinitival clause contains a base-generated PRO. This PRO is considered to be a lexically-null category which bears pronominal features of person, number (and gender for those languages that have pronominal gender). It will be recalled that by the Extended Projection Principle, every clause must have a subject.

The implication of this requirement in relation to the bracketed complement clauses in (73b-e) is stated in Chomsky (1986(a):84) thus:

if some element is understood in a particular position, then, it is there in syntactic representation, either as an overt category that is phonologically realized or as an empty category assigned a phonetic form.

Both the Projection Principle and the Extended Projection Principle require that the infinitival clauses in (73b-e) be analysed as full sentences. These infinitival clauses are untensed and also lack an overt subject. For this reason, they are assigned PRO as subject.

It is assumed that PRO depends on its controller for reference. According to Chomsky (1980:8) "the lexical properties of the verb in the matrix clause" determines the position of the NP controller of PRO in the matrix clause. In (73b) the reference of PRO is dependent on the subject of the matrix clause. In this case PRO is said to be under subject control. The reference of PRO in (73c) is dependent on the object of the matrix clause in which case there is object control. The interpretation of PRO in example (73d) is two ways ambiguous. The first interpretation derives from the controller in the matrix clause subject position. The second interpretation is arbitrary or free in

reference because PRO can refer to anyone else in terms of its controller. It is in this sense that PRO is said to be generic in reference. PRO in example (73e) also refers freely or generically.

Each of the occurrences of PRO in (73b-e) shows that it appears in an ungoverned position where no Case is assigned. Hence, the claim is that nonfinite verbs lack the potential for assigning Case because of the absence of $\langle \bar{+}Tense, +AGR \rangle$ INFL in such verbs. Since Case is assigned under the configuration of Government, PRO therefore is Caseless and ungoverned. The restriction of PRO to an ungoverned position is referred to in G-B as the PRO Theorem (Lasnik and Uriagereka 1988:53).

However, let us examine the occurrence of PRO in governed and Case-assigned positions, contrary to the PRO Theorem.

74. (a) *Ada_i chòrò $\langle \bar{k}a \text{ PRO}_i \text{ gaa ah} \bar{i}a \bar{a} \rangle$

Ada want that PRO go market

(b) Ada_i chòrò $\langle \bar{k}a \text{ ya}_i \text{ gaa ah} \bar{i}a \bar{a} \rangle$

Ada want that she go market

"Ada wants to go to the market".

75. (a) *Dokità_i kwùrù $\langle \bar{n}a \text{ PRO}_i \text{ gà-àgwọ g} \bar{i} \bar{a} \rangle$

Doctor say-pst that PRO will-cure you

(b) Dokità_i kwùrù $\langle \bar{n}a \text{ ya}_i \text{ gà-àgwọ g} \bar{i} \bar{a} \rangle$

Doctor say-pst that he will-cure you

"The Doctor said that he would treat you".

76. (a) *Uchè₁ biara [Rà O₁ zùte PRO₁]
 Uche come-pst that she meet PRO
- (b) Uchè₁ biara [kà O₁ zùte enyì ya]
 Uche come-pst that she meet friend her
 Uche came to meet her friend.

The verbs in the bracketed complement clauses in examples (74)-(76) are finite verb forms, with [_S+Tns, +AGR] INFL which govern and Case-mark the subject. In examples (74a) and (75a) PRO functions are the subject of the complement clause, whereas in (76a) it occurs as the object of the verb zùte. These subject and object positions occupied by PRO in these examples are governed and Case-marked positions. As a result, the PRO Theorem is violated, hence the ungrammaticality of the (a) sentences in (74)-(76). You will notice that the positions analogous to the ones occupied by PRO in the (a) sentences are filled by lexical NPs in the (b) examples of (74)-(76). These lexical NPs are governed and Case-marked by their appropriate governors and Case assigners. For this reason the sentences are grammatical.

Finally, let us examine PRO in the light of the θ -Criterion (53). This criterion ensures that every argument position bears exactly one θ -role. This requirement notwithstanding, it is claimed that there are instances where the θ -Criterion appears to be violated. Consider example (77) below:

77. Àda₁ gàrà ahĩa [PRO₁ ìchàtàrà gĩ akwà]]
 Ada go-pst market PRO to cut-App1 you cloth
 "Ada went to the market to buy a cloth for you".

In (77) the matrix clause subject Àda is the controller of PRO in the subordinate clause. The subject Àda is assigned the θ -role Agent in the matrix clause. As the controller of PRO, the NP Àda receives the θ -role Agent in the subordinate clause. This appears to contradict the θ -Criterion (53). As Chomsky (1986(a):97) claims, there is no such violation of the θ -Criterion "because each subject - VP relation would be analyzed as a distinct minimal chain with only one θ -role assigned to each chain" (Valin 1986:583). Thus in (77) the matrix and complement clauses are assumed to constitute distinct chains, and their subject positions "analyzed as being two distinct but overlapping minimal chains" (Valin 1986:Ibid).

2.10. The Empty Category Principle (ECP)

The ECP is a requirement that empty categories, namely NP-trace and Wh-trace (variable) must be properly governed. It is thus the ECP that specifies the formal licensing condition for traces. Ordinarily, simple government will not adequately guarantee the licensing of traces. By simple government, we mean government by such lexical heads as N, V, P, A, and INFL which are assumed to govern and Case-mark

their complements. Traces have to be licensed in a special way, hence the notion of 'Proper Government' which ensures that traces have to occur in certain positions. There are two quite distinct ways in which Proper Government can be achieved. These are namely lexical government, and antecedent government. In lexical government, a head theta-governs a constituent if it both governs and theta-marks it. Antecedent government, on the other hand, is government by a coindexed maximal projection. Therefore, either a head or a coindexed maximal projection can function as a proper governor under the right conditions (Haegeman 1991:403-404).

The Projection Principle requires that constituents which have undergone movement leave traces behind to preserve the categorial expression of argument relationships. Where and when such a constituent can move will then be restricted. This is because any traces left behind by the moved constituent must be properly governed in accordance with the ECP (Lasnik and Saito 1984:235). In G-B, the ECP is stated as follows:

78. B is properly governed by α if it is governed by α and a certain kind of connection holds between α and β (Chomsky 1986(b):17). In (78) the assumed connection that holds between α and β is that of θ -government or antecedent

government. Let us adopt Haegeman's (1991:404) definition of government which incorporates both head-and antecedent-government.

79. α governs B iff
- (i) α is a governor
 - (ii) α m-commands B
 - (iii) No barrier intervenes between α and B
 - (iv) Minimality is respected.

Where governors are:

- (a) heads,
- (b) coindexed XPs.

The Minimality Condition (79iv) is formulated as follows in Chomsky (1986(b):42):

80. .. α ... $\bar{Y}$... δ ... B]
 α does not govern B if Y is a projection of δ excluding α .

. According to Chomsky (1986(b):42) the Minimality Condition fails to hold of the configuration (80) if * δ 'protects' B from government by α even though Y may not be a barrier or even a maximal projection*.

Following the establishment of the concepts in (79) and (80) above, we now consider the structures in which the relevant traces appear. We will start by considering lexical government (θ -government) which holds between the trace of the preposed object of the verb in an embedded clause and its lexical head.

81. whom_i do $\langle \bar{\text{you}} \text{ predict } \langle \bar{t}'_i \text{ that } \langle \bar{\text{the panel will}} \text{ interview } t_i \rangle \rangle \rangle ?$

The object trace t in the subordinate clause of (81) is governed by the verb interview. This verb equally θ -marks the position vacated by the moved wh-phrase. Consequently, this object trace is properly governed because it occupies a position which is governed and Case-marked by the lexical head interview. In addition, this lexical head θ -governs the object position occupied by the wh-trace. Hence, the ECP is satisfied.

We shall next consider the status of the intermediate trace t' in (81). Before then, let us examine the case of antecedent-government involving extraction from the subject position of an embedded clause in (82) below:

82. $*\text{Who}_i$ do $\langle \bar{\text{you}} \text{ think } \langle \bar{t}'_i \text{ that } \langle \bar{t}_i \text{ killed the goat} \rangle \rangle \rangle ?$

Example (82) is an ungrammatical string. This can be accounted for in terms of the ECP and the 'That-trace' Effect.

First, the subject trace t in the subordinate clause of (82) is governed by INFL. The subject position is a position to which INFL assigns Nominative Case. It is also a position indirectly θ -marked by the VP configuration (Haegeman 1991:61). It is assumed that the INFL governor of the trace is defective since INFL $\langle$ does not belong to the set of proper governors.

But this trace needs to be properly governed from outside its IP. The complementizer that intervenes between the intermediate trace t' in $\langle \bar{S}_{\text{Spec}}, \text{CP} \rangle$ and the subordinate clause subject trace t. Being the head of CP, the complementizer that is a potential governor.

The intermediate trace in $\langle \bar{S}_{\text{Spec}}, \text{CP} \rangle$ is coindexed with the subject trace, hence it can potentially antecedent-govern its coindexed trace. In (82), it does appear that there are two potential governors for the subordinate clause subject trace. The complementizer that, and the intermediate trace t' in $\langle \bar{S}_{\text{Spec}}, \text{CP} \rangle$ are the potential governors. By the Minimality requirement in (80), the intermediate trace cannot govern its coindexed subject trace in the subordinate clause because the intervening complementizer that is equally a potential governor for the subject trace. However, that does antecedent-govern the subject trace, since that is not coindexed with it. Hence, the subject trace is not antecedent-governed by the complementizer that. The absence of a proper governor for the subordinate clause subject trace t results in an ECP violation (Haegeman 1991:407).

Secondly, (82) shows that extraction of the subject of an embedded clause over an overt complementizer is not permissible in English. It is on account of this that the **effect** of the complementizer that on the subject trace is

referred to as the "That-trace' Effect. This is formulated configurationally in (83) as follows:

83. *...[that [t...]]]
 CP IP

The configuration in (83) is stated as a filter which prohibits the extraction of the subject of an embedded clause, but allows the extraction of its object (Uwalaka 1991:95). However, it is possible to rescue the ungrammaticality of (82) by dispensing with the overt complementizer that.

84. Who_i do [you think [t'_i [t_i killed the goat]]]] ?
 CP IP IP

The embedded clause subject trace t in (84) is antecedent-governed by its coindexed intermediate trace t' in the lower [Spec, CP]. There is no barrier which blocks antecedent-government from holding between the intermediate trace t' and its coindexed subject trace t. This is unlike the case of the ungrammatical string in (82) where the complementizer that constitutes a barrier that prevents antecedent-government from holding between the coindexed intermediate and subject traces.

In (84), the intermediate trace t' in the lower [Spec, CP] is not governed by the matrix verb think. This

verb neither subcategorized for the $\langle \text{Spec}, \text{CP} \rangle$, nor does it θ -govern it. Rather, the intermediate trace is regarded as the head of the lower CP. As claimed by Lasnik and Uriagereka 1988:96) "the head of S' (CP) is accessible for Proper Government from outside its S'". The intermediate trace then can be antecedent-governed by its coindexed wh-phrase in $\langle \text{Spec}, \text{CP} \rangle$ of the matrix clause, hence there is no ECP violation. This accounts for the grammaticality of (84). In like manner, the intermediate trace in the lower $\langle \text{Spec}, \text{CP} \rangle$ in (81) is antecedent-governed by its coindexed wh-phrase in the matrix clause $\langle \text{Spec}, \text{CP} \rangle$.

The Igbo examples below will be examined with regard to the ECP. We start by ^{considering} extraction from object position, a position governed and Case-marked by the verb.

85. (a) $\text{Ònye}_i \text{ kà } \langle \text{unū hūrù } t_i \rangle?$
 CP IP

Who that you-pl see-pst t?

"Whom did you see?"

(b) $\text{Gì nī}_i \text{ kà } \langle \text{Òbi chère } \langle t_i \text{ nà } \langle \text{Ada mèrè } t_i \rangle \rangle \rangle?$
 CP IP CP

What that Obi think t' that Ada do-pst t

"What does Obi think that Ada did?"

The object trace t in (85a), and its analogue in the embedded clause of (85b) are governed and θ -marked by their respective head-governors hùrù and mèrè. Hence these object traces are properly governed. In (85b) the intermediate trace t' in the $\langle \text{Spec, CP} \rangle$ of the embedded clause is antecedent-governed by its coindexed Wh-phrase in the matrix $\langle \text{Spec, CP} \rangle$. Thus in examples (85a-b) the ECP is not violated, as all the traces are properly governed. That accounts for the grammaticality of the strings in (85).

The following examples, however, illustrate an ECP violation, as well as the case of preposition stranding.

85. (a) Ònye_i kà $\langle \text{unū hùrù } t_i \rangle$?
 CP IP

Who that you-pl see-pst t?

"Whom did you see?"

(b) Gīnī_i kà $\langle \text{Òbi chère } \langle t'_i \text{ nà } \langle \text{Àda mèrè } t_i \rangle \rangle \rangle$?
 CP IP CP

What that Obi think t' that Ada do-pst t

"What does Obi think that Ada did"

The object trace t in (85a), and its analogue in the embedded clause of (85b) are governed and θ -marked by their respective head-governors hùrù and mèrè. Hence these object traces are

properly governed. In (85b) the intermediate trace t' in the $\langle \text{Spec, CP} \rangle$ of the embedded clause is antecedent-governed by its coindexed Wh-phrase in the matrix $\langle \text{Spec, CP} \rangle$. Thus in examples (85a-b) the ECP is not violated, as all the traces are properly governed. That accounts for the grammaticality of the strings in (85). The following examples, however, illustrate an ECP violation, as well as the case of preposition stranding.

86. (a) * $\text{Ònye}_i \text{kà} \langle \text{unū} \text{biarà} \langle \text{màkà } t_i \rangle \rangle \rangle ?$
 CP IP PP

Who that you-pl come for t?

(b) * $\text{Èbeē}_i \text{kà} \langle \text{Òbi} \text{mà} \langle \text{t}'_i \text{nà} \langle \text{òke} \text{ahū} \text{rùgbùrù} \rangle \rangle \rangle ?$
 CP IP CP IP

Where that Obi know t' that rat that drown-pst

$\langle \text{nà } t_i \rangle \rangle \rangle ?$

PP

in t?

The traces in the PP configuration are not properly governed because the preposition màkà (86a) and nà (86b) do not belong to the subset of proper governors (cf(78) for the definition of proper government). Only verbs can head-govern traces, though prepositions govern and Case-mark their object NPs when such NPs are phonologically realized. When without their object NPs as in (86a) and (86b), prepositions are said

to be 'stranded'. As in the PFs in (86a-b), the stranded prepositions "constitute a Minimality barrier.... thus preventing the verb from governing the relevant trace" (Uwalaka 1991:193). In languages such as English where prepositions can be stranded, a reanalysis rule is applied "to 'absorb' the preposition into the verb...." (Hornstein and Weinberg 1981:63, Riemsdijk and Williams 1986:147).

The ungrammatical strings in (86a-b) can however be rescued by adopting the 'pied-piping' strategy. By this strategy both the prepositions and their object complement are 'pied-piped' (extracted and moved) to the $[-\text{Spec}, \text{CP}]$ as the following sentences indicate.

87. (a) $[-\text{CP}]$ $[-\text{CP}]$ Mākà ònye $[-\text{IP}]$ kà $[-\text{IP}]$ unū bìarà t_i]] ?
 CP PP IP

For who that you-pl come-pst t

"For whom did you come?"

(b) $[-\text{CP}]$ $[-\text{CP}]$ N'èbeē $[-\text{IP}]$ kà $[-\text{IP}]$ Òbi mà $[-\text{CP}]$ t' $[-\text{IP}]$ nà $[-\text{IP}]$ òke anū
 CP PP IP CP IP

In where that Obi know t' that rat that

rùgbùrù t_i]]]] ?

"Where does Obi know that the rat got drowned?"

Now that the prepositions and their complement have been moved to the $\left[\text{Spec, CP} \right]$ in (87a) and the matrix clause $\left[\text{Spec, CP} \right]$ in (87b), the object traces have come to be properly governed by their respective verbs bìara (87a) and rùgbùrù in (87b). In (87b), also the wh-element in the matrix $\left[\text{Spec, CP} \right]$ antecedent governs the coindexed intermediate trace t . The ECP is satisfied.

Now consider extraction from the subject of an embedded clause in (88).

88. (a) *Ònye_i kà $\left[\text{Òbi gwàrà Àda} \left[\text{t}'_i \text{ kà} \left[\text{t}_i \text{ gaara} \right] \right] \right]$
 CP IP CP IP
 Who that Obi tell-pst Ada t' that t go-pst-Appl
 yā ahia]]]?
 him market]
- (b) *Ònye_i kà $\left[\text{Ibē mà} \left[\text{t}'_i \text{ nà} \left[\text{t}_i \text{ gàrà ahia} \right] \right] \right]$
 CP IP CP IP
 Who that Ibe know t' that t go-pst market?

In each of the embedded clauses in (88a-b), the subject trace occupies the position governed and Case-marked by the relevant $\left[+\text{Tns, } +\text{AGR} \right]$ INFL. In these examples however, INFL cannot govern the subject traces, since it does not θ -mark the subject position. In other words INFL is a defective governor in the sense of Proper Government. As head of CP, the complementizers ka (88a) and na (88b) in the embedded clauses seem to be potential governors for the subject trace t' . But

complementizers are not proper governors. Perhaps, the subordinate clause subject trace would seem to be antecedent-governed by its coindexed intermediate trace in the $[^{\text{Spec}}, \text{CP}]$ of its clause. But the subject trace is "protected from antecedent-government by" the complementizer (ka (88a), na (88b), "by virtue of the Minimality Condition" (89) (Chomsky 1986(b):47). The ECP is violated as the intervening complementizer between the intermediate trace in the subordinate clause $[^{\text{Spec}}, \text{CP}]$ and the subject trace results in the 'That-trace' Effect. However, the intermediate trace is antecedent-governed by its coindexed wh-phrase in the matrix clause $[^{\text{Spec}}, \text{CP}]$.

In spite of the ungrammaticality of the strings in (88a-b), they can be rescued from the ECP violation. As Uwalaka (1991:197) rightly points out, the deviant strings in (88) can be rendered grammatical by "the adoption of a resumptive pronoun" strategy.

89. (a) Dnye_i kà $[^{\text{Spec}} \text{Òbi}$ gwàrà Ada $[^{\text{Spec}} \text{kà}$ $[^{\text{Spec}} \text{O}_i$
 CP IP CP IP

who that Obi tell-pst Ada that he

gaara yā ahia]]]]?

go-pst-AppI him market

"Who did Obi ask Ada to go to the market for him?"

(b) Ònye_ikà ʎ̄-Ibē mà ʎ̄-nà ʎ̄-ò_i gàrà
 CP IP CP IP

Who that Ibe know that he go-pst

anĩa]]]?

market

"Who does Ibe know that he went to the market?"

Examples (89a-b) are grammatical because no ECP violation is involved. The reason is that the subject position of the embedded clauses in (89a-b) is filled by the resumptive pronoun $\bar{O}$ which is assumed to be base-generated (Lasnik and Uriagereka 1988:83). On the basis of this assumption, it is claimed that no traces are involved, since no movement has taken place.

We hold a contrary view on the base-generation of resumptive pronouns. We claim that a resumptive pronoun is derived from movement and it is assumed to resume the position vacated by its coindexed antecedent. A trace is not necessarily an empty category, it could equally be an anaphoric copy of a constituent that has undergone movement. (Wasow 1979:92). The resumptive pronoun is adopted as a strategy for circumventing the ECP violation.

From the foregoing discussion, we conclude that in Ìgbò the extraction of the object of a verb does not lead to an ECP violation. The trace which results from such an extraction

is lexically head-governed by the verb which governs and Case-marks such a position. In this case, proper government is involved. Again in Ìgbò, the NP complement of a preposition cannot be extracted out of the PP because the language does not allow preposition stranding. Ìgbò however adopts the piedpiping strategy to circumvent the ECP violation that could result from extracting the object of a preposition. Finally, extraction from the subordinate clause subject over an overt complementizer results in the 'That-trace' Effect (Uwalaka 1991:195). But the language adopts the resumptive pronoun strategy to circumvent such an ECP violation that could result from the 'That-trace' Effect.

2.11 Binding Theory

The Binding Theory is the module of grammar responsible for expressing or determining the relationship that holds between at least two linguistic elements. This module is formulated in terms of such S-structure configurational relationships as government and $\bar{a}$ -command.

In G-B Theory, two kinds of binding are distinguished: argument-binding (A-Binding) and non-argument-binding ($\bar{A}$ -Binding). In an A-binding relationship, the binder is said to be in an argument position. This is a position to which is

assigned a θ -role (A-position). On the other hand, the binder in an $\bar{A}$ -binding relationship is in a non-argument position, a position to which no θ -role is assigned ($\bar{A}$ -position). This position is typified by the $[-\text{Spec}, \text{CP}]$ (Jacobsen 1986:104).

The Binding Theory is expressed in terms of the Binding Conditions. These conditions are stated as Principles A, B and C as follows:

90. (a) An anaphor is bound in its governing category

Principle A

(b) A pronominal is free in its governing category

Principle B

(c) An R-expression is free Principle C (cf Chomsky)

1981(a):188, 1986(a):167).

Binding itself is defined as follows:

91. i. α binds B if α c-commands and is coindexed with B or

ii. α locally binds B if α binds B and there is no Y such that α binds Y and Y binds B

(Chomsky 1986(a):164-165).

The governing category for α (an anaphor or a pronominal) is its local domain. This is defined by Chomsky as

the minimal governing category of α where a governing category is a maximal projection containing both a subject and lexical category governing α (hence, containing α) (Chomsky 1986(a):169).

Given this definition, a governing category can only be assumed to be either an S (IP) or an NP. A governing category is further referred to as a "Complete Functional Complex (CFC)" (Chomsky 1986(a):169). It is said to be complete "in the sense that all grammatical functions compatible with its head are realized in it" (Chomsky 1986(a):169). According to Haegeman (1991), a governing category contains:

All the functions determined by the Projection Principle. It contains the head of a projection, the governor, i.e. the predicate which assigns the θ -roles, the governed elements, i.e. the complements, to which the internal θ -roles are assigned, and the subject, to which the external θ -role is assigned (Haegeman 1991:202).

The Binding Theory will feature prominently in the subsequent chapter. To avoid repetition, this module will come up for discussion in the relevant section.

2.12 Summary

This chapter gives an overview of the G_vB framework adopted in this study. The model is a revision of the earlier transformational generative models. Though the model has been

used extensively on European based linguistic data, it has not been widely applied to data from Nigerian languages.

We subjected a sample of Ìgbò data to the basic principles of G-B syntax and found that much of the data can be accounted for. For this reason, we adopted the G-B framework with the hope that it would equally account for much of the data on antecedent-anaphor relations in Ìgbò better than the earlier transformational generative models.

CHAPTER THREE
ANAPHORIC RELATIONS IN ÌGBÒ

3.0. Preliminaries

This chapter makes use of the Binding Theory to account for anaphoric relations in Ìgbò. Among other issues, the chapter examines the status of the emphatic pronoun, and the nature of verbs associated with anaphora.

3.1 A - and $\bar{A}$ - Binding

The nature and scope of this work has restricted us to the use of A-binding. For the purpose of contrast, we undertake a brief survey of A - and $\bar{A}$ -binding.

The following sentences illustrate A-binding.

- 92, (a) $\left[\bar{O}bi \ n\grave{a} \ Uzo \right]_i$ meborò ònwe hā_i
 Obi and Uzo disgrace -pst poss them
 Obi and Uzo disgraced themselves
- (b) $\bar{A}da_i$ s_i $\left[\bar{n}\grave{a} \left[\bar{y}a_i \ k\grave{o}r\grave{o} \ m\grave{a}k\grave{a} \ \grave{o}nwe \ y\bar{a}_i \right] \right]$
 CP IP
 Ada say that she tell-pst about poss her
 "Ada said that she talked about herself"

The local domain or governing category for the reflexive anaphor ònwe hā in (92a) is the entire sentence. Within this domain, the reflexive anaphor is coindexed with an m-commanding subject Òbi nà Uzo. There is in addition a governor, the verb

mebo which governs and Case marks the reflexive anaphor. Thus, principle A of the Binding Theory is satisfied, as the reflexive anaphor is bound in its governing category.

For sentence (92b) the reflexive anaphor onwe yā is bound in the subordinate clause which contains it. Example (92b) however illustrates binding involving a pair-wise coreference relation. This is a relationship that involves an anaphor bound in its governing category, and a remote antecedent in another clause. The subordinate clause pronominal subject ya m-commands the reflexive anaphor with which it is coindexed. The preposition mākà governs and Case-marks the reflexive anaphor. Principle A of the Binding Theory is satisfied.

There is need to relate the reflexive anaphor onwe yā in (92b) with the remote antecedent subject Ada in the matrix clause. To achieve this goal, we adopt Reinhart's (1983:71) coindexing procedure which is stated as follows:

Coindex a pronoun P with a c-commanding NP- α (α not immediately dominated by Comp or S') Conditions: (a) if P is an R-pronoun (ie a reflexive or reciprocal anaphor) α must be in its minimal governing category if P is a non-R-Pronoun, α must be outside its maximal governing category.

With the tree diagram (94) representing sentence (92b), we examine how a remote antecedent in the matrix clause can be

said to bind an anaphor in the subordinate clause.

94.

Following Condition (b) of (93), we coindex the subordinate clause pronominal subject ya with the matrix clause subject Ada which m-commands the subject of the subordinate clause. The matrix clause subject is not immediately dominated by S' (CP) since the NP Ada occurs in an argument position (A-position).

Both the co-indexed m-commanding matrix clause subject Ada, and the pronominal subject ya of the subordinate clause are not contained in the same local domain. The subordinate clause subject ya has its containing clause as its local domain since it is governed and Case-marked by the subordinate INFL. Hence, the subordinate clause subject ya is bound by the coindexed matrix clause subject Ada from where it derives its reference. Principle B of the Binding Theory is satisfied because the subordinate clause pronominal subject ya is free in its governing category. By extension, or Transitivity,⁵ in the sense of Wasow (1979:49), the reflexive anaphor onwe yā remotely derives its reference from the matrix clause subject Ada via the subordinate clause pronominal subject ya.

Having described A-binding, we now turn to $\bar{A}$ -binding.

Consider the following sentences:

⁵See pp. 20.

95. (a) Ònye_i kà [$\bar{A}$ Ada [$\bar{z}$ ùrù t_i]_{VP}] n'ùzò]?
 CP IP VP

Who that Ada meet-pst t on road

"Whom did Ada meet on the way?"

- (b) Ùzò_i, [$\bar{A}$ Òkorie gbapùtara ya_i]
 NP IP

Uzo, Okorie redeem-pst him

"Uzo, Okorie redeemed him".

The object trace in (95a) results from the movement of a wh-element into the [$\bar{A}$ Spec, CP], which is an $\bar{A}$ -position. The trace of the wh-element has the verb zù as its governor. This trace is coindexed with the wh-element ònye in [$\bar{A}$ Spec, CP] which m-commands it. Thus, the wh-trace is said to be $\bar{A}$ -bound by its m-commanding antecedent in [$\bar{A}$ Spec, CP], an $\bar{A}$ -position. Example (95b) is a left-dislocated sentence. Rivero (1980) describes left-dislocated sentences as those sentences which

have an NP set off by commas at the beginning of a clause-TOP position and a pronoun (or NP) which is anaphorically related to the phrase in TOP position (Rivero 1980:363).

Left-dislocated sentences are structures of adjunction which are base-generated (Lasnik and Uriagereka 1988:154).

In (95b) the NP Uzo occurs in sentence initial position. This position, created by adjunction, is said to be an $\bar{A}$ -position (Haegeman 1991:213). From this position, the NP Uzo $\bar{A}$ -binds the object pronoun ya, which is anaphorically related to it.

We have used the Binding Theory to show the two types binding: A- and $\bar{A}$ -binding. A-binding involves anaphors bound by antecedents in argument position. Conversely, the traces of wh-element, and coreferential nominals of left dislocated constituents fall under $\bar{A}$ -binding. Here, the antecedent-binder is in a non-argument position. In the subsequent chapters, our discussion will focus primarily on instances of A-binding since it relates directly to our work.

3.2. Structure of the Reflexive and Reciprocal Anaphors.

The $\dot{\text{Igb}}\dot{\text{o}}$ reflexive/reciprocal anaphors share a common morphological form. This form is made up of the derived nominal constituent onwe (possessor) plus the relevant personal pronoun, to be represented as X (cf section 2.6 (Table 1) for the $\dot{\text{Igb}}\dot{\text{o}}$ personal pronoun). The nominal onwe is derived by affixing the low tone nominalizing prefix ò/ò

to the verb root nwe (own, possess). This derivation can be roughly stated as follows:

96.

The low tone nominalizing prefix is a class-changing category, and it functions as the head of the derived nominal onwe. It is this nominalizing prefix which "determines the syntactic category of that construction" (Owolabi 1995:104). The constituent onwe inherits "the syntactic properties or features of its head" through percolation (Owolabi 1995:105). The configuration in (96) shows that Igbo shares the Lefthand Head Rule (LHR) with Yoruba. As Owolabi (1995:105-6) rightly observes, the LHR in Yoruba contradicts Williams (1981:248) universal Righthand Head Rule (RHR). The RHR is assumed to allow only the righthand member of a morphologically complex word the privilege of functioning as the head of the complex word.

The two nominal constituents of the reflexive/reciprocal anaphors (ònwè and the relevant pronominal form X) are juxtaposed to form a head-modifier 'Associative' construction, which is sketched as in (97) below:

An 'Associative' construction is defined as a construction "in which two nouns are put together to form a genitive phrase, with one acting as head" (Maduka-Durunze 1992:167). These two nouns are glossed roughly as N_1 of the type associated with N_2 (Emenanjo 1978:35).

The Associative construction has a characteristic tone pattern. Consider Table 2 below.

Reflexive/Reciprocal Anaphors

Table 2

N ₁	N ₂	N ₁	N ₂
onwe+	$\left. \begin{array}{l} \left\{ \begin{array}{l} m \\ gi \\ ya \end{array} \right\} \text{ sg} \end{array} \right\}$	Onwe +	$\left. \begin{array}{l} \bar{m} \text{ (myself)} \\ g\bar{i} \text{ (yourself)} \\ y\bar{a} \text{ (him/herself/itself)} \end{array} \right\}$
	$\left. \begin{array}{l} \left\{ \begin{array}{l} \grave{a}nyi \\ un\grave{u} \\ ha \end{array} \right\} \text{ pl} \end{array} \right\}$		$\left. \begin{array}{l} \left\{ \begin{array}{l} \bar{a}nyi \text{ (ourselves)} \\ un\grave{u} \text{ (yourselves)} \end{array} \right\} \text{ each other} \\ h\bar{a} \text{ (themselves)} \end{array} \right\}$

The second constituent (N₂) changes its tone if it belongs to tone Group 1(H) H, LH) but it retains its tone if it belongs to Tone Group 11 (HL, LL, HS). The first constituent (N₁) retains its tone if it belongs to Tone Group 1 but changes its tone if it belongs to Tone Group 11 and precedes a low tone

(L) Maduka-Durunze (1992:167-8). In Table 2, ònwé (N_1) retains its tone, since it belongs to Tone Group I. For the constituents in N_2 only unù retains its tone because it belongs to Tone Group 11.

Our configurational approach to the analysis of antecedent-anaphor relations in Ìgbò has been able to meet the subject-antecedent, M-command, clause mate, and the antecedent-anaphoric NP identity conditions. These structural requirements seem to be insufficient for interpreting the intended reflexive/reciprocal sense. We therefore need to provide a formalized semantic interpretation rule as a supplement to the configurational analysis. The semantic approach which we will adopt here relies heavily on Awoyale's (1985) insight.

Let us consider the partial configurations in (98b) and (99b). We will examine how (98b), which represents the non subject NP in (20), is interpreted anaphorically, as opposed to (99b), which also represents the non subject NP in (21). For convenience, examples (20a) and (21a) are repeated here as (98a) and (99a), respectively.

98. (a) Àda_i hùrù $\bar{\text{[ònwé [yā}_i\text{]]}$ n'anya
 Ada see-pst poss her in eye
 "Ada loves herself"

98. (b)

99. (a) Àda hùrù [dòkìtá [v̄a_i/j]] n' anya
 Ada see-pst doctor her in eye
 "Ada loves her doctor"

99. (b)

Each of the constituent elements in the configurations (98b) and (9b) bears a set of semantic features: $[-_+ \text{Ref1/Recip}]$, $[-_+ \text{Poss}]$, $[-_+ \text{Pron}]$, $[-_+ \text{AGR}_1/j]$, and $[-_+ \text{Sg}]$. Following Awoyale's (1985:10) analysis, the $[-_+ \text{Ref1/Recip}]$ sense is shifted on the head noun from the pronominal determiner which is coreferential with the subject NP. The feature $[-_+ \text{Poss}]$ is used to establish an association between

the head noun and the pronominal determiner. The $[^-_+Pron]$ feature makes reference to either a pronominal or nominal determiner. $[^-+AGR_{i/j}]$ is a feature restricted to a pronominal element. For example, $[^-+AGR_{i/j}]$ marks the pronominal determiner as either coreferential or disjoint in reference with the antecedent subject NP. The feature $[^-_+Sg]$ is necessary for the singular and plural distinction when the modifier of the head noun is a noun. (cf Awoyale (1985:9)).

In (98b), where the reflexive phrase of (98a) is contained, the assumption is that the features of the head noun ɔnwɛ (poss), together with those of its pronominal determiner ya (her) will account for the reflexive interpretation in the sentence. What justifies this claim is that in (98b) the head noun is invariably the noun ɔnwɛ (poss), hence the features $[^-_+Refl + Poss]$. The modifier of the head is always a pronominal. In addition, the pronominal determiner is coreferential with the subject NP, both sharing person and number agreement features. In this regard, the pronominal determiner is specified as $[^-_+Pron + AGR_i]$. It is necessary to point out that the reflexive/reciprocal sense is implicit in the pronominal determiner via the $[^-_+AGR_i]$ feature. This is to say that coreference is between the pronominal and the

antecedent subject NP. As a consequence, the features of the head in (98b) associate with those of the pronominal determiner for the reflexive interpretation intended in (98a)⁶. Assuming that a different head noun, other than ònwè (poss) is generated in the head position of (98b) (cf 99b), it will definitely block the intended reflexive interpretation.

We now examine the non subject NP of example (99a) in the light of (99b). In (99b), the head noun can be any noun, but never ònwè (poss). The possessive determiner could be a pronominal or a noun. With regard to this, we assign the features $[\bar{+}Poss \ \bar{+} \ Pron \ +AGR_{i/j} \ \bar{+}Sg]$ to the possessive determiner. We need to note that (99a) is ambiguous when the determiner is the third person $[\bar{+}Sg]$ (3₊Sg) pronoun. The features $[\bar{+}Poss + Pron + AGR_i]$ of the pronominal determiner associate with the $[\bar{-}Refl]$ feature of the head noun to derive the first reading, "Ada loves her own doctor". This interpretation is determined by the feature $[\bar{+}AGR_i]$ which bears the same index as the subject

⁶ Henceforth, we subsume (98b) for all the non-subject NP configurations which dominate the head noun ònwè (poss) and the appropriate pronominal determiner coindexed with the antecedent subject NP.

NP, in addition to the agreement features of person and number. For the second reading however, "Ada loves someone else's doctor", the possessive pronominal determiner and the subject NP are contra-indexed, even though both agree in person and number. The feature $\left[\begin{smallmatrix} +AGR \\ j \end{smallmatrix} \right]$ accounts for this reading.

At this juncture, we seem to have been able to account for the semantic readings associated with the configurations in (98b) for the reflexive sense in (98a), and (99b) for the genitival interpretation in (99a). To conclude therefore, we propose the following semantic interpretation rule for the reflexive/reciprocal anaphor in Igbo:

In a simplex sentence, assign the feature $\left[\begin{smallmatrix} +anaphor \end{smallmatrix} \right]$ to the non-subject NP whose head noun is invariably designated as ònwè (poss), and the pronominal determiner is coreferential with the subject NP. (cf Awoyale 1985:13).

3.3 Syntactic and Semantic Overview of the Reflexive and Reciprocal Anaphors

The reflexive and reciprocal anaphors exhibit some similarities and differences. Their reference is usually determined by a coindexed m-commanding antecedent. The assumption therefore is that the antecedent asymmetrically m-commands the anaphor which it binds. Both the reflexive and reciprocal anaphors are constrained by Principle A of the

Binding Theory which stipulates that an anaphor be bound within a local domain, defined as the governing category for the anaphor. In other words, the Binding Theory ensures that the antecedent and the anaphor occur in the same governing category.

According to Enc (1989:60), what follows from this requirement is the assumption that Principle A does not really constrain the antecedent but rather the anaphor which the antecedent binds.

3.4. The Reflexive Anaphor

We assume that the reflexive anaphor requires its referent to be the direct target of the action or state predicated by the verb (Hintikka and Kulas 1985:176). In other words, the arguments predicated by the verb refer to the same person.

The following sentences are examples.

100. (a) Àda kèrè ònwe yā_i òkpo n'isi

Ada knock-pst poss her knock on head

"Ada gave herself a knock on the head"

(b) Ha_i ēmeboṣṣa onwe hā_i n'ihu òhà

They disgrace-perf poss them in front public

"They have disgraced themselves in public"

- (c) Ibè_i kòòrò ànyí akúkò bányere onwe yā_i
 Ibe tell-pst-Ben us story about poss him
 "Ibe told us a story about himself"

In (100a) for instance, the action of giving a knock was performed by the subject Ada. The resultant knock landed on the head of the object, the reflexive anaphor onwe yā, who is the same entity as Ada, the subject.

We will next consider reflexive binding, using IP as the governing category for the anaphor. The reflexive anaphor onwe yā in (100a) is coindexed with its m-commanding antecedent, the subject Ada. There is a governor for the anaphor, the verb ke... Òkpo. The analysis of (100a) can be generalized over that of (100b) and (100c). However, in (100c) the anaphor onwe yā is governed by the preposition bányere, as exemplified in the tree diagram below.

101.

The anaphors in (100) are bound by their antecedents in accordance with Principle A of the Binding Theory. This is because within the IP which serves as their governing category, there is, for each anaphor, a governor and a coindexed m -commanding antecedent. In the examples that follow, we show the functioning of NP as a governing category.

102. (a) Nkowa Ibē_i nyèrè màkà ònwe yā_i dòrò anya

Explanation Ibe give-pst about poss him be-clear-
pst eye

"The explanation Ibe gave about himself was explicit"

(b) Ùgwù unū_i kwànyèèrè ònwe unū_i màsìrì ha

Prestige you-pl give-pst-Appl poss you-pl please-st them

"The respect you accorded yourselves pleased them"

(c) Ñdùmọdu i_i dūrù ònwe gī_i kàchà mmā

Advice you advise-Ben poss you surpass beauty

"The advice you give to yourself is the best"

The analysis of (102a) generalizes to sentences (102b-c). The configuration in (102d) shows an instance where an NP, which is immediately dominated by the matrix IP, functions as the governing category for the anaphor. The anaphor ònwé yá and its coindexed antecedent NP Ibè are contained within this governing category, the subject (Ibè) of the embedded clause M-commands its coindexed anaphor ònwé yá. The preposition màkà is the governor for the anaphor. Thus, in accordance with Principle A of the Binding Theory, the anaphor ònwé yá is bound by its m-commanding antecedent Ibè.

In the examples that follow, we investigate the binding of anaphors in imperative (Imp) sentences. Imperative sentences are used to make a request, or to issue a command. Such sentences usually have second person subject which may be overt, or non-overt (Radford 1988:333). We will draw our examples from two imperative sentence-types: those that optionally occur with an overt subject (103a-c), and those with 'understood' or implied subject (104a-c). Imperative sentences with overt subject are assumed to be more emphatic than those with implied or 'null subject'. When an overt subject occurs, it is usually marked off by a comma when

written, while in speech it is intonationally marked off by a pause after the overt subject.

The imperative in Ìgbò is associated with two verb forms. The first form occurs with a high tone harmonizing open vowel suffix. The second one uses the bare (or citation) form of the verb. The following examples are representative of imperative sentences with an overt subject.

103 (a) Àda_i, d̀ùò -∅_i ònwe gí_i ọ̀dù

Ada advise - Imp poss you advice

"Ada advise yourself"

(b) Ụm̀ù_i m, wèreǹù_i ònwe uǹù_i nyè Chukwu

Children my take-Imp-2pl poss you-pl give God

"My children, surrender yourselves unto God"

(c) Uǹù_i hu-∅_i onwe uǹù_i n'anya

You-pl see-Imp poss you-pl in eye

"You, love yourselves"

The verb form d̀ùò in example (103a) takes a high tone harmonizing open vowel suffix, whereas the verb forms wèrè and hu in (103b) and (103c) respectively occur in their citation forms. In the presence of an overt plural subject (but not a pronominal subject as in (103c) the imperative verb form takes a pronominal

clitic -nu⁷, which is base-generated in INFL.

In sentences (104a-c) the entire sentence acts as the governing category for the anaphor. For example, the reflexive anaphor ònwé gī in (103a) has the verb dù... ọdù as the governor, and the subject Ada as its coindexed m-commanding antecedent. In this context, Principle A of the Binding Theory is satisfied because the anaphor ònwé gī is bound in its governing category.

But now, consider the subjectless imperative sentences below:

104. (a) Kpúo-~~Ø~~_i ònwé gí_i akwà
Cover-Imp poss you cloth
"Cover yourself with a piece of cloth"
- (b) Ma-~~Ø~~_i ònwé gí_i ikpē
Convict-Imp poss you judgement
"Convict yourself"
- (c) Dúọ̀nù_i ònwé unù_i ọdù
Advise-Imp-2pl poss you-pl advice
"Advise yourselves"

⁷The pronominal clitic -nu is regarded as the weak second person plural, subject pronoun. This pronominal clitic is assumed to be base-generated in INFL, but subsequently "attaches morphologically to the head V with which it forms one complex lexical unit" (Haegeman 1991:557).

- (d) Wèrenù₁ ònwe unù₁ nyè Chukwu
 Take-Imp-2pl poss you-pl give God
 *Surrender yourselves unto God.

Sentences (103a) and (104a-b) are of the imperative-singular form, unlike examples (103b-c) and (104c-d) with a plural form. The pronominal clitic -nu features only in the plural imperative sentences. In the absence of this pronominal clitic in the singular imperative sentences such as in (103a) and (104a-b), we postulate an abstract pronominal clitic $\emptyset$.

In examples (104) the sentences is also assumed to be the governing category of the anaphor. Apparently, the sentences in (104) counter-exemplify Principle A of the Binding Theory. Though the reflexive anaphor has the verb as governor, the absence of a lexicalized subject in (NP, IP) seems to suggest that the reflexive anaphor in this case has no m-commanding antecedent. This would suggest that the anaphor lacks a governing category. In spite of this, our claim is that antecedent-anaphor relations in such sentences as (104a-d) are compatible with Principle A of the Binding Theory.

In order to show that the Igbo subjectless (null subject) imperative sentences does not provide counter-evidence to Principle A of the Binding Theory, we postulate a base-generated nominal element pro as the subject. One evidence in support of the postulation of a pro subject comes from Yoruba. According to Yusuf (1990:115).

Yoruba provides support for the 'you-as-subject-of-imperative' hypothesis. While Yoruba can say wá 'come', where plural or a socially higher addressee is involved, the imperative form will be e wá 'you (pl) come' with the second person overtly expressed. No other personal pronoun is possible in this context (Yusuf 1990: Ibid).

Again, the postulation of pro as the subject of the Ìgbò null subject imperative sentence is in accord with the pro of the pro-drop languages like Italian and Spanish. One of the fundamental properties of pro-drop languages like Italian and Spanish is the rich inflectional system associated with the [+AGR] INFL element. In pro-drop languages therefore, the verb is inflected for person, number and sometimes gender and Case features which agree with the implied subject. In view of this, Chomsky (1981(a):241) claims that

The intuitive idea is that where there is overt agreement, the subject can be dropped, since the deletion is recoverable. In Italian-type languages, with a richer inflectional system, the element AGR permits subject-drop while in French-type languages, it does not.

According to Cowper, with the richly inflected verb form,

the information which would be carried by the subject pronoun is also present on the verb. Thus, the subject pronoun is, in some sense, redundant (Cowper 1991:186).

We have noted that the verb in pro-drop languages is inflected for person, number, gender, and case features inherited from the morphologically rich $[-\text{AGR}]$ INFL element. Igbo on the contrary, is deficient in inflectional morphology. In the absence of a morphologically spelt-out features of agreement in Igbo, we suggest that the language makes use of an abstract $[-\text{AGR}]$ INFL element for person, number and Case features.

With the foregoing discussion as a preamble, consider the derivation of example (104b) as follows:

105 (a)

(b)

It does appear that the D-structure configuration (105a) satisfies the conditions that are compatible with Principle A of the Binding Theory. The subject pro is assumed to inherit the abstract agreement $[+AGR]$ features of person, and number of the pronominal clitic -nu. Hence pro and the pronominal clitic are coindexed. This is because "the element AGR is basically a nominal, and shares the person and number features of the subject" (Chomsky 1986(a):52). Consequently, the pronominal clitic -nu counts as the coindexed m-commanding antecedent of the reflexive anaphor ònwè unù. The verb wèrè functions as the governor for the reflexive anaphor ònwè unù. The anaphor is therefore bound in accordance with Principle A

of the Binding Theory. At the level of D-structure where antecedent-anaphor relations are assumed to hold for the Igbo null subject imperative sentence-type, the examples in (104) do not counter-exemplify Principle A of the Binding Theory.

We now turn to the S-structure configuration in (105b). Following Chomsky (1986(b):4-5) we adopt the V to I movement analysis which is determined by morphological Principles. By this verb-to-INFL movement (a head-to-head movement involving X^0 categories V and I), the verb acquires the $[+Tns, +AGR]$ properties associated with INFL (Radford 1988:410). Subsequently, the pronominal clitic -nu is incorporated into the verb wèrè, thereby forming a morphologically complex predicate. The trace of the moved V "must be properly governed, and since the movement is local, this proper government must be by antecedent-government, not θ -government" (Chomsky 1986(b):69). Hence, the trace of V (t_j) is antecedent-governed by the moved V (wèrè_j). No ECP violation is involved.

The licensing of the null-subject pro in (105b) creates a fundamental problem for the ECP. Once again, we adopt a strategy analogous to the licensing of subject-pro in pro-

drop languages. In Napoli's (1991) review of Roberge (1990) on the licensing of null arguments in Romance, it is claimed that the null arguments can be licensed by $[+\text{AGR}]$ and clitics. This argument is based on the assumption that the $[+\text{AGR}]$ and clitic exhibit the relevant features of person and number, and sometimes the gender and Case features of person and number, and sometimes the gender and Case features associated with the null-argument. As Napoli (1991) then asserts that:

a verb could have a null argument only if there is some syntactically realized element that will allow access to all the relevant information about the null argument. Since lexical pronouns in Romance languages are feature-bundles for person, number, gender and Case, only if this set of features can be recovered about a null argument will the null argument be licensed. (Napoli 1991:637).

Based on the licensing of null arguments in Romance languages like Italian, we claim that in the Ìgbò null-subject imperative sentence, the pronominal clitic (-nu or -Ø), is encoded with the abstract $[+\text{AGR}]$ features of person and number which can be recovered about the null-subject pro. We also claim that the Case feature of the pronominal clitic is part of $[+\text{AGR}]$ features, since "AGR can be associated with only one Case (that of the subject)"

(Napoli 1991:638). Therefore, the null pronominal subject in (105b) is claimed to be licensed by the $\langle \bar{+}AGR \rangle$ INFL element because the subject is governed and Case-marked by the $\langle \bar{+}AGR \rangle$ INFL element. It is argued that for the pro-drop parameter $\langle \bar{+}AGR \rangle$ is a proper governor due to the expression of its 'rich' morphological features on the verb (Riemsdijk and Williams 1986:302). For Igbo, a non pro-drop language, as well as a language deficient in inflectional morphology, we assume that the $\langle \bar{+}AGR \rangle$ INFL encodes an abstract number, person, and Case features on the verb and the pronominal clitic -nu/-Ø. In this way, the notion of proper government has to be parameterized to accommodate the licensing of the null subject in both the pro-drop and non pro-drop languages. In view of this Riemsdijk and Williams conclude that:

The ECP, supplemented with the parameterized definition of AGR, yields a highly general and simple account of an entire cluster of properties by which pro-drop languages differ from non-pro-drop languages (Riemsdijk and Williams 1986:303).

3.5 The Reciprocal Anaphor

Like the reflexive anaphor, the reciprocal is constrained by Principle A of the Binding Theory. But a reciprocal anaphor is used to designate a symmetry between the actions or relations of the members of the relevant antecedent.

It is on account of this plurality of participation that the antecedent of a reciprocal anaphor must always be plural. There is need to add that a mutual action or relationship expressed in a reciprocal relation exists between the antecedent and the anaphor. As is rightly claimed by Kyellmer (1982:241).

If a reciprocal pronoun is used, what is stated in the sentence is as true of A with regard to B as of B with regard to A.

Now consider the sentences below:

106. (a) Ụmù_i m nà-ènyere ònwè ha_i aka
 Children my Aux-give-Ben poss them hand
 "My children help each other"
- (b) Unù_i nyèèrè ònwè unù_i aka n'ọrụ
 You-pl give-pst-Ben poss you-pl hand in work
 "You helped each other at the job"
- (c) Ndi Ìnyòm_i ahụ bèrè ònwè hā_i ñkọ
 Those women that vilify-pst poss them vilification
 "Those women vilified each other".
- (d) Ànyị_i chọrò [kà/anyị_i ghọta ònwè anyị_i]]
 IP
 We want that we understand poss we
 "We want to understand each other"

(e) *Nwaànyị̀_i ahụ̀ tòrò ònwe hā̀_i

Woman that extol-pst poss them

The reciprocal anaphors in (106a-c) are bound in accordance with Principle A of the Binding Theory. Take sentence (106a) for example. The reciprocal anaphor ònwe hā̀ has a coindexed m-commanding antecedent Unù as subject of the sentence, and the verb nye (give) as governor. Both the antecedent and anaphor agree in number. In (106d) the reciprocal anaphor ònwe ānyị̀ is bound in the subordinate clause. It is in this governing category that the anaphor has a coindexed m-commanding antecedent ānyị̀ and a governor, the verb ghọta. We will return to example (106d) to examine the binding of the subordinate clause pronominal subject ānyị̀. The string in (106e) is ungrammatical. The anaphor ònwe hā̀ and the coindexed m-commanding subject nwaànyị̀ ahụ̀ do not match in terms of number agreement. A reciprocal anaphor requires an antecedent which denotes a set of two or more entities. The m-commanding subject of the reciprocal anaphor in (106e) is singular, contrary to the stipulation of the Matching Condition (107) below:

107. If two NPs are assigned the same index, they must 'match' in features (e.g number, gender, person, etc)
(Radford 1981:366, 198:1b).

Example (106e) is therefore ruled out by the stipulation in (107) because the reciprocal anaphor and the potential antecedent do not 'match' in terms of number.

Now consider the binding of the pronominal subject anyi of the sub-ordinate clause in (106d). The subordinate clause subject anyi is coindexed with an m-commanding antecedent which is the subject of the matrix clause. The matrix clause subject is also the pronominal anyi. The subordinate clause is the governing category for the pronominal subject of this clause. The $[+Tns, +AGR]$ INFL is the governor for the subordinate clause subject anyi. There is no coindexed m-commanding antecedent for the subordinate clause pronominal subject anyi within this clause. Thus, in accordance with Principle B of the Binding Theory, the subject anyi of the subordinate clause is free in its governing category. However, the subordinate clause pronominal subject anyi is bound in the matrix clause. In the matrix clause, the pronominal subject anyi functions as the coindexed m-commanding antecedent of the subordinate clause pronominal subject anyi. Nevertheless, both the reciprocal anaphor and the pronominal subject of the subordinate clause share the matrix clause subject as antecedent by means

of Transitivity (cf section 1.3 (18)).

It is necessary to point out that the sentences in (106a-d) ^{are} ambiguous. For instance, the reciprocal interpretation of sentence (106a) could have a reflexive reading. This seems to be the case when the antecedent Umú m of the reciprocal anaphor onwe hā is interpreted distributively, as individuals in a set, rather than as a set of entities. Under this interpretation, example (106a) would be construed as (108).

108. Nnwa_i m òbùlà nà-ènyere onwe yā_i aka
 Child my each Aux-give-Ben poss him hand
 "Each of my child helps himself"

The reciprocal reading is preserved when the antecedent of the reciprocal anaphor in (106a-d) is interpreted as a set of entities.

3.6 Ergatively Derived NP-trace as Anaphor.

This section deals with the anaphoric status of NP-trace. We examine the claim that an NP-trace in ergative structures is subject to Principle A of the Binding Theory, just like the reflexive and reciprocal anaphors. Our attention will be focused on NP-trace derived from ergative structures.

An ergative structure occurs just in case the sentence involves an ergative verb. Such verbs are defined in Chomsky (1981(a):72) as "verbs that subcategorize for a formal NP object but do not assign case to it". Thus, an ergatively derived structure is "an intransitive clause which has a transitive counterpart in which the transitive object corresponds to the ergative subject" (Radford 1988: 446). In his analysis of ergativity in Modern Hebrew, Kaddari (1973) states as follows:

This ambivalent syntactic behaviour is dependent on (a system of) logical (contextual) and formal (syntactical) relations which can be discovered and described (Kaddari (1973:390)).

This characteristic whereby a subset of verbs can function either transitively or ergatively has also been observed in Igbo.⁸

The sentences below exemplify ergatively derived structures in Igbo.

109. (a) $\frac{\text{Mmanu } \bar{m}}{\text{NP}} \text{ } \bar{7}_i \text{ kwafurù } t_i$
 Palm oil my spill-pst t
 "My palm oil got spilt"

⁸ cf Nwachukwu (1983:108).

- (b) Ahĩa_i zùrù t_i n'obom ùnyàahù
 Market buy-pst t in square yesterday
 "There was a market transaction at the village square yesterday"
- (c) Ebelebe_i gbùrù t_i ebe ahù
 Wonder kill-pst t place that
 "Wonders were performed there"
- (d) [̄Elekere íse]̄_i nà-àkù t_i ugbu à
 Hour five Aux-knock t now
 "It is now five O'clock"
- (e) Ògelè_i àkùola t_i n'ogè taà
 Gong knock-perf t in time today
 "The gong has sounded early today"

To illustrate the derivation of an ergative construction, we assume that the configurations in (110a) and (110b) represent the D-structure and S-structure, respectively, of (109a).

110. (a) $\left[\begin{array}{c} \bar{\ } \\ \text{IP} \end{array} \left[\begin{array}{c} \bar{\ } \\ \text{NP} \end{array} \text{NPe} \right] \left[\begin{array}{c} \bar{\ } \\ \text{VP} \end{array} \left[\begin{array}{c} \bar{\ } \\ \text{NP} \end{array} \text{kwafùrù} \left[\begin{array}{c} \bar{\ } \\ \text{NP} \end{array} \text{mmanu} \bar{\ } \right] \right] \right] \right]$
 NPe spill-pst palm oil my

(b) $\left[\begin{array}{c} \bar{_} \\ IP \end{array} \right] \left[\begin{array}{c} M\text{many } \bar{m} \\ NP \end{array} \right] _i \left[\begin{array}{c} R\text{wafurù} \\ VP \end{array} \right] \left[\begin{array}{c} t_i \\ NP \end{array} \right] \right]$

Palm oil my spill-pst

"My palm oil got spilt"

As (110b) shows, NP-movement is involved. By this movement, the D-structure object becomes the derived subject by moving into the base-generated empty $\left[\begin{array}{c} \bar{_} \\ NP, IP \end{array} \right]$. Two independent principles account for this movement. They include the Extended Projection Principle, and Case Theory (Chomsky 1981(a):49). As we have noted in section 2.4, the Extended Projection Principle ensures that every clause must have a subject (Radford 1988:552). Hence, the base-generated empty subject position (as illustrated in 110a) serves as host for the D-structure object which becomes the derived subject in (110b). The effect of the Case Theory 2.6 on the movement of the D-structure object will be explored in section 3.8.1 below.

The claim that an NP-trace is an anaphor comparable to the reflexive and reciprocal anaphors need exemplification. Let us assume that the object NP-trace in (110b) has the entire sentence as its governing category, a feature shared by the reflexive anaphor in (100a) and the reciprocal in (106a). Within this governing category, the verb kwafù

governs the NP-trace in object position. The NP-trace is thus properly governed, and so the ECP is not violated. In addition, the derived subject many $\bar{m}$, which is coindexed with the NP-trace by movement, functions as the m-commanding antecedent for the NP-trace. Hence, the NP-trace is said to be bound to its antecedent within its governing category.

The foregoing analysis has shown that an NP-trace, such as we find in examples (109a-e), is analogous to the reflexive and reciprocal anaphors. An NP-trace and the reflexive and reciprocal anaphors have the same type of governing category (IP) within which they are governed. They also must have a coindexed m-commanding antecedent within the governing category. As a result of these features which an NP-trace shares with the reflexive and reciprocal anaphors, we conclude that the relationship between an NP-trace and its antecedent is that of bound anaphora (Cowper 1992:86). The relationship naturally leads to the interesting generalization that NP-traces, reflexive and reciprocal anaphors, are subject to Principle A of the Binding Theory.

3.7 The Emphatic Pronoun

In terms of morphological structure, the emphatic Pronoun, and the reflexive/reciprocal anaphors in Igbo share

a common form. Like the personal pronoun, the emphatic pronoun, and reflexive/reciprocal anaphors, share the features of person and number agreement with their antecedent. Structurally, the emphatic pronoun immediately follows its antecedent. It can optionally be adjoined to the end of the clause that contains it.

In Igbo, the emphatic pronoun can be interpreted and glossed in English as 'personally'. Consider the following sentences with the emphatic pronoun in subject position (111a), object position (111b), subject position of an embedded clause (111c) and in a VP adjoined position (111d).

111. (a) ʔAda_i nà ʔonwe yā_i zipurù ha
 Ada by poss her send off-pst them
 "Ada herself sent them off"
- (b) I zùrù ʔObi_i nà ʔonwe yā_i n'ɣzò
 You meet-pst Obi by poss him along road
 "You met Obi himself along the road"
- (c) ʔ chòrò [kà unū_i nà ʔonwe unū_i bia zùte yā_i]
 He/She want that you-pl by poss you-pl come meet him
 "He/She wants you yourselves to come and meet him."

(d) Àda_i zipùrù ha nà ònwe yā_i

Ada send off-pst them by poss her

"Ada sent them off by herself"

For instance, (111a) implies that Àda and no one else, sent them off.

The morphological properties which the emphatic pronoun shares with the reflexive and reciprocal anaphors, together with the person and number agreement features they all have in common with the personal pronoun, have given rise to the question as to whether the emphatic pronoun is constrained by either Principle A or B of the Binding Theory.

If the emphatic pronoun is an anaphor, it will be constrained by Principle A of the Binding Theory. In (111a) for example, we assume that the emphatic pronoun has the entire string as its governing category. Within this domain, the emphatic pronoun ònwe yā has Àda as its m-commanding coindexed antecedent. But there is no governor for the emphatic pronoun within its assumed governing category. Principle A of the Binding Theory therefore does not apply to the emphatic pronoun in (111). Hence, the emphatic pronoun is not an anaphor.

Assuming that the distribution of the emphatic pronoun patterns that of the personal pronoun, then the emphatic pronoun will be constrained by Principle B of the Binding Theory. Within the noun phrase [$\bar{A}da_i$ $n\grave{a}$ $\grave{o}nwe$ $y\bar{a}_i$] in (111a) which serves as the governing category, the emphatic pronoun has a coindexed m-commanding antecedent but lacks a governor. More importantly, the antecedent is located within the governing category, rather than outside it. Thus, the emphatic pronoun is not constrained by Principle B of the Binding Theory. It is therefore not a pronominal.

Having dispensed with showing that the emphatic pronoun is neither an anaphor nor a pronominal, we now examine the structural features of the emphatic pronoun in relation to its antecedent. Basically, the emphatic pronoun occurs in a morphologically complex NP which may be headed by a noun or a pronoun which agrees in number and person with the emphatic pronoun. Example (111a) is represented in the configuration (112) below:

112.

In (112) the emphatic pronoun bnwe yā is structurally an adjunct,⁹ in relation to the head Ada. Oluikpe (1989:73-76) describes the emphatic pronoun as a "reflexivized appositive structure". We claim that the emphatic pronoun is an adjunct because it can be deleted without any syntactic change.

⁹An adjunct phrase position is a modifier position "attached to a head' upon which it is dependent and from which it can be detached without any consequent syntactic change in the sentence" (Lyons 1968:344).

Examples (113a-c) have no emphatic pronouns, like their analogous (111a-c).

113. (a) Àda zipùrù ha

Ada send off-pst them

"Ada sent them off"

(b) I zùrù Òbi n'uzò

You meet-pst Obi along Road

"You met Obi along the road"

(c) Ọ chòrò [kà unù bia zùte yā]

He/She want that you-pl come meet him/her

"He/She wants you to come and meet him/her."

Sentences (113a-c) are grammatical, even when the emphatic pronoun is detached from its head. Sentences (111a) and (113a) basically express the same notion. The only difference between the two sentences is that of emphasis. In example (111a) the emphatic pronoun merely serves to pick out the head of the phrase (Àda) as the one who personally performed the action described by the verb.

There is a morphological resemblance between the preposition¹⁰ na and the conjunction na. This similarity

¹⁰This preposition na, which we gloss as by in English, is assumed to bear the semantic feature [+comitative] in the sense of Fillmore (1968:81).

seems to suggest two things. The first is that the emphatic pronoun and its head constitute a coordinate structure, while the second suggests that the na is equally a conjunction, like the conjunction na. The deletion of the emphatic pronoun without any loss of grammaticality in the examples of (113) provide contrary evidence on the coordinate structure status of the emphatic pronoun and its head. Furthermore, compare the feature of number agreement between the coindexed subject and object positions in sentences (114a) and (114b).

114. (a) $\angle^{-}\text{Ugò nà } \text{Ojì } \text{ghòtára} \angle^{-}\text{ònwe hā} \text{]}_i$
 Ugo CONJ Oji understand poss them

"Ugo and Oji understand each other"

(b) * $\angle^{-}\text{Ugò nà ònwe yā} \text{]}_i \text{ghòtára} \angle^{-}\text{ònwe hā} \text{]}_i$
 Ugo COMIT herself understand poss them.

In the grammatical (114a) the coordinate structure subject agrees in number with the reciprocal anaphor. Example (114b) is ungrammatical as a result of the number - agreement conflict between the non-coordinate subject and the anaphor. Thus, the ungrammatical (114b) provides further evidence against the coordinate structure status of the emphatic pronoun and its head as well as the comitative na as a conjunction.

It is important to note that the deletion of the emphatic pronoun in the sentences of (113) has not violated the Case Filter (49), and the θ -Criterion (53). We assume that Case is not assigned directly to the emphatic pronoun. Whatever Case the containing NP is assigned percolates to the emphatic pronoun. The θ -Criterion (53) correctly predicts that no independent θ -role is assigned to the position where the emphatic pronoun occurs. Rather, θ -role is uniquely assigned to the NP position headed by the antecedent of the emphatic pronoun. By virtue of the θ -Criterion (53) one would justifiably conclude that by its structural position in the sentence, the emphatic pronoun is an adjunct, occupying a non-argument position in relation to the head of the NP that contains it (Chomsky 1986(b):16).

At the beginning of this section, we stated that the emphatic pronoun can optionally be adjoined to the end of the clause. Like the optional deletion of the emphatic pronoun in (113a-c), its adjunction in (116a-c) does not constitute an ungrammatical sentence. This adjunction of the emphatic pronoun constitutes another evidence for its non-conjoined interpretation.

116. (a) Àda t_i zipùrù hà nà ònwe yā_i
 Ada t send-off-pst them by poss her
 "Ada sent them off herself"
- (b) Ọ chòrò [kà unù t_i bịa zùte yā
 He want that you-pl t come meet him
 nà ònwe unù;]
 by poss you-pl
 "He wants you to come and meet him yourselves"
- (c) [Ugò nà Ọjì t_i] kpòtàrà [hà t_j]
 Ugo and Oji t bring-pst them t
 [nà ònwe hā]_{i/j}
 by poss them
 "Ugo and Oji brought them themselves"

The emphatic pronoun in (116a-c) forms an adjunction structure with the IP. In other words, the emphatic pronoun in these examples has been extraposed to the end of the sentence.

This is illustrated in the configuration (117), to represent example (116a).

117.

The emphatic pronoun onwe ya in (117) forms an adjunction structure with the IP. This conforms with the requirement on adjunction which specifies that an extraposed constituent is adjoined to the first maximal projection above the constituent out of which the extraposed constituent is extracted (Radford 1988:451). This requirement agrees with Chomsky's (1986(b):6) view that adjunction be restricted to non argument maximal phrases. When an NP is an argument,

adjunction to that NP is ruled out.

The question now is how to ensure the licensing of the trace left by the extraposed emphatic pronoun in examples (116a-c). As indicated by the grammatical sentences of (116) the trace of the extraposed constituent does not violate the ECP. In (116a) represented as (117) the emphatic pronoun is adjoined to the right of IP from where it m-commands and antecedent-governs its trace (Haegeman 1991:409).

The representation in example (116c) is ambiguous. This ambiguity can be resolved by tone as in the following configurations (118a) and (118b). The two readings of (116c) are interpreted as follows:

- (a) When the head of the subject Ùgò nà D̀jì is the referential source of the extraposed emphatic pronoun, the pronominal object ha bears a low tone.
- (b) When the head of the object ha serves as the referential source of the extraposed emphatic pronoun, the pronominal object ha bears a high tone.

These two interpretations of (116c) are reflected by the structural positions of the emphatic pronouns, relative to their respective heads as in (118a) and (118b).

118. (a)

(b)

At this juncture, we subject the emphatic pronoun to a focus test.¹¹ In view of the morphological resemblance which the emphatic pronoun shares with the personal pronoun and the reflexive/reciprocal anaphors, the focus test will provide additional proof that there is a difference between them.

¹¹See section 4.3 for a detailed account of the focus construction.

119. (a)

O zìgàrà m̀ ahĩa

He send-off-pst me market

"He sent me to the market"

(b)

O bù yā_i [t_i zìgàrà m̀ ahĩa]

It be him t send-off-pst me market

"It was he who sent me to the market"

(c)

O bù m_i [kà o zìgàrà t_i ahĩa]

It be me that he send-off-pst t market

"It was me that he sent to the market"

120. (a)

Àda_i zìgàrà ònwe yā_i skuùl

Ada send-off-pst poss her school

"Ada was responsible for giving herself formal education"

(b)

O bù ònwe yā_i [kà Àda_i zìgàrà t_i skuùl]

It be poss her that Ada send-off-pst t school

"It was herself that Ada was responsible for providing formal education"

121. (a)

Ogú_i nà ònwe yā_i zìgàrà Àda skuùl

Ogu by poss him send-off-pst Ada School

"Ogu himself was responsible for sending

Ada to school"

121. (b) $\emptyset$ bù Ogu_i nà ònwe yā_i [$\bar{t}_i$ zìgàrà Àda skuùl]
 It be Ogu by poss him t send-off-pst Ada school]
 "It was Ogu himself who was responsible for
 sending Ada to school"

(c) * $\emptyset$ bù nà ònwe yā_i [$\bar{Ogu}$ t_i zìgàrà Àda skuùl]
 It be by poss him Ogu t send-off-pst Ada school]

The (b) and (c) examples in sentences (119) - (121) are the cleft forms of those in (a). The traces of the focused constituents will be considered in relation to the ECP (cf section 2:10). In other words, we want to determine to what extent the traces are licensed.

The personal pronoun subject trace in (119b) is antecedent governed by ya in [$\bar{Spec}, CP$]. There is no barrier between the subject NP-trace and its antecedent, hence the trace is properly governed. In like manner, the object NP-trace is lexically governed by the verb zìga in (119b). The pronominal traces in (119b-c) are thus licensed by antecedent government in (119b) and lexical government in (119c). The focusing of the personal pronoun as shown in (119b) and (119c) does not lead to ECP violation.

Consider the focused reflexive anaphor ònwè yā and its object trace in (120b). The object trace in (120b) is lexically governed by the verb zìga. Thus licensed, the object trace in (120b) observes the ECP. Again, this has shown that the reflexive anaphor can be focused.

Example (121b) is an instance of the focusing of the emphatic pronoun with its antecedent in $[-\text{Spec}, \text{CP}]$. The trace of the focused constituent is antecedent-governed by the constituent Dgù nà ònwè yā in $[-\text{Spec}, \text{CP}]$. Thus, the subject NP-trace in (121b) is properly governed, hence no constraint is violated. Example (121c) is ungrammatical because the emphatic pronoun ònwè yā is focused alone, without the head Dgù. Consequently, the resultant trace is not licensed. The NP Dgù constitutes a barrier to antecedent-government. This means that the extraction site of the trace in (121c) is not L-marked, in the sense of the Barriers framework where L-marking is defined as follows:

122 α L-marks B iff α is a lexical category, and α directly θ -marks B (Chomsky 1986(b):15). It follows from (122) that the subject position in (121) is not L-marked. The only option left for the trace in (121c) to be properly governed is that of antecedent-government. This option is exemplified in the case of the subject trace in (121b).

But this is not possible in (121c) because the non-L-marked subject Ogù constitutes a Blocking Category defined as follows in (123) below:

123. Y is a blocking category for B iff:
 Y is a maximal projection, and
 Y is not L-marked, and
 Y dominates B

(Chomsky 1986(b):14)

We deduce from (122) and (123) that in (121c) the subject Ogù (Y) is a Blocking Category which constitutes the barrier that prevents antecedent-government from holding between the emphatic pronoun in $[-\text{Spec}, \text{CP}]$ and its trace (B) in subject position. Hence, the lack of proper-government for the trace in (121c) results in an $\bar{\text{CP}}$ violation. This accounts for the ungrammaticality of (121c).

In this section, we have been able to prove that the emphatic pronoun lacks a governing category in the sense of the Binding Theory (see section 2.11), even though, like the pronominal and the reflexive/reciprocal anaphors, it shares the person and number agreement features with its antecedent. The deletion and VP adjunction facts in (113) and (116) respectively, lend further support to our claim that the emphatic pronoun is an optional constituent,

"which is not required by the verb and to which the verb does not assign a-θ-role" (Cowper 1992:142). Finally, clefting has given conclusive proof that the emphatic pronoun cannot be focused, just like the personal pronoun and the reflexive/reciprocal anaphors can be focused, even though they all share morphological and person and number agreement features in common.

3.8 Verbs Associated with Anaphora

A number of Ìgbò verbs contribute to the establishment of anaphoric relations. Such verbs include a subset of transitive verbs which are referred to as ergative verbs. Others are reflexive and reciprocal verbs. We shall examine a sample of each of these verbs in terms of their Lexical Thematic Representation. We will argue that the Lexical Thematic Representation of the verb specifies the the sentence options which the verb can provide.

3.8.1. Ergative and Transitive Features of Some Ìgbò Verbs

It will be insightful to examine the nature of Ìgbò verbs that exhibit both ergative and transitive features. The knowledge about the nature of these verbs will help in throwing more light on the choice between an ergative structure or a transitive one. Having defined an ergative verb in section 3.6, we now define a transitive verb.

In traditional terms, a transitive verb makes a predication about two participants in which the second participant is a direct object complement (Stockwell 1977:52).

Haegeman (1991) defines a transitive verb as

a verb which has two arguments and assigns two θ -roles... Such a verb must be able to case-mark its complement NP (Haegeman 1991:297).

Consider the transitive verbs in examples (124a-e).

These verbs have their ergative variants in (109a-e).

124. (a) Ewu gĩ kwafùrù mmanụ m̄

Goat your spill-pst palm oil my

"Your goat spilt my palm oil"

(b) Ànyị zùrù ahịa n'obom ùnyàahụ

We buy-pst market in square yesterday

"We had market transactions at the village square yesterday"

(c) Ha gbùrù ebelebe ebe ahụ

They kill-pst wonder place that

"They performed wonders there"

(d) Kùlọ̀òkù nà-àkụ elekere Īse ùgbu à

Clock Aux-knock hour five now

"The clock says it is now five o'clock"

- (e) Ndi ñche akuola ogelè n'ogè taà
 Those vigilante knock-perf gong in time today
 "The vigilante group has sounded the gong early today"

For example, sentence (124a) has the following D-structure configuration (124).

125.

As illustrated in (125), the object NP complement mmanu m remains in situ. Its movement is blocked because there is no empty subject position to host it, since the subject position has been filled by the NP ewu gi. This is not the case with the ergative structure (110a) where the base-generated empty subject is subsequently filled at

S-structure by the subcategorized object NP complement
mmanu m̄.

The choice between the ergative or transitive construction is determined by the verb's Lexical Thematic Representation. The verb kwafù in (109a) and (124a) has (126) as its Lexical Thematic Representation.

If the verb kwafù is intended to be used transitively, the θ -role assignment option in (126(i)) is selected. This option allows that the verb bears two argument positions. The first argument position is assigned an Agent θ -role, while the second bears the θ -role Theme. Sentence (124a) illustrates this option. In (126(ii)), the verb kwafù has only one argument position which bears the Theme θ -role. Since the Agent role is assumed to have been suppressed, the Thematic Hierarchy (65) crucially determines the choice of subject in order to satisfy the Extended Projection Principle. Consequently, the principle that governs the Thematic Hierarchy (65) applies and the Theme surfaces as the derived subject. The selection of

option (126(ii)) is exemplified by sentence (109a).

We shall now consider the effect of Case (cf section 2.6) on the D-structure object of a ^{verb}specified for the ergative option. Though ergative verbs θ -mark their object complement, it is believed that they lack the potential for assigning Accusative Case to their D-structure object NP complement (Belletti 1988:6). Thus, the D-structure object is forced to vacate its position. This object then moves into the base-generated empty subject position where it is assigned Nominative Case at S-structure by the $\bar{A}$ Tense, +AGR-7 INFL, hence there is no violation of the Case Filter (49) (Levin and Rappaport 1986:645). The following constituency test is a validation of this assumption.

127. (a) Mmanụ m̄, ò kwafùrù?
 Palm oil my it spill-pst
 "Did my palm oil spill"
- (b) ò kwāfùrù
 It spill-pst
 "It got spilt"
- (c) *Ya kwafùrù
 It spill-pst

(d) Ewu gī kwafurù ya

Goat your spill-pst it

•Your goat spilt it•

The derived subject mmanu m̄ in the ergative structure of (110a) is questioned in (127a). As a response, the questioned constituent is substituted for by the Nominative case form of the third person singular pronoun subject o in (127b). This contrasts with the ungrammatical (127c) where the questioned constituent is substituted for by the Accusative Case form of the third person singular pronoun ya as subject. In the transitive clause (109a) the object mmanu m̄ is substituted for by the Accusative case form of the third person singular pronoun ya in (127d). Hence (127d) is grammatical.

Apart from distinguishing the ergative-transitive use of a verb on the basis of its Lexical Thematic Representation as in (126) further distinction is made in terms of the active-stative parameter. It is argued that when a verb is used ergatively, it describes a state or change of state, but when it is used transitively, the verb describes an activity (Li 1993:486). For instance, the transitive use of the verb kwafu in (124a) describes an activity performed by the subject ewu gī, in consonance

with its θ -role function. Conversely the ergative variant kwafù in (109a) describes a state or change of state undergone by the derived subject mmanụ m̄, as determined by its θ -role.

3.8.2. Reflexive Verbs

It is assumed that in Ìgbò, as well as in other languages, there are verbs "which depict actions which one can perform on oneself in contradistinction to others which a person cannot perform on himself" (Uwalaka 1988:70). Thus, languages make use of verbs which depict actions performed by an Agent NP which revert to that same NP. Verbs which belong to this class are referred to as reflexive verbs. Such verbs however may or may not take the reflexive anaphor as object. The list below is a sample of reflexive verbs in Ìgbò.¹²

¹²Examples (124 a-g) are adapted from Uwalaka (1988:71:72)

128. (a) (a) $\dot{\text{i}}\text{k}\dot{\text{p}}\dot{\text{u}} \text{ àf}\dot{\text{u}} \text{ ɔn}\dot{\text{u}}$ to shave beard
 (b) $\dot{\text{i}}\dot{\text{j}}\dot{\text{i}}\text{k}\dot{\text{e}}$ to dress up
 (c) $\dot{\text{i}}\text{s}\dot{\text{a}}/\dot{\text{i}}\text{gh}\dot{\text{u}} \text{ àh}\dot{\text{u}}$ to bathe
 (d) $\dot{\text{i}}\text{t}\dot{\text{e}} \text{ ùde}$ to rub pomade
 (e) $\dot{\text{i}}\text{m}\dot{\text{a}}/\dot{\text{i}}\text{j}\dot{\text{e}} \text{ akw}\dot{\text{a}}$ to tie a wrapper
 (f) $\dot{\text{i}}\text{y}\dot{\text{i}} \text{ àf}\dot{\text{e}}/\dot{\text{u}}\text{we}$ to put on clothes
 (g) $\dot{\text{i}}\text{b}\dot{\text{o}}/\dot{\text{i}}\text{h}\dot{\text{a}} \text{ isi}$ to comb hair
 (h) $\dot{\text{i}}\text{s}\dot{\text{u}}/\dot{\text{i}}\text{k}\dot{\text{e}} \text{ ìch}\dot{\text{a}}\text{f}\dot{\text{u}} \text{ is}\dot{\text{i}}$ to put on a head tie
 (i) $\dot{\text{i}}\text{k}\dot{\text{o}} \text{ ɔk}\dot{\text{o}}$ to scratch itches
 (j) $\dot{\text{i}}\text{k}\dot{\text{p}}\dot{\text{o}}\text{b}\dot{\text{i}} \text{ ɔkw}\dot{\text{u}}$ to hit a toe against
 an object
 (k) $\dot{\text{i}}\text{s}\dot{\text{o}}\text{j}\dot{\text{i}} \text{ aka/}\dot{\text{u}}\text{kw}\dot{\text{u}}$ to fracture the
 hand/leg
 (l) $\dot{\text{i}}\text{h}\dot{\text{i}} \text{ aka n'anya}$ to rub the eye

In this section, we will examine the case of reflexive predication. We will examine the Lexical Thematic Representation of a reflexive verb, in relation to the choice of object complement. Now consider the following sentence trio as represented in (129) - (131).

129. (a) $\text{Òbi n}\dot{\text{a}}\text{-}\dot{\text{a}}\text{k}\dot{\text{p}}\dot{\text{u}} \text{ àf}\dot{\text{u}} \text{ ɔn}\dot{\text{u}}$
 Obi Aux-shave beard
 "Obi is shaving beard"

(b) Òbi nà-àkpụ ònwe ya àfù ọnụ
 Obi Aux-shave poss him beard
 "Obi is having himself of his beard"

(c) Òbi nà-àkpụ gị àfù ọnụ
 Obi Aux-shave you beard
 "Obi is having your beard"

130. (a) Àda gà-àsa āhụ
 Ada will-wash body
 "Ada will take a bath"

(b) Àda gà-àsa ònwe ya àhụ
 Ada will-wash poss her body
 "Ada will bathe herself"

(c) Àda gà àsa ụmụ unù àhụ
 Ada will wash children you-pl body
 "Ada will bathe your children"

131. (a) Ha tèrè ùde isì ọma
 They rub-pst pomade smell beautiful
 "They rubbed pomade with a sweet fragrance"

(b) Ha tèrè ònwe hā ùde isì ọma
 They rub-pst poss them pomade smell beautiful
 "They rubbed pomade with a sweet fragrance on
 themselves"

(c) Ha tère Kraist ùde isi oma

They rub-pst Christ pomade smell beautiful

"They rubbed pomade with a sweet fragrance on
Christ"

The (a) and (b) sentences in (129) - (131) have a reflexive interpretation. In the (a) examples, the verb does not take the reflexive anaphor as complement, but it does so in the (b) sentences. Examples (c) of sentences (129) - (131) have no reflexive reading. The verb however takes an object complement in exactly the same position as in the (b) sentences. The inherently reflexive characteristic of the verb in the (a) sentences of (129) - (131) is such that even in the absence of the reflexive anaphor, the verb depicts an action by the subject which reverts to the same subject. Thus, in this context, the action described by the verb is said to be implicitly reflexive. However, pragmatic or context dependent factors can necessitate the inherently reflexive verb to take the reflexive anaphor as its object complement. The (b) sentences in (129) - (131) exemplify this option. The presence of the reflexive anaphor in the (b) examples merely serves to make these sentences more emphatic than their counterparts in the (a) sentences. This emphatic feature is necessary when, for instance (129a) could be interpreted as "Obi is having his beard shaved by the barber".

As Uwalaka (1988:73) rightly observes, the (a) sentences in (129) - (131) represent the unmarked construction because even in the absence of a reflexive anaphor it is the reflexive interpretation that is intended. Conversely, the co-occurrence of the reflexive verb with the reflexive anaphor as object in the (b) examples represents the marked construction. There is need to point out that an abstract or implicit reflexive anaphor $\emptyset$, an empty category, is assumed for the (a) examples in exactly the same position where the reflexive anaphor occurs in the (b) sentences of (129) - (131). As an empty category the abstract reflexive anaphor $\emptyset$ must be licensed. We assume that since it occurs in object position, it is properly governed by the verb which governs and θ -marks the position.

The binding of a reflexive anaphor in a sentence involving a reflexive verb is illustrated with example (129b), repeated here as (132).

132. Òbi_i nà-àkpụ ònwe ya_i àfù ọnū

Obi Aux-shave poss him beard

"Obi is shaving himself of his beard"

The sentence in (132) serves as the governing category for the reflexive anaphor ònwe yā. Within this domain, the

subject Òbi is the coindexed m-commanding antecedent for ònwé yā. The reflexive anaphor ònwé yā is in addition governed and Case-marked by the verb kpy. Hence, ònwé yā is bound in accordance with Principle A of the Binding Theory. The same analysis as in the case of (132) is postulated for similar examples.

It is possible to find instances where the reflexive verbs in (128) are used in the non-reflexive sense. The (c) examples in (129) - (131) represent this usage. In these examples, the verb describes an action by the subject which affects someone else.

It is necessary to draw our attention to a certain class of verbs which appears to counter exemplify our definition of a reflexive verb. The verbs include.¹³

- | | | | |
|------|-----|------|------------|
| 133. | (a) | irī | to eat |
| | (b) | inū | to drink |
| | (c) | ilō | to swallow |
| | (d) | ikpō | to sniff |
| | (e) | irā | to lick |

The verbs in (133) belong to a restricted set of verbs which we here refer to as verbs of "ingestion".

¹³These are verbs that involve taking food (both solid and fluid) into the body.

Consider examples 134a-b).

134. (a) $\dot{A}$ da riri nri
 Ada eat-pst food
 "Ada ate some food"
- (b) Unu kpòrò anwùrù ndi ọgọ anyị
 You-pl sniff-pst snuff-powder those inlaws our
 "You sniffed the snuff-powder from our inlaws"

The action performed by the subject Ada in (134a) also reverts to the subject. In other words, the action of eating performed by Ada started and ended with her. This seemingly reflexive connotation is exemplified in (134b) where the action performed by the subject NP Unu also reverts to it. Unlike the reflexive verbs in (128), the verbs in (133), as exemplified in (134), cannot take the reflexive anaphor as object. Consider the ungrammatical strings in (135) below.

135. (a) * $\dot{A}$ da riri ònwe yā nri
 Ada eat-pst poss her food
- (b) *Unu kpòrò ònwe unù anwùrù ndi ọgọ anyị
 You-pl sniff-pst poss you-pl snuff-powder
 those inlaw our.

perhaps, the inability of the set of ingestive verbs in (133) to co-occur with the reflexive anaphor as object disqualifies them from the class of reflexive verbs. Thus, the verbs in (133) do not actually serve as counter-evidence to our definition of a reflexive verb as they would appear at first glance.

The sentence trio as represented by examples (129) - (131) can be accounted for by the Lexical Thematic Representation of a given reflexive verb.

We therefore claim that the choice of any member of the trio in (129) - (131) can be derived from the verb's Lexical Thematic Representation. The verb isā āḥu in (128c) is illustrated with the following representation in (136).

The representation in (136a) shows that the verb sa āḥu can take a non-overt reflexive anaphor $\emptyset$ as its object. By this choice, the Theme associated with this abstract or non-overt reflexive anaphor has no lexical representation

at S-structure. Hence, the Theme is enclosed in parentheses. This option takes care of the (a) examples in (129) - (131), representing the unmarked construction. Example (136a) also shows that a reflexive verb can take the reflexive anaphor as its object. In this regard, the Theme is lexically realized at S-structure. The (b) examples which represent the marked structure adopts this option. As illustrated in (136b) the feature [=Ref1] associated with the object of the verb shows that the verb sa āhy, and the members of its class, can be used in the non-reflexive sense. This is exemplified by the (c) sentences of (129) - (131). We conclude therefore that the choice of (136a) leads to the constraints imposed by Principle A of the Binding Theory.

3.8.3. Reciprocal Verbs

Igbò has a restricted set of reciprocal verbs. The characteristic feature of these verbs is that the participant NPs in the activity, event, or state described by the reciprocal verbs are both the subject and the object. Therefore, a reciprocal verb defines a mutual relationship between the participant NPs. In other words, a reciprocal verb "refers to a property which may be predicated only of a set" (Miller 1971:56). A representative sample of

reciprocal verbs in Ìgbò are as follows:

137. (a) iyĩ to resemble
 (b) izù to meet
 (c) inōkètà to be adjacent to
 (d) ibì omà to embrace
 (e) igbà okè to share a boundary
 (f) ihà to be equal
 (g) igbā izù to talk privately or whisper to
 (h) ikpā nkàta to engage in a conversation
 (i) igbā mgbà to wrestle
 (j) ilù ògù to fight

In the discussion that follows, the nature of the reciprocal relations expressed by some of these reciprocal verbs will be considered. As the main focus of this section, we will attempt to show the binding of the reciprocal anaphor in a sentence with a reciprocal verb. The lexical Thematic Representation of a given reciprocal verb will be examined so as to enable us account for the choice of object complement. Finally, a generalization will be made with respect to the abstract S-structure representation of the reflexive and reciprocal anaphors.

The following sentences illustrate a reciprocal relationship.

138. (a) Àda nà Ùgò yìrì
Ada and Ugo resemble
"Ada and Ugo are alike"
- (b) Àda nà Ùgò yìrì ònwe nā
Ada and Ugo resemble poss them
"Ada and Ugo resemble each other"
- (c) Àda yìrì Ùgò
Ada resemble Ugo
"Ada resembles Ugo"
- (d) Ùgò yìrì Àda
Ugo resemble Ada
"Ugo resembles Ada"
139. (a) Mụ nà Ogù zùrù n'ụzò
I and Ogu meet-pst along road
"Ogu and I met along the road"
- (b) Mụ nà Ogù zùrù ònwe ānyị n'ụzò
I and Ogu meet-pst poss we along road
"Ogu and I met each other along the road"
- (c) Ezùrù m Ogù n'ụzò
Meet-pst I Ogu along road
"I met Ogu along the road"

(d) Ogu zùrù ì n'uzò
 Ogu meet-pst me along road
 "Ogu met me along the road"

140.

(a) Gị nà Ezè ngkètàrà n'oche
 You and Eze sit-adjacent-to on seat
 "You and Eze sat adjacently on the seat"

(b) Gị nà Ezè ngkètàrà ònwe unù n'oche
 You and Eze sit-adjacent-to poss you-pl on seat
 "You and Eze sat adjacent to each other on the seat"

(c) I ngkètàrà Ezè n'oche
 You sit-adjacent-to Eze on seat
 "You sat adjacent to Eze on the seat"

(d) Ezè ngkètàrà gị n'oche
 Eze sit-adjacent-to you on seat
 "Eze sat adjacent to you on the seat"

The set of verbs in (137) are inherently reciprocal. The reciprocal reading prevails even when in the sentence, the verbs take an abstract or non-overt reciprocal anaphor $\emptyset$. This is exemplified by the (a) sentences of (138) - (140), which are analogous to the reflexive verb constructions in (129) - (131) of section 3.8.2. Thus, examples (a) of

(138) - (140) represent the unmarked construction. In the (b) sentences of (138) - (140), the reciprocal verb takes a reciprocal anaphor as object. These examples parallel the (b) sentences involving the reflexive verb in (129) - (131). Similarly, the reciprocal construction with the reciprocal anaphor as object represents the marked structure.

A paraphrase relationship exists between the (a) and (b) sentences of (138) - (140) on the one hand, and the (c) and (d) sentences on the other. These (a) and (b) sentences enter into a relationship of entailment¹⁴ with those of (c) and (d) which have a singular subject. Thus, the reciprocal verbs in (138) - (140) are said to be symmetrical. The term symmetrical refers to "Sentences which express certain semantic relations, and to certain pairs of sentences which have the same truth value..." (Boadi 1975:97).

We now illustrate the binding of the reciprocal anaphor with example (138b) above. The entire IP in (138b) serves as the governing category for the reciprocal anaphor ònwé hā. Within this domain, the subject Àda nà Ùgò serves as the coindexed m-commanding antecedent for the reciprocal anaphor. The reciprocal anaphor is in turn governed and Case-marked by the verb yi.

¹⁴ Entailment is a semantic dependence which holds between one utterance and another. A relation of entailment is easily translatable into terms of truth and falsehood. To say that X entails Y means that if x is true, then y is also true, and vice versa. Thus, for example, if (134a) is true, then (134c) and (134d) are also true.

Principle A of the Binding Theory is satisfied, hence the reciprocal anaphor ònwe hā is bound to its antecedent Àda nà Ùgò. As in (a) examples of the reflexive verb construction in (129) - (131), we postulate an abstract reciprocal anaphor $\emptyset$ for the (a) sentences in (138) - (140) in exactly the same position where the reciprocal anaphor occurs in the analogous (b) sentences.

Three sentence varieties are associated with the verb in (138) - (140). The choice of any one of the varieties can be determined from the verb's Lexical Thematic Representation. For instance, the reciprocal verb yi in (137a) can be associated with the following Lexical Thematic Representation (141).

The choice of (141a) provides for two sentence varieties: (138a) which is the unmarked construction, and (138b) which represents the marked structure. The subject position occupied by the external argument is assigned the θ -role Theme. In addition, the external argument is specified

for the feature [$\bar{+}$ Set]. This feature implies that the subject position should be filled by a coordinate NP, or its equivalent pronominal form. The internal θ -role Goal is not realized at S-structure when the reciprocal anaphor is abstract or has null representation as in (138a). The reciprocal anaphor may surface at S-structure as the object of the reciprocal verb, with the θ -role Goal.

Also the choice of (141b) accounts for two sentence options. These options are the (c) and (d) sentences of (138) - (140). By the choice of (141b), the verb yi can select either of the participant arguments as subject or object. The subject position is θ -marked as Theme, while the object position is assigned the θ -role Goal. The object is the argument on the basis of which the subject is assessed. Because the reciprocal verb yi is a symmetric verb, it can feature in a construction involving subject-object switching (Uwalaka 1988:43). In the (c) and (d) examples of (138) - (140) the subject and object can be switched round.

These arguments so switched do not carry their θ -roles along them, since θ -roles are assigned to argument positions, rather than to arguments themselves (Speas 1990:10). It is assumed that two positions can exhibit the subject-object

switching phenomenon when they have an equal number of entailed θ -role properties (Dowty 1991:576). Hence, the two arguments in the (c) and (d) sentences in (138) - (140) seem not to be distinguished from each other by what the verbs in the respective sentences entail.

It appears that an important generalization can be made with respect to the inherently reflexive and reciprocal verbs. We have postulated in section 3.8.2, and also in this section, that at S-structure, reflexive and reciprocal verbs can take an abstract or null reflexive and reciprocal anaphor as object. The null anaphor occurs in exactly the same position where the lexicalized reflexive, or reciprocal anaphor occurs at S-structure.

We assume that as an unrealized term at S-structure, the abstract reflexive and reciprocal anaphor $\emptyset$ belongs to the set of empty categories. If this assumption holds, then the abstract reflexive and reciprocal anaphor must be licensed. In other words, the abstract reflexive, and reciprocal anaphors $\emptyset$ in the (a) examples of (129) - (131) and (138) - (140) are subject to the ECP (section 2.10).

The position in which the abstract reflexive and reciprocal anaphors occur in their respective sentences is a governed and Case-marked position. Consider the (a) and (b) examples of (129) and (138), represented in the

following tree diagrams as (142) and (143) respectively.
 Each of the tree diagrams stands for the (a) and (b) sentences.

142.

143.

The configurations in (142) and (143) show that both the abstract and lexicalized reflexive and reciprocal anaphors occur in object position. Thus, both the abstract and lexicalized anaphors are governed by their respective verbs. In the unmarked construction represented by the (a) examples of (142) and (143), the abstract reflexive and reciprocal anaphors $\emptyset$ are properly governed by the verbs kpu and yi. No ECP violation is involved in the sentences represented by examples (1) of (142) and (143), hence their grammaticality.

3.9 Summary

We investigated a sample of Igbo data in the light of the Binding Theory. The data are made up of a number of sentence types associated with antecedent-anaphor relations - reflexive and reciprocal anaphors. The result of the investigation shows that so far, the Binding Theory can account for instances of anaphoric relations associated with the data.

This chapter also considered the nature of verbs which are associated with anaphors. We examined the Lexical Thematic Representation of such verbs and argued that this representation specifies the choice of sentence types in which a given verb can feature.

CHAPTER FOUR

APPARENT COUNTER EXAMPLES

4.0. Preliminaries

In this chapter, we investigate instances where some of the basic assumptions about Case-marking and binding theory in standard G-B syntax seem to be contradicted. First, we consider the anaphoric status of the logophoric pronoun in Ìgbò. Secondly, we examine a set of infinitival clauses. Each of the infinitival clauses seems to have a lexical subject which occurs in a position that lacks a potential governor and Case assigner. Thirdly, the binding of anaphors in [Spec, CP] will be examined. Finally, we present and account for a set of sentences in which anaphors occur in subject position.

4.1 The Logophoric Pronoun

The logophoric pronoun is defined by Hyman and Comrie as a:

Special pronoun or set of pronouns used to indicate coreference with an individual(s) whose speech or point of view is reported in a direct discourse (Hyman and Comrie 1981: 19).

Thus, "logophoric pronouns appear predominantly within

sentential arguments of predicates of communication and mental experience" (Sells 1987:445). The use of the logophoric pronoun is not restricted to Ìgbò. It is found in such languages as Greek, Gokana, Ewe, and Yoruba, among others (Enc 1989:77). The logophoric pronoun is not limited to the third person singular, and also to the subject position as is the case in Ìgbò.

In Ìgbò, the logophoric pronoun is morphologically similar to the separable¹⁵ third person singular pronoun ya. The third person pronoun is the pronoun of "the person referred to but not addressed" (Robins 1964:210). When used as subject, this pronoun usually gives rise to ambiguity when its reference is not uniquely specified. To this end, languages adopt various strategies to resolve such ambiguity. The use of the logophoric pronoun is one of the strategies which Ìgbò and other languages adopt.

The following set of verbs provide the context for the occurrence of the logophoric pronoun.

¹⁵The separable pronouns are not restricted to the subject position. They can occur as subject, or object. They can also occur after a noun in a genitival relationship (Igwe and Green 1964:14).

144.	(a)	si	say
	(b)	kwu	talk
	(c)	gwa	tell
	(d)	kowa	explain
	(e)	ju	ask
	(f)	kwe	agree, believe
	(g)	ma	know
	(h)	ju	refuse
	(i)	nu	hear, perceive
	(j)	ghota	understand
	(k)	chè	think
	(l)	cho	want, desire

The verbs in (144) are representative of predicators of communication (144a-e), and predicators of mental experience (144f-l).

Carrell (1970:55) presents an interesting account of the logophoric pronoun in Igbo from the Transformational-Generative view point. Carrell claims that in a biclausal sentence, two base-generated nominal phrases which are [-plural], share "the same extra linguistic referent", and the second nominal phrase obligatorily undergoes a pronominalization transformational rule. This transformational rule is optional only when the two nominal phrases "have

different referents" (Carrell 1970:55). The following examples (145) and (146) are taken from Carrell (Ibid).

145. (a) Jɔn_i gwàrà m̀ nà Jɔn_i rìrì jì
 "John told me that John ate yams"
 (b) Jɔn_i gwàrà m̀ nà ya_i^{*16} rìrì jì

The matrix clause subject corefers with the subordinate clause subject in (145a). Thus, the subordinate clause subject is pronominalized as ya. This pronoun ya bears a formal semblance to the third person singular separable pronoun ya. The subordinate clause pronominal subject ya in (145a) is barred from undergoing a transformational rule which will convert it to the subject pronoun form o/p (Carrell 1970:55).

It is possible for the base-generated subject of both the matrix and subordinate clauses to be disjoint in reference. Examples (146a-c) illustrate this.

146. (a) Jɔn_i gwàrà m̀ nà Àda_j rìrì jì
 "John told me that Ada ate yams"

¹⁶ As Carrell (1970:55) claims the asterisk on the pronoun subject of the subordinate clause in (145b) prevents the pronoun from "undergoing the general subject pronoun" transformational rule.

(b) $J\text{on}_i$ gwàrà ì nà ya_j rìrì jì $\Rightarrow$
 "John told me that she ate yams"

(c) $J\text{on}_i$ gwàrà ì nà o_j rìrì jì
 "John told me that she ate yams"

The matrix clause subject Jon in (146a) is disjoint in reference with the subordinate clause subject Ada. The subordinate clause subject Ada pronominalizes as ya in (146b), parallel to (145b). In (146b) the subordinate clause subject ya bears no asterisk, hence it is not excluded from the general subject pronoun transformational rule. Consequently, ya in (146b) is derived as o in (146c) by the general subject pronoun transformational rule. (Carrell 1970: Ibid).

Through Carrell (1970:55) did not use the label "logophoric pronoun" for the subordinate clause pronoun subject ya in the analysis of (141b), she however showed that the language makes use of such a feature as the logophoric pronoun. Carrell's Transformational-Generative approach to account for the logophoric pronoun in Igbo has been overtaken by recent developments in linguistic theory. Her transformational analysis of pronominalization shares the same fate with Lees and Klima's (1963) transformational (cf section 1.2.). More recent Transformational-Generative theories, essentially Jackendoff (1972) and Chomsky's G-B

framework (1981, 1986) have presented a better account of pronominalization.

Having examined Carrell's (1970:55) analysis of the Ìgbò logophoric pronoun, we now present our own analysis within the theoretical framework of this study. In the sentences that follow, examples (a) illustrate the use of the logophoric pronoun, examples (b) illustrate the use of the non-logophoric pronoun. These exemplify the use of the singular form of the logophoric/non-logophoric pronoun.

147. (a) Àda_i sì [̀nà ya_i gà-èje ah_ia]]
 Ada say that she will - go market
 "Ada said that she would go to the market".
- (b) Àda_i sì [̀nà o_j gà-èje ah_ia]]
 Ada say that she will go market
 "Ada said that she would go to the market"
148. (a) Òbi_i mà [̀nà ya_i erūtegh_i n'ogè]
 Obi know that he rach-not in time
 "Obi knows that he did not arrive on time"
- (b) Òbi_i mà [̀nà o_j rutēgh_i n'ogè]
 Obi know that he reach-not in time
 "Obi knows that he did not arrive on time"

149. (a) Govānò_i gwàrà hà_j [kà ha_j pùta
Governor tell-pst them that they come-out

[Mgbè ya_i gà-àlafè]]]

When he will-return

"The governor told them to come out

When he would be coming back".

(b) Govānò_i gwàrà hà_j [kà ha_j pùta [mgbè o_k

Governor tell-pst them that they come out when he

gà àlafè]]]]]

will return

"The governor told them to come out when he

would be coming back".

The (a) and (b) sentences of (147) - (149) make a contrasting pair. The contrast is as a result of the source of reference for the subject of the subordinate clause in these sentences.

In (147a), the logophoric pronoun ya is the subject of the subordinate clause. The subject of this subordinate clause uniquely refers to the matrix clause subject Ada, hence they are coindexed. The converse of (147a) holds for (147b).

The non-logophoric pronoun o is the subject of the subordinate clause in (147b). This subordinate clause pronominal subject o does not refer to the matrix clause subject Ada, but refers freely or arbitrarily to someone else.

Let us investigate whether Ìgbò makes use of the plural logophoric pronoun. The sentences in (150) - (152) are the plural version of the (a) examples in (147) - (149) above.

150. Ụmụ̀àgboghò_i sì Ẹ̀nà ha_{i/j} gà-èje ahịa Ẹ̀
 Ladies say that they will go market
 "The ladies said that they would go to the market"
151. Ẹ̀Òbi nà enyì ya Ẹ̀_i mà Ẹ̀nà ha_{i/j} erūteghì
 Obi and friend his know that they reach-not
 n'ogè Ẹ̀
 in time
 "Obi and his friend know that they did not arrive
 on time".
152. Ndi gọvānò_i gwàrà hà_j Ẹ̀kà ha_j pùta
 Pl governor tell-pst them that they come-out
 Ẹ̀Mgbè ha_{i/j} gà - àlafè Ẹ̀ Ẹ̀
 When they will return
 "The governors told them to come out when they
 would be coming back".

The (a) examples in (147) - (149) show the occurrence of logophoric pronouns, coindexed with the matrix clause subject. Since sentences (150) - (152) are used as the plural version of the (a) sentences of (147) - (149) we expect that the plural logophoric pronoun will occur in exactly the same

position as in the singular sentence form. Contrary to expectation, logophora breaks down in examples (150) - (152), since the pronominal form that occurs is ambiguous in reference. In (150) for example, the pronoun ha (they) can refer to the matrix clause subject (umùàgboghò) or it can have an arbitrary reference. Hence, logophoricity in Ìgbò is limited to the singular pronominal form.

We now examine some data from Yoruba, a language closely related to Ìgbò. Yoruba exhibits a similar paradigm as represented in the Ìgbò sentences of (147) - (149).

153. (a) Kòlá_i sọ [pé òún_i wá]
"Kola said that he came"

(b) Kòlá sọ [pé ó_j wá]
"Kola said that he came"

The Yoruba logophoric pronoun òún in the subordinate clause subject position in (153a) corefers with the matrix clause subject Kòlá. In (153b) the matrix clause subject Kòlá and the subordinate clause pronominal subject ò are disjoint in reference.

The English language adopts a different strategy from Ìgbò and Yoruba. English makes use of stress as a strategy for avoiding any ambiguity inherent in the use of the third

person singular pronoun he in the subordinate clause subject position as shown in the following examples.

154. (a) Peter_i said [_T that he_i had never been so confused_T]

(b) Peter_i said [_T that he'_j had never been so confused_T]

The subordinate clause subject he in (154a) would have been ambiguous as to its source of reference if the language lacked the device for resolving such an ambiguity. In (145a) the subordinate clause pronoun subject he refers specifically to the matrix clause subject Peter. "He is thus unstressed ... because it is coreferential to the non-pronominal noun phrase Peter" (Langacker 1972:295).

It is crucial at this point to address the issue of the anaphoric status of the logophoric pronoun in terms of the Binding Theory as sketched in section 2.11. From this discussion we determine which of the principles of the Binding Theory actually constrains the distribution of the logophoric pronoun in the language. In (147a), for instance, the subordinate clause is the governing category for the logophoric pronoun subject ya. As subject, the logophoric pronoun ya is governed and assigned Nominative Case by the [_T +Tns, +AGR_T] INFL of the subordinate clause. There is however no coindexed m-commanding antecedent for the logophoric pronoun in the sense of Principle A of the Binding Theory.

Though the logophoric pronoun ya has a coindexed m-commanding antecedent Ada in the matrix clause subject position, it is free in its governing category. Since it is free in its governing category, the logophoric pronoun ya satisfies Principle B of the Binding Theory. Hence the logophoric pronoun is a pronominal in the sense of Principle B.

It appears that both the logophoric pronoun ya and the separable third person singular pronoun ya share similarities and differences. The two pronominal forms share the same morphological shape. As pronominals, both are constrained by Principle B of the Binding Theory. In spite of these similarities, the logophoric pronoun ya and the separable third person singular pronoun ya can be distinguished.

The logophoric pronoun ya is free in its governing category but it is restricted to seeking its antecedent in the matrix clause of its containing sentence. On the other hand, the separable third person singular pronoun ya is not restricted in the choice of its antecedent. Consider the underlined third person singular pronominal form ya in sentences (155a) - (155c).

155. (a) unù gaa n'ahĩa [̄ya ēresi unù mmanu yā¹⁷]
 You-pl go in market he sell-to you-pl oil his
 "If you go to market he will sell you his oil".
- (b) Àda_i gwàrà ì [̄kà m mete yā_{i/j} [̄mà ọ bürù]
 Ada tell-pst me that I wake her if it be
 [̄nà ya_i rahùfèrè]]]
 that she sleep-surpass
 "Ada asked me to wake her in case she oversleeps"
- (c) Àda gwàrà ì [̄kà m mete yā_{i/j} [̄mà ọ bürù]
 Ada tell-pst me that I wake him/her if it be
 [̄nà ọ_j rahùfèrè]]]
 that he/she sleep-surpass
 "Ada asked me to wake him/her in case he/she
 oversleeps".

In the subordinate clause of (155a), the separable third person singular pronoun form ya occurs as subject, and possessive pronoun, in the genitival phrase mmanu yā. The subordinate clause of (155a) serves as the governing category for the pronominal subject ya where it is governed and Case-marked by

¹⁷ Example (155a) is taken from Igwe and Green (1964:14).

the [₊INS, +AGR] INFL. The subordinate clause pronominal subject ya lacks a coindexed m-commanding antecedent both in its clause and in the matrix clause. It is thus constrained by Principle B of the Binding Theory. The pronominal object ya in the subordinate clause immediately following the matrix clause of (155b) is governed and Case-marked by the verb mete. There is no coindexed m-commanding antecedent for this pronominal object within its clause. Notice that this pronominal object ya is ambiguous as to its source of reference. In (155b) this pronominal object refers to Ada, the subject of the matrix clause, and in (155c); it has an arbitrary reference. Again, Principle B of the Binding Theory licenses the pronominal object ya in the subordinate clauses immediately preceded by the matrix clauses of (155b) and (155c), respectively. The most deeply embedded clause in (155b) has the logophoric pronoun ya as its subject, hence it derives its reference from the matrix clause subject Ada.

The analysis of data from sentences (155a) - (155c) has proved that as pronominals, the logophoric pronoun ya and the separable third person singular pronoun ya are constrained by Principle B of the Binding Theory. The analysis has also shown that the logophoric pronoun in Igbo is restricted in terms of its source of reference because its antecedent is always the subject of the matrix clause. The separable third person singular pronoun can find an antecedent intra-

sententially, as is the case with the pronominal object ya of the subordinate clause immediately preceded by the matrix clause in (155b). Alternatively, this pronoun can refer arbitrarily to an antecedent outside the sentence. This is the case with the subordinate clause subject pronoun ya in (155a) and the pronominal object ya in the subordinate clause immediately following the matrix clause in (155c).

In conclusion, whereas the Ìgbò logophoric pronoun is restricted to the subordinate clause subject position, logophora in Gokana can be linked to any argument position (Enc 1989:79). In contrast to the logophoric pronoun in Ìgbò, the non-logophoric pronoun can occur as subject of its clause as in (155a), and object of a verb as in (155b) and (155c). Thus, the logophoric pronoun ya is distinct from the separable third person pronoun with which it shares an identical form.

4.2 Anaphor in Infinitive Clause with a Lexical Subject

One of the basic assumptions in G-B is that an infinitive clause does not have a lexical subject. This is primarily because the subject position of an infinitive clause is an ungoverned, and hence a Caseless position (Chomsky 1981:49). However, an abstract pronominal element PRO is postulated as the subject of an infinitive clause. Since PRO occurs in such

a position as we demonstrated in section 2.9, consequently it is puzzling to find instances where infinitive clauses occur with lexical subject and yet such sentences are grammatical. Consider the examples below:

156. (a) Ọ̀ d̄i mmā̀ b̄u Ogù is̄iri ònwe yā̀ nri

It be good be Ogu to-cook-for poss him food
 "It is good for Ogu to cook for himself".

(b) Ogù is̄iri ònwe yā̀ nri d̄i mmā̀

Ogu to-cook-for poss him food be good
 "For Ogu to cook for himself is good".

157. (a) Ọ̀ d̄i mkpā̀ b̄u ḡi ịkw̄ur̄u ònwe ḡi ụgwọ̀ akw̄ukwọ̀

It be necessary be you to-pay-for poss you debt book
 "It is necessary for you to pay for your school fees".

(b) Ḡi ịkw̄ur̄u ònwe ḡi ụgwọ̀ akw̄ukwọ̀ d̄i mkpā̀

You to-pay-for poss you debt book be necessary
 "For you to pay for your school fees is necessary".

158. (a) Ọ̀ dā̀bàrà̀ b̄u m̄ inwḕre ònwe m̄ taà̀

It proper be me to-own-for poss me today
 "It is proper for me to be free today".

(b) M inwēre ònwe m̄ taà dabàrà
 Me to-own-for poss me today proper
 "For me to be free today is proper".

159. (a) Ọ̀ dīkwāghị ya bụ ndi mmadụ itò ònwe hā
 It be-also-not it be people to praise poss them
 "It is no longer fashionable for people to praise themselves".

(b) Ndi mmadụ itò ònwe hā adīkwāghị ya
 People to praise poss them be-also-not it
 "For people to praise themselves is no longer fashionable."

The analysis of (156) - (159) will enable us determine how the lexical subject in these examples can be licensed. The issue of licensing the lexical subject of infinitive clauses is not peculiar to Igbo. As Chomsky (1981)(a):50) rightly points out, "...languages have marked rules that permit Case to be assigned to the subject of an infinitive..." For instance, English uses the prepositional complementizer for to license the lexical subject of an infinitive clause, while Hebrew adopts the preposition al (on) in roughly the sense of the English complementizer for ... (Chomsky 1981(a):140).

For Igbo, we postulate the copula verb bu¹⁸ (be) as a complementizer which is analogous to the English prepositional complementizer for. Thus, Igbo makes use of the copula verb complementizer bu for licensing the lexical subject of an infinitive clause.

The (a) and (b) sentences of (156)-(159) are mutual paraphrases. In each case, example (a) is posited as the source of (b). For the analysis, we restrict our discussion to example (156), which also generalizes over the rest of the data. As (156a) shows, Ogù is the phonetically realized subject of the embedded infinitive clause Ogù isiri ònwe yā nri. The lexical subject Ogù occurs in the context of the copula verb complementizer bu. This copula verb complementizer bu assigns Accusative Case to Ogù, hence satisfying the Case Filter. This postulation finds a close parallel in the English prepositional complementizer for. The examples are as follows:

160. (a) It would be a shame [for John to lose the game]

(b) [For John to lose the game] would be a shame.

The phonetically realized NP John functions as the subject of the embedded infinitival clause in (160) where the NP John

¹⁸We assume that the copula verb bu can assign structural Case. However, as "a semantically dummy verb" (Lyons (1968:322), the copula bu cannot assign a θ -role to its object (Chomsky 1986(a):78) Haegeman 1991:58).

occurs in the context of the prepositional complementizer for. It is assumed that both the Ìgbò copula verb complementizer bu and the English prepositional complementizer for, respectively, license the phonetically realized subject Ogù and John in examples (156a) and (160). Our analysis is supported by the claim that

PRO is in general obligatory as the subject of an infinitive by virtue of the Case Filter, but phonetically-realized NP may appear as subject if the infinitive is in the context of V- or P-... (Chomsky 1981(a):66).

Thus in Ìgbò and English the copula verb complementizer bu and the prepositional complementizer for represent V and P respectively.

The following examples confirm that the copula verb complementizer bu assigns Accusative Case to the phonetically-realized subject of an infinitive clause.

161. (a) $\text{O di mmā bu } g_i/ya_j \text{ isiri } \text{ònwe } g_i/\text{ònwe } yā_i \text{ nri}$
 It be good be you/him to cook-for pass you/pass
 him food
 "It is proper for you/him to cook for yourself/
 himself"
- (b) $*\text{O di mmā bu } i_i/o_j \text{ isiri } \text{ònwe } g_i/\text{ònwe } yā_j \text{ nri}$
 It be good for you/he to-cook-for pass you/pass
 him food

- (c) * $\emptyset$ d_i mmã kà g_i_i/ya_j isīri ònwe g_i_i/ònwe yã_j nri
 It be good that you/him to-cook-for poss you/poss
 him food.
- (d) * $\emptyset$ d_i mmã b_y g_i_i/ya_jsiere ònwe g_i_i/ònwe ya_j nri
 It be good be you/him cook-for poss you/poss him food.

Morphological Case-marking in Ìgbò is residual in the second and third persons singular pronominal forms i:g_i and o:ya respectively. Except for this set of pronouns, Ìgbò nominals lack overt morphological Case-forms (cf Table 1, section 2.b). In view of this, we substitute Ogù in (156a) with either the second or third person singular pronoun as in (161). In example (161a) the Accusative Case form of the subject g_i/ya is assumed to have been assigned by no other Case assigner than the copula verb complementizer b_y (Brody 1985:519).

Now, contrast the grammatical (161a) with the ungrammatical (161b-d). The subject of the infinitive clause in (161b) bears the Nominative Case form of the second and third persons singular pronoun i/o. As an ungoverned and Caseless position, the subject of the infinitive clause in (161b) can only be assigned the appropriate Case from its governor and Case-marker. Thus, (161b) is ungrammatical because the subject of the infinitive clause does not reflect the Case features of its governor and Case assigner.

In (161c) the copula verb complementizer by is substituted with the complementizer ka. This complementizer is not a governor, hence it is not a case marker. Even though the subject of the infinitive clause in (161c) is the same as in the grammatical (161a), example (161c) seems to be ungrammatical because the subject gi/ya is not licensed. Finally, the embedded complement clause in (161d) has a finite verb form sġere in place of an infinitive verb form isġ. The $[+Tns, +AGR]$ INFL in (161d) is supposed to assign Nominative Case to the subject of the complement clause simultaneously as the complementizer by assigns Accusation Case to the same constituent. This results in a Case conflict in the subject of the complement clause in (161d) (Chomsky 1981(a):334), hence (161d) is ungrammatical.

In example (156a) the subject position of the matrix clause Q di mmā is occupied by the expletive (or pleonastic) pronoun Q. This pronoun is not a referring expression but rather a dummy pronominal without any semantic contribution to the sentence (Haegeman 1991:53). Essentially the expletive pronoun is "Inserted to occupy an obligatory position of syntactic structure" (Chomsky 1981(a):135). The following tree diagram illustrates example (156a).

162.

As the tree diagram (162) shows, it does appear that there will be a conflict in Case assignment between by, the head of CP in (162) on the one hand, and the $[-Tns, -AGR]$ INFL of the IP Ogù isiri ònwe yā nri on the other. With regard to this, Haegeman (1991:157) argues that in an infinitive clause such as Ogù isiri ònwe yā nri, the $[-Tns, -AGR]$ INFL is the head of the IP, hence the potential governor for the lexical subject Ogù of the infinitive clause.

Furthermore, INFL defines a governing domain IP, and by the Minimality Condition (cf Section 2.5), the copula verb by cannot govern into the IP containing the infinitive clause. It is claimed: "that infinitival IP is not a barrier for outside governors" (Haegeman 1991: Ibid). Being negatively specified for the features $[-Tns]$ and $[-AGR]$, non-finite INFL is assumed to be 'too weak' to define a barrier for outside heads. For this reason, the $[-Tns, -AGR]$ INFL loses out to a stronger outside head (Haegeman 1991: Ibid). Consequently, the copula verb complementizer by is able to govern into IP and assign Accusative Case to the subject of an infinitive clause in (156a-b) and (162).

We now consider the derived structure of (156b) in the light of (163) where the infinitive clause is a preposed constituent. It should be noted that the infinitive clause

Ogù isiri ònwe yā nri occurs with a lexical subject Ogù, but lacks the copula verb complementizer by as shown below:

163.

The tree diagram (162) shows that in example (156a) the infinitive clause Ogù isiri ònwe yā nri occurs as the complement of the matrix clause verb di. We argue that this infinitive clause becomes the derived subject of (156b). By Move- α , the infinitive complement lands in the matrix clause subject position, which had been filled by the semantically null expletive pronoun O. Sequel to this

movement the copula verb complementizer by is deleted in the PF component. This is similar to the deletion of the prepositional complementizer for in English (Chomsky 1981(a):69). The following examples are from Chomsky (1981(a):Ibid):

164. (a) John wants [_S Bill to win]
 (b) John would like [_S (for) Bill to win].

The examples in (164) show that the prepositional complementizer for is obligatorily deleted in (164a), but can optionally be deleted in (164b). Chomsky's (1981(a):69) explanation for the facts of (164) is that for the matrix verbs, there is a rule for the deletion of for "in immediate post verbal position for these verbs in the PF-component".

Finally, we consider whether the anaphors in the infinitive clause of (156) - (159) are bound in accordance with Principle A of the Binding Theory. We claim that the binding of these anaphors is compatible with the Binding Theory. In the derived structure (156b) for example, the IP which is immediately dominated by the subject NP is the governing category for the anaphor ònwè yá. In addition, this anaphor has the verb si as governor, and the subject Ogù as the α -commanding antecedent. Principle A of the Binding Theory is therefore satisfied.

4.3. Anaphor in Focus-marked Position.

There are instances where reflexive and reciprocal anaphors

occur in [$\bar{\text{Spec}}, \text{CP}$] position. In Igbo, an anaphor in such a position is said to be focus-marked. Focus-marking refers to the coding of a message, relative to what is most important in the speaker's intention, and what is presupposed. According to Yiman (1988), the term focus

is used in relation to the semantic (structural) representation of a sentence.... The focus is the part which carries the information which the speaker believes to be new to his addressee. The presupposition constitutes the part which he assumes to be shared both by him and the addressee, and on which they agree as to its truth or falsity (Yiman 1988:367).

In probably all languages, various constituents can be selected for attention or focus-marked by means of a number of devices. The cleft-construction is one of such mechanisms. In clefting, the focus-marked constituent is moved into sentence initial position, in [$\bar{\text{Spec}}, \text{CP}$] position. The focus-marked constituent is usually preceded by an expletive pronominal subject o (it) plus the copula verb by (be). When the object of the sentence is focus-marked, the presupposed constituent is introduced by the complementizer ka (that), as in example (120b). The complementizer ka is however absent when the subject of the sentence is under focus (example 121b). In a focus-marked position, the anaphor structurally α -commands its antecedent, while the converse is the case when the anaphor remains in situ. The structural position of the

anaphors in [$\bar{\text{Spec. CP}}$] position vis-avis their antecedents in [$\bar{\text{NP, IP}}$] will be examined to enable us determine their relationship. In addition, we will consider the relationship between the focus-marked anaphor and its trace.

The following sentences illustrate the cleft construction in Igbo.

165. (a) $Un\bar{u}_1$ ghogburu onwe un $\bar{u}_1$ n'aghughò
 You-pl cheat-pst poss you-pl in cunning
 "You cheated yourselves".
- (b) $\bar{O}_1$ bù onwe un $\bar{u}_1$ kà un $\bar{u}_1$ ghogburu t_1 n'aghughò
 It be poss you-pl that you-pl cheat-pst t
 "It was yourselves that you cheated".
166. (a) $\bar{O}_1$ nà-àtu onwe ya $_1$ egwù
 He Aux-fear poss him fear
 "He is afraid of himself".
- (b) $\bar{O}_1$ bù onwe yā $_1$ kà $\bar{O}_1$ nà-àtu t_1 egwù
 It be poss him that he Aux fear t fear
 "It is himself that he is afraid of".
167. (a) I_1 gè-èdefū onwe g $\bar{I}_1$
 You-sg will - lead-loss poss you
 "You will lead yourself astray".

- (b) Ọ bú ònwé ọ́í kà í gá-èdufù t₁
 It be poss you that you-sg will lead loss t
 "It is yourself that you will lead astray".

168. (c) M₁ kpàrìrì ònwé m₁
 I insult-pst poss me
 "I insulted myself".

- (b) Ọ bú ònwé m₁ kà m₁ kpàrìrì t₁
 It be poss me that I insult-pst t
 "It was myself that I insulted".

169. (a) Ụmụkà₁ ahụ nà-ègbu ònwé ha₁ ọgè
 Children those Aux-kill poss them time
 "Those children are wasting their time".

- (b) Ọ bú ònwé ha₁ kà Ụmụkà₁ ahụ nà-ègbu t₁ ọgè
 It be poss them that children those Aux-kill t time
 "It is their time that those children are wasting".

The (a) sentences represent the source of the derived (b) forms. Sentence (165a) is illustrated with the tree diagram (170a), while sentence (165b) is represented with the tree diagram (170b). The discussion on the focused structures will be based on (170b).

This discussion cuts across the rest of the clefted (b) sentences of our data.

170. (a)

The object trace in (173b) is the NP-trace of the focused reflexive anaphor bnwe unù in $[-\text{Spec}, \text{CP}]$. The displaced reflexive anaphor has not violated the Subjacency Condition (cf Section 2.10). The reflexive anaphor in $[-\text{Spec}, \text{CP}]$ has crossed only one bounding node, the IP node. There is also no ECP violation as the object trace in lexically governed by the verb ghògbu. Thus, the derived (b) sentences in (165) - (169) are grammatical.

It is important to consider whether the reflexive anaphor in $[-\text{Spec}, \text{CP}]$ is constrained by Principle A of the Binding Theory. What comes to mind is how to establish a binding relationship between the displaced reflexive anaphor in $[-\text{Spec}, \text{CP}]$ and the antecedent in subject position of the derived structure. The derived structure of the (b) examples in (165) - (169) is not peculiar to Igbo. Analogous data occur in other languages like English. The sentences below are the English examples:

171. (a) John_i likes himself_i
 (b) Himself_i, John_i likes t_i

(from Lasnik and Uriagereka 1988:157).

It appears that the $[-\text{Spec}, \text{CP}]$ m-commands the subject NP position in (170b). This is because the $[-\text{Spec}, \text{CP}]$ occurs in a structurally higher position than the subject position. This view is a misconception about the two structural positions. Ordinarily, the m-command relation here is unclear and this is why a reconstruction analysis is posited (Williams 1986:289, Belletti and Rizzi 1988:313-315, Haegeman 1991:288). In this analysis example (170b) is assumed to be derived from (170a). It is argued that the subject position m-commands the $[-\text{Spec}, \text{CP}]$ in the reconstructed (170b). Based on this analysis, we claim that the binding requirements to be fulfilled by the constituents in subject and $[-\text{Spec}, \text{CP}]$

positions in (170b) had already been satisfied in (170a), with IP as the governing category for the anaphor ònwè unù. Within this governing category, the anaphor has an m-commanding antecedent unù, and the verb ghògbu as governor. Principle A of the Binding Theory is satisfied.

The reconstruction analysis is based on the assumption that the anaphoric relations in (170a) is superimposed on (170b). For this reason, Belletti and Rizzi (1988:314-315) argue that Principle A of the Binding Theory should be regarded as an 'anywhere' principle, rather than one to be satisfied only at the level of S-structure. According to them, the S-structure is an arbitrarily chosen level. Belletti and Rizzi claim that Principle A should equally be applicable at the level of D-structure even when the

application of Move- α destroys a well-formed binding configuration by extracting ... an anaphor from the c-domain of its antecedent (Belletti and Rizzi 1988-314).

With regard to the trace of the reflexive anaphor in (170b), this trace is encoded with all the syntactic properties of its antecedent ònwè unù with which it forms a chain. The trace of the focused reflexive anaphor transmits all the encoded properties viz m-command, θ -role, and AGR requirements to its displaced antecedent ònwè unù in $[^{\text{Spec, CP}}]$ through the chain

transmission mechanism (Williams 1986:289, Haegeman 1991:288). The m -command relation between the $\left[\text{Spec, CP} \right]$ and object NP-trace in (170b) is explicitly captured in Williams's (1986:289) formulation as follows:

172. X m -commands Y iff X m -commands Y or the trace of a phrase that contains Y

Based on the formalization in (172), we claim that in (170b) the subject position m -commands the derived $\left[\text{Spec, CP} \right]$ position and that the reflexive anaphor in $\left[\text{Spec, CP} \right]$ does not counter-exemplify Principle A of the Binding Theory. The $\left[\text{Spec, CP} \right]$ reflexive anaphor is bound to its antecedent in subject position via the trace of the reflexive anaphor.

4.4. Anaphor as Subject of Experiential/Psych Predicator

There is a restricted case in which the reflexive anaphor occurs as the subject of a sentence. The occurrence of a reflexive anaphor in such a position is associated with a construction type identified with certain predicators. These predicators are referred to in the literature as experiential/psych verbs (Reinhart 1983, Belletti and Rizzi 1988, Uwalaka 1988). According to Uwalaka (1988:148), "experiential/psych predicates are verbs which refer to an

entity's perception, cognition sensation, and reaction".
The list below forms a representative sample of these verbs
in Ìgbò.

173. (a) ju afō - be contented/satisfied
(b) tō gchì - be ludicrous/ridiculous
(c) me iherē - be ashamed
(d) we iwē - be angry

Each of the verbs in (173) is a V+N complex predicate. In
an Ìgbò complex predicate both the verbal and nominal
elements are semantically inseparable. The nominal element,
which may or may not be morphologically related to the verbal
element, is referred to as an inherent complement.

(IC) (Nwachukwu, 1983:109).

In the examples that follow, the reflexive anaphor occurs
as subject of the sentence.

174. (a) Ònwe yā₁ jùrù yā₁ afō
Poss him fill-stat him belly
"He feels contented with himself".
- (b) Ònwe m̄₁ nà-àtō m̄₁ ochì
Poss me Aux-sweet me laughter
"I feel ridiculous with myself"

(c) Ònwe gī₁ emegbuola gī₁ n'ìherè
 Poss you cause-finish-Perf you in shame
 "You are very much ashamed of yourself".

(d) Ònwe hā₁ nà-èwezi hā₁ iwe
 Poss them Aux-angering them anger
 "They are getting angry with themselves".

We represent sentence (174a) with the tree diagram in (175).
 The analysis of examples (174a-d) will be based on the
 configuration in (175).

175.

One discernible feature about the configuration in (175) is that the subject reflexive anaphor ònwe yā does not seem to have an *m*-commanding antecedent. In an ideal structural relationship as stipulated by Principle A of the Binding Theory, an anaphor is constrained to have an *m*-commanding

antecedent within its governing category. The IP in (175) is the governing category for the reflexive anaphor ònwè yā. Within this IP the anaphor ònwè yā is coindexed with the pronominal object yā with which it shares the relevant agreement and referential features. Observe that rather than having an m-commanding antecedent within its governing category the subject reflexive anaphor ònwè yā instead m-commands the coindexed pronominal object yā:

We assume that the pronominal object yā is θ -marked as Experiencer. The subject anaphor ònwè yā is assigned the Source θ -role. This role defines the subject anaphor as the source of the disposition associated with the Experiencer pronominal object yā. A situation where an NP that bears the Source θ -role m-commands the NP which bears the Experiencer θ -role is an aberration of the Thematic Hierarchy Condition (cf Section 2.7). By this condition, the NP position which is assigned the Experiencer θ -role should be projected to a higher structural position than the NP position which is assigned the Source role. The abnormal subject choice by the set of experiential/psych verbs represented in (173) has been reported in Uwalaka (1988:157).

The examples in (174a-d) can be paraphrased as in the following corresponding sentences.

176. (a) Afo ònwe ya₁ júrù ya₁
 Belly poss him fill-stat him
 "He feels contented with himself".
- (b) Ọchí onwe nà-àto ñ₁
 Laughter poss me Aux-sweet me
 "I feel ridiculous with myself".
- (c) Iherē onwe gí₁ emegbuola gí₁
 Shame poss you cause-finish-Perf you
 "You are very much ashamed of yourself".
- (d) Iwe ònwe ha₁ nà-ewezi hā₁
 Anger poss them Aux-angering them
 "They are getting angry with themselves".

We represent (176a) with the tree diagram in (177).

In spite of the presence of the inherent complement within the subject, it still maintains an inseparable semantic relationship with the verb ju (Uwalaka 1989:160). The relationship between the subject anaphor onwe ya and its coindexed pronominal object ya in (176a) and (177) remains the same. We thus regard the examples in (186a-d) as the stylistic variants of the corresponding sentences in (174a-d).

The spectacular thing about (175) and (177) is that in spite of the lack of m-command relation between the subject anaphor and its coindexed pronominal object, sentences (174a-d) and (176a-d) retain their grammaticality. To account for the data in (174a-d) and (176a-d), we posit two probable solutions. The first solution is based on the claim that the Experiencer object coindexed with the subject anaphor can bind the subject anaphor, even when it does not m-command the subject anaphor. It is assumed that the subject anaphor is governed and Case-marked by the $[^{-}+Ins, +AGR]$ INFL of its clause. It also bears the relevant agreement and reference features of the Experiencer object which is assumed to bind it. In other words, in the context of an experiencer/psych verb the lack of an m-commanding antecedent for the anaphor does not prohibit binding. For instance Reinhart (1983:81), Johnson

(1987:358), among others are in support of the first solution. According to Reinhart (1983:81).

The object of an experiencing verb can in many cases control a pronoun in the subject, although it does not m-command it.

The second solution proposes that the domain for the subject anaphor be minimally expanded. The expanded domain ought to contain the reflexive anaphor, as well as a governor and an m-commanding antecedent for the anaphor. Chomsky (1986(a):169) refers to this domain as a complete functional complex (CFC). This domain is said to be complete in the sense that it is within it that the S-structure m-command requirement for the anaphor is satisfied. According to Pollard and Sag (1992:262 fn 1) such a binding domain is postulated as the least maximal projection M. This projection M contains a subject and a governor for the anaphor such that for some assignment of indices to the NPs within the domain M, the anaphor is A-bound in M under that assignment. For such a domain M in the context of an experiencer predicate in Igbo, we provide the following examples.

178. (a) Ibè_i ghòtarà [nà ònwe yā_i iùrù yà_i afo]
 Ibe understand that poss him fill-stat him belly
 "Ibe understands that he is contented with himself"

(b) 0 nà-èwute m̄₁ [nà ònwe m̄₁ nà-àto m̄₁ ochi]

It Aux-upset me that poss me Aux-sweet me laughter

"It upsets me that I feel ridiculous with myself".

(c) I₁ kwētala [nà ònwe gī₁ emegbuola gī₁ n'itherē]

You agree-Perf that poss you cause-finish-Perf you
in shame

"You have agreed that you are very much ashamed of
yourself".

(d) 0 doro hà₁ anya [nà ònwe hā₁ nà-èwezi hā₁ iwe]

It clear them eye that poss them Aux-angering them
anger.

"It is obvious to them that they are getting angry
with themselves".

Let the tree diagram (179) represent example (178a).

179.

The configuration in (179) is the representation of minimally expanded domain for the subject anaphor contained in the subordinate clause. The tree diagram in (175) constitutes the embedded clause of (179). Thus, the examples in (174a-d) form the subordinate clauses of the corresponding sentences of

(178a-d). In the subordinate clause of (178) the subject anaphor onwe ya is coindexed with the pronominal object ya. Both constituents share identical agreement and referential features. The subject anaphor in addition has a coindexed nominal expression in the subject position of the matrix clause. This matrix clause subject Ibe functions as the α -commanding antecedent of the subject anaphor in the subordinate clause. In the light of this analysis, we state that the subordinate clause which contains the subject anaphor, and the matrix clause in which the subject anaphor finds a coindexed α -commanding antecedent constitute what Chomsky (1986(a):196) refers to as a 'complete functional complex'. Thus in (179) the configurationally constrained Principle A of the Binding Theory is satisfied.

We have examined the configurations in (175) and (179) in the context of a complete functional complex for the subject anaphor in (174) and (176). Within this expanded domain the subject anaphor satisfies the S-structure constraints imposed by Principle A of the Binding Theory. For this reason we suggest that the sentences of (174) and (176) are stylistic variants derived from the structure represented in (179).

The occurrence of a subject anaphor in a higher structural position than its potential binder is not limited to Igbo.

In English the "picture noun reflexive" and certain experienter verbs present a problem with the α -command condition on anaphoric binding. Examples (180a-b) and (181a-b) represent instances of "picture noun reflexive". These examples are adapted from Pollard and Sag (1992:278). To account for these sentences, we will claim that the governing category for the subject anaphor in (180a) and (181a) had been minimally expanded as (180b) and (181b) respectively.

180. (a) Pictures of each other would be on sale
 (b) The men_i knew [_S that pictures of each other_i would be on sale_S]
181. (a) A picture of himself hung on the post office wall.
 (b) John_i realized [_S that a picture of himself_i hung on the post office wall_S]

The (a) sentences of (180) and (181) are not exactly like the Igbo examples in (174a-d) and (176a-d). The subject anaphor each other in (180a), and himself in (181a) lack a coindexed nominal within their own clause, whereas their Igbo counterparts in (174a-d) and (176a-d) have a coindexed pronominal object. The (b) examples of (180) and (181) are similar to the Igbo examples in (178a-d). In these two cases, the sentence which contains the subject anaphor is subordinated to a matrix clause.

Within this matrix clause, there is a coindexed *m*-commanding antecedent for the subordinate clause subject anaphor, as well as a governor for the anaphor. This provides the complete functional complex in which the subject anaphor satisfies the *S*-structure constraint of Principle A of the Binding Theory.

The following examples illustrate the problem posed by certain experiencer/psych predicate in English. The examples are taken from Pesetsky (1987:12,130).

182. (a) Pictures of each other_i annoy the politicians_i
 (b) [_S Pictures of each other_i]_j annoy the politicians_i
 [_S PRO_i to look at [_S]_i]
183. (a) Each other's_i health worried the students_i
 (b) [_S Each other's_i health]_j worried the students_i
 [_S PRO_i to think about]_j e]_j]

The Igbo examples of (174a-d) and (176a-d), and the (a) sentences of (182) and (183) in English are similar. In these two examples, the subject anaphor *m*-commands a coindexed object. It appears that in the (a) examples of (182) and (183) from English, the Experiencer object "seems to act for binding purposes as if it *c*-commanded the subject" (Pesetsky 1987:127).

Pesetsky's (1987:127) observation is similar to ours in respect of examples (174a-d) and (176a-d), as well as those of Reinhart (183:81), and Johnson (1987:358).

Pesetsky (1987:130) proposes a solution for the command violation in the (a) sentences of (182). He argues that though these (a) examples may be used in isolation (as is the case with examples (174a-d) and (176a-d) in *igbd*) a context is "assumed" for the (a) sentences in the absence of a preceding discourse. Thus, the bracketed infinitival clause in the (b) sentences of (182) and (183) provides the "assumed" context. Within the "assumed" context the subject PRO in (182b) for instance, is controlled by the Experiencer ~~s~~-role, the politician. In turn, PRO m-commands the object [e]. It is assumed that the subject picture of each other which contains the reciprocal anaphor each other, was in the coindexed empty object position [e], "with the result that PRO is the immediate antecedent for the lexical anaphor" (Pesetsky 1987:130). Pesetsky (Ibid) claims that in the light of discourse factors, the contextually "assumed" infinitival clause is later deleted.

Two solutions have been postulated for the binding of the subject anaphor in (174a-d) and (176a-d). The first rests on

the claim that the subject anaphor can be bound by the coindexed Experiencer object. The second solution is based on the minimal expansion of the governing domain for the subject anaphor, as reflected in examples (178a-d). But a set of data in Igbo seem to counter-exemplify the second proposed solution. On account of this counter-evidence, there is need for a modification of the Binding Theory to be able to provide a single generalization which will determine the possible antecedents of anaphors in language. The following sentences constitute the counter-examples.

184. (a) Ī chōpùtala [̄nà ònwe yā_i jùrù yà_i

You find-out-perf that poss him fill-stat him

afọ]

belly

*You have realized that he is satisfied with

himself*

(b) Ha āghotala [̄nà ònwe m̄_i

They understand-Perf that poss me

nà - àtọ m̄_i ọchì]

Aux-sweet me laughter

*They have realized that I feel ridiculous with

myself*

- (c) M gwàrà hà [̀nà ònwe gī_i emegbubla
 I tell-pst them that poss you cause-finish-Perf
 gī_i n'ihērē]
 you in shame
 "I told them you are very much ashamed of yourself"

- (c) Unù ekwētàbèghì [̀nà ònwe hā_i
 You-pl believe-Perf-not that poss them
 nà-èwezi hā_i iwe]
 Aux-angering them anger
 "You have not accepted the fact that they are getting
 angry with themselves"

Sentences (174a-d) and (176a-d) are the same embedded clauses in (178a-d) and (184a-d). In all these examples, the subject anaphor *m*-commands the coindexed Experiencer pronominal object. The matrix clause of (184a-d) lacks a coindexed *m*-commanding antecedent for the subordinate clause subject anaphor. This is in spite of the fact that the governing category for the subordinate clause subject anaphor seem to have been minimally expanded, as exemplified with sentences (178a-d). Thus, the governing category for the subordinate clause subject anaphor becomes the subordinate clause. Within this domain, the subject anaphor is governed and Case-marked by the [̀+Tns, +AGR] INFL, and

is also coindexed with the Experiencer object. For the binding of the subordinate clause subject anaphor in (184a-d), we posit also the first probable solution for the binding of the subject in examples (174a-d) and (176a-d). In these examples, as well as in the embedded clause of (184a-d), the subject anaphor has the $[+Tns, +AGR]$ INFL as governor. The subject anaphor also has a coindexed Experiencer pronominal object with which it shares the relevant agreement and referential features.

From our analysis, we observe that the subject anaphor exhibits a dual property in relation to the nominal element that binds it. This has led to the postulation of two probable solutions as regards the choice of a binder for the subject anaphor. The common feature which cuts across the data in (174a-d), (176a-d), (178a-d) and (184a-d) favours the first proposed solution. The common feature is that in all these examples, the subject anaphor is governed in its own clause, and also has a coindexed Experiencer object, both of which share the relevant agreement and referential features. The second solution which provides for the minimal expansion of the governing domain for the subject anaphor, as illustrated by example (179a-d), is discarded because the

examples in (184a-d) provide counter-evidence.

It is necessary at this juncture to examine the choice of subject exhibited by the experiential/psych verbs in (174), for example. We have already noted that the Experience θ -role is higher than the Source θ -role in the Thematic Hierarchy (65). In spite of this fact, the experiential/psych verb selects the reflexive anaphor θ -marked as Source as its subject over and above the Experiencer pronominal object. We claim that this seemingly anomalous subject choice by the experiential/psych verb is possible because the subject anaphor functions as the source of the psychological disposition experienced by the pronominal object which the predicate entails to be sentient (Dowty 1991:579.) Thus, our conclusion is that the subject anaphor with the θ -role Source is ascribed the status of the most prominent argument. According to Tang (1989:118), experiential/psych verbs select the most "Prominent Argument" as the subject NP.

As for the binding of the subject anaphor of an experiential/psych verb, we agree with Rinehart (1983:81) who claims that though the Experiencer pronominal object does not θ -command the subject anaphor, it can control the reference of the said anaphor. Following Principle A of the Binding Theory,

we assume that the subject anaphor can only be bound by the coindexed pronominal object, since both of them share the same agreement features of number and person.

4.5 Summary

This chapter has examined a set of data in which Case-marking and the Binding Theory seem to be contradicted. Our investigation shows that in Igbo the logophoric pronoun is constrained by principle B of the Binding Theory. In spite of this formal resemblance with the separable third person singular pronoun object, the logophoric pronoun is restricted to the subordinate clause subject position, a position that is governed and Case-marked by $[-Tns, +AGR]$ INFL.

In the case of the lexicalized subject of an infinitive clause, we claimed that the language makes use of the 'copula verb complementizer' by to license such a lexicalized subject. This is analogous to the way English makes use of the prepositional complementizer for.

In order to account for the anaphoric relation between the derived anaphor in $[-Spec, CP]$ and the subject NP, we adopted Williams' (1986:289) reconstruction-analysis. Our claim is that though the $[-Spec, CP]$ position is structurally higher than the subject position, the subject position m-commands the

derived [$\bar{\text{Spec}}, \text{CP}$]. In addition, the subject NP serves as the antecedent of the anaphor in [$\bar{\text{Spec}}, \text{CP}$] via the trace of the displaced anaphor.

Finally, we examined the structural positions of the co-arguments of an experiential/psych verb. Our data show that the subject anaphor, θ -marked as Source, occupies a higher structural position than the Experiencer pronominal object, contrary to the Thematic Hierarchy (65) and the assumption that an antecedent should m -command its coindexed anaphor. We claimed that in spite of the higher structural position occupied by the subject anaphor, it is still bound by the coindexed pronominal object, both of which have common agreement features.

CHAPTER FIVE

SUMMARY AND CONCLUSIONS

5.0 Preliminaries

This study has primarily been concerned with formulating a generalization that will account for all the instances of antecedent anaphor relations in Igbo. We adopted a syntactic argumentation in our analysis of Igbo data involving antecedent - anaphor relations. More specifically, we have critically examined the applicability of Principle A of the Binding Theory in accounting for the configurational relationship between an antecedent and its anaphor, bearing in mind the supplementary semantic interpretation rule.

5.1 Contributions

There is no doubt that this thesis has made some significant contributions to our knowledge of Igbo syntax. This thesis has been able to describe antecedent-anaphor relations in Igbo to a degree not yet done before. The thesis has shown that total reliance on the configurational ^{approach} to our study did not provide the necessary rule mechanism that will constrain the grammar from overgeneration. We therefore proposed a semantic interpretation rule to supplement the configurational constraint. We have been able to distinguish between

reflexive and reciprocal interpretation in Igbo. The study has shown that to a large extent, the Binding Theory, supplemented ^{with} a semantic rule constraint, can predict many instances of antecedent-anaphor relations without any modification.

By employing distributional differences, the thesis has argued convincingly that the emphatic pronoun and the reflexive/reciprocal anaphors, though formally identical, are in fact different.

For the set of verbs which are associated with anaphors, the thesis claims that the Lexical Thematic Representation of such a verb should specify whether the verb can take a lexicalized anaphor or a postulated abstract anaphor as object.

As regards the lexicalized subject of an infinitive clause, we postulated the 'copula verb complementizer' bu to license such a subject. This analysis has a parallel in the analysis of the English prepositional complementizer for. We argued that the derived anaphor in [$\bar{\text{Spec}}, \text{CP}$] does not m-command the subject of the sentence even when the [$\bar{\text{Spec}}, \text{CP}$] anaphor is structurally higher than the antecedent subject. Our claim is that the subject position m-commands the

[Spec, CP] via the trace of the displaced anaphor in [Spec, CP].

Finally, we examined the structural position of the co-arguments of an experiential/psych predicate. Our study has shown that even though the subject anaphor θ -marked as Source m-commands the Experiencer pronominal object, it is still the pronominal object that binds the subject anaphor.

5.2 Conclusion

As far as we are aware, this study is the most detailed work on antecedent-anaphor relations in Igbo. Our Igbo data is largely restricted to the dialect spoken within the Orlu Local Government Area, and this, we believe, constitutes a limitation to this study. However, in the face of more data from the various Igbo dialects, there may be need to reformulate some of the basic assumptions of the Binding Theory. Thus, more fruitful results in the quest for Universal Grammar would be realized through further research.

5.3 Unresolved Problems

We have made a number of claims as to the contributions of this study. In spite of these claims the study has not adequately handled all the issues relating to antecedent-

anaphor relations in ìgbò. The study has not been able to account for the subject-choice exhibited by the psych/experiential verbs. By this subject choice, anaphors structurally m-command their antecedents which occur in a lower structural position. There is therefore the need to investigate how the G-8 framework adopted in this study can handle such a problem.

Nevertheless, the G-8 framework has enabled us to make some significant contributions to the study of antecedent-anaphor relations in ìgbò.

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